

Collection of Papers:
The Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’)
Work Environment
Version Summer 2019

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Preface

The main topic of the collection of papers is the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) work environment and the effects, if any, on organizational design, structure, management, and human resource policies.

Section One, the research papers, are titled: *Organizational Design: The Hybrid (Combined Virtual / Traditional Office) Organization*; *The Hybrid Work Environment: The Business Process Argument for Adapting Organizational Structure*; *Organizational Management in the Hybrid (Combined Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’) Transnational Organizations*; and *The Virtual Workforce: Adapting Human Resource Policies*. *

Section Two, the stand-alone literature review, assembles, and in some cases edits, the reviews from each of the research papers listed in Section One. ** The objective of this section is to summarize, synthesize, and evaluate the current knowledge, as based on literature reviews of the research papers, regarding the impact of the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) practices on design, structure, management, and human resources..

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* Note: All papers, including the stand-alone literature review, were written by Donna L. Zeller, were previously posted and are available online. The objective of this text is to offer the information collectively in one resource.

** Note: Whereas “a literature review that forms part of a research proposal or project also describes the gaps in the current knowledge that the project aims to address; a stand-alone literature review aims to summarize and evaluate the current knowledge of a specific topic” (Monash.edu, 2018).

Section One:
Design, Structure, Management, and Human Resource Policies

Organizational Design: The Hybrid (Combined Virtual / Traditional Office) Organization

Version Summer, 2018

Abstract

The overall objective is to identify changes, if any, in organizational design in United States-based hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organizations. One part of the issue is whether the existing design influences the hybrid virtual / transnational venue or if the changes introduced by the hybrid venue influence the existing design. Another possibility to be considered is that while formal designs may remain intact, the actual hybrid practices and processes portray a different organizational design. Particularly relevant to the topic on hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations is the organizational theorists’ interest in “how new organizational designs arise and become established” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). Their theories will provide the foundation for the discussion points on organizational design for the selection of case studies.

According to a 2014 PricewaterhouseCoopers survey, external global trends, such as an increase in competitors, changing customer behavior, and revamped distribution channels; will create disruptions for organizations (Neilson, Estupinan, & Sethi, 2015). In anticipation of the disruptions, Chief Executive Officers are considering changes that may be required in their organizational design (Neilson, Estupinan, & Sethi, 2015). Their anticipation is realistic because, in order to remain competitive, organizations must continually ‘fit’ both internal design and structure; in a variety of external environments. Complicating the ‘fit’ is that, in the evolving global economy, design often transcends the boundaries of organizations; e.g. to ‘fit’ laws, politics, cultures, and geography (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007; and Edwards, 2004).

Generally, from a business perspective, structural reorganization is considered before redesign. For one, structural change and outcome can be explained with visual diagrams. In contrast, changes to organizational design are more difficult to diagram and the impact on the

business is more difficult to determine (Burnes & Randall, 2016). Moreover, a successful roll-out of the new design requires alignment with strategy; while also stimulating employee commitment, building distinguishing capabilities, and attracting a worldwide customer base (Neilson, Estupinan, & Sethi, 2015). Ultimately, the test is to thrive while remaining flexible to changes that are taking place within and around the organization (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012).

Though the design plays a critical role, “less than a quarter of organizational-redesign efforts succeed. And, forty-four percent run out of steam after getting underway, while a third fail to meet objectives or improve performance after implementation” (Aronowitz, De Smet, & McGinty, 2015). Those statistics become even more compelling when considering that organizational design determines “the manner in which management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational theorists, interested in a wide range of designs, are concerned with areas such as “governance capabilities (e.g., the ability to innovate, learn, and adapt), processes (e.g., decision making), and consequences (e.g., for whom)” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). Particularly relevant to the topic on hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations is the organizational theorists’ interest in “how new organizational designs arise and become established” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). Their theories will provide the foundation for the discussion points on organizational design in the selection of United States-based hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional physical office) transnational organization case studies.

The general purpose of this research will be to identify changes, if any, in the designs of hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional physical office) transnational organizations. The hybrid transnational model was selected because of its influence on design. First, while the hybrid (virtual / traditional) operations introduce changes to the integration or coordination across key organizational systems, the hybrid environments are also known to encourage the coordination of efforts to support adaptability and flexibility. Next, the transnational model of United States-based multinational organizations was selected because of its high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation with its environment (Admin, 2009). In addition, the

components of transnational organizations, each empowered to become a source of specialized innovation, “are integrated into the overall corporate structure across several dimensions” (Reference for Business, n.d.).

The introduction of changes, the pressure for integration and differentiation, and the empowered components influence design. Whether that influence is considered to require a redesign to align internal and external environments is one issue. The other is the manner in which management achieves the right combination for the organization’s operations. (Appendix A: Bartlett and Ghoshal’s Four Models of Multinational Organizations).

Literature Review

This section is a brief overview of organizational theories and predominant theorists. The selections, applied to the discussion points section of this paper, includes classical theory, neoclassical theory, contingency theory, and modern systems theory.

Classical Organizational Theory

During the first half of the 20th Century, Classical Organizational Theory evolved to include the merger of scientific management theory; the administrative theory; and the bureaucratic theory. The major deficiency of the classical organizational theory “was that it attempted to explain people's motivation to work strictly as a function of economic reward” (Walonick, 1993).

Frederick W. Taylor’s (1917) Scientific Management Theory sought to identify the best way to organize work and to assure that this was not challenged or changed (Burnes & Randall, 2016). The Administrative Theory (1931) of James D. Mooney and Alan C. Reiley promoted that organizational structure governed by the orderly coordination of three universal principles: coordinative, scalar, and functional; “would lead to more efficient applicability to all areas of collective human effort” (Thomas, n.d.). And, Max Weber’s (1947) Bureaucratic Theory described the design of organizations as mechanical structures; largely depicted by layers of report-to hierarchies and specific functional assignments for the workforce (Burnes & Randall, 2016).

Conversely, Mary Parker Follet, a contemporary of Frederick W. Taylor, differed greatly on power and authority. Whereas “Taylor viewed power as the boss knows better than anybody

else and should scientifically analyze what his subordinates do and give them orders; Follet (1924) focused on the science of getting people to cooperate” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003). Instead of “power over, Follet believed that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003). Another Classical era theorist, Lillian Moller Gilbreth, Ph. D. Psychology, also viewed work and the workforce differently. Dr. Gilbreth collaborated with her husband, Frank, to “apply the social sciences to industrial management, emphasizing the worker rather than the nonhuman factors” (Encyclopedia Britannica, n.d.).

Neoclassical Organizational Theory

The Neoclassical Organizational Theory addressed “the most serious objections to classical theory”; e.g. the “overconformity and rigidity that squelched creativity, individual growth, and motivation” (Walonick, 1993). In essence, “neoclassical theory displayed genuine concern for human needs” (Walonick, 1993).

Philip Selznick, one of the key figures in the development of the neo-classical organization theories of the 1930s, recognized the “unavoidable reality of the emergence of informal structure” (Kraatz, 2015, p. 155). In contrast to Weber, who endorsed bureaucracies as a rational solution for the execution of long-term goals; Selznick contended that structure continually evolves from the informal order of the organization and its changing goals (Kraatz, 2015, p. 155).

Then, in the 1940s, Kurt Lewin’s “force field theory viewed people’s activity as affected by forces in their surrounding environment, or field” (British Library, n.d.). The theory “is used extensively for purposes of organizational and human resource development to help indicate when driving and restraining forces are not in balance, so that change can occur” (British Library, n.d.). In addition, Lewin’s works “covered studies of leadership styles and their effects, work on group decision-making, the unfreeze/change/refreeze change management model, the action research approach to research, and the group dynamics approach to training, especially in the form of T-groups” (British Library, n.d.).

Contingency Theory

However, in the 1950s, the development of the Contingency Theory introduced a new line of thinking. Instead of promoting one best way of organizing, “the contingency theory

proposes that organizations are most effective when the design of their structures and processes is internally coherent and fits or matches their environment” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 395). Notably, relative to the topic of this paper, research on organizational design “has largely adopted the contingency approach” (Judge & Li, 2012, p. 48).

A study by “one of the most influential contributors to the Contingency School, Joan Woodward (1950-1959), focused on the relationship between organizational structure and organizational performance” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). The results of Woodward’s comparative empirical study (1950-1959) of 100 manufacturing organizations in England indicated that the “relationship between structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). “In her later studies, Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures” (Hinings & Greenwood, 2017, p. 135). On a related note, Woodward (1965, 1980), also recognized that with advances in technology, “the entire concept of authority in industry may have to change” (p. 30).

James Thompson’s (1967) “work is a classic of contingency theory in organizational theory and essentially suggests that, for organizations attempting to act rationally, the optimal structures will be highly contingent on a large number of factors” (Acawiki, 2010). Whereas “most previous classic work from organizational theory had focused on the role of individual behavior within organizations, Thompson set organizations (and their structure) as the unit of analysis” (Acawiki, 2010).

According to the Contingency Theorists, Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), integration is “the process of achieving unity of effort”; and differentiation is “the state of segmentation of the organizational systems into subsystems” (pp. 1-30). Their theory, frequently referred to as structural contingency theory, is applied in most studies to “characterize the organization in structural terms” with regards to their environment (Foss & Saebi, 2015, p. 90). “Structural contingency theory informs the theory of organizational design by providing a comprehensive framework that relates variations in organizational design to variations in the situation of the organization (i.e., contingencies)” (Donaldson, 2006, p. 38).

Modern Systems Theory

“The foundation of the Modern Systems Theory is the principle that all of an organization’s components interrelate nonlinearly; therefore, making a small change in one variable impacts many others” (Wright, n.d.). “Another principle is that organizations operate as open systems in dynamic equilibrium as they constantly adjust and adapt to changes in their environments” (Wright, n.d.).

In addition, Modern Systems Theory recognizes that “systems are composed of processes the currency of which is information” (Charlton & Andras, 2003). Because “information is expressed in terms of a communications code or ‘language’”, “systems are therefore characterized, and may be differentiated, by their specific languages” (Charlton & Andras, 2003).

A major contributor to the Modern Systems Theory, Niels Andersen, recognized that, historically, organizations have been homophonic. That is, whereas “organizations have always used several codes in their communication, they have always had a primary codification” (IPFS, n.d.). However, Andersen notes that the homophonic organization has been replaced by the polyphonic organization “that describes itself through many codes” (IPFS, n.d.). Hence, without the “predicted hierarchy of codes”, “there is no connection between organizations and specific communication” (IPFS, n.d.). Likewise, this has created challenges for management as multiple communications, and interpretations thereof, have to be taken into account (IPFS, n.d.).

Summary

Compared to the earlier classical organization theories that were based on the bureaucratic structure, sustained by a strict hierarchy of management control of the workers; the later theories included a genuine concern for workers’ creativity, individual growth, and motivation; as well as the unavoidable reality of the emergence of the flexible, adaptable informal structure. For this paper, the informal structure includes the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional physical office) transnational organization.

Objective

The overall objective is to identify changes in organizational design in hybrid (virtual / traditional), United States-based transnational organizations. While the hybrid virtual / traditional

operations introduce changes to the integration or coordination across key organizational systems, the hybrid environments are also known to encourage coordinating efforts to support adaptability and flexibility. With a transnational strategy, “the overseas components are integrated into the overall corporate structure across several dimensions, and each of the components is empowered to become a source of specialized innovation” (Reference for Business, n.d.). “The key philosophy of a transnational organization is adaptation to all environmental situations and achieving flexibility by capitalizing on knowledge flows (which take the form of decisions and value-added information) and two-way communication throughout the organization” (Reference for Business, n.d.).

Thus, the integration across key organizational systems, the individual empowerment of each component, the adaptation to all environmental situations, and the flexibility achieved through the capitalization of knowledge flows and two-way communication influences the organizational design; e.g. the manner in which management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in the environment. Within this context, the specific issue is the effect on design due to changes, if any, that the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization introduces to operations. (Appendix B: Transnational Organization Defined).

Problem Definition

The problem is defined as the organizational design in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization. Whether the design influences the hybrid organization or if the changes introduced by the hybrid venue influence the design is one part of the issue. Another possibility to be considered is that while formal designs may remain intact, the actual practices portray a different organizational design. A related problem is to understand “how new organizational designs arise and become established” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015)

Significance of Problem.

“Organizational design is important because the ability of societies to respond to various problems depends on the availability of organizations with different capabilities” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). However, since the empirical research of the 1970s and 80s, organization

design has not been researched with any scope or depth; thereby, missing changes that may have been introduced by the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 389). Thus, the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization and its influence on organizational design requires further research (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 146). Furthermore, the number of transnational organizations transitioning to the hybrid (combined virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') setting are increasing; thereby, sustaining the need to understand the organizational design. (Appendix C: United States-based Hybrid -Combined Virtual Offsite / Traditional 'Brick and Mortar'-Transnational Organizations).

Research Questions

Whether the design influences the hybrid organization or if the changes introduced by the hybrid venue influence the design is one part of the issue. The other is to understand "how new organizational designs arise and become established" (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). The research questions are: What are the changes, if any, to the organizational design in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization? If formal organizational designs remain unchanged, do the actual practices portray a different design?

Research Method and Design

The qualitative method will be applied to describe the characteristics of the population (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). The rationale for using the qualitative design is that it will allow "the study of things in their natural settings, then attempt to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them" (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011, p. 3). From an organizational research viewpoint, the "organizational dynamics and change are major areas of interest, and only qualitative methods are sensitive enough to allow the detailed analysis of change" (Cassell & Symon, 1994, p. 1).

The exploratory, multiple case study research strategy is applicable in that there is no clear, single set of outcomes (Yin, 2003). "Widely used in organizational studies and across the social sciences", this research strategy will provide the framework for an in-depth analysis of organizational design in United States-based transnational organizations (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 3). A within-case analysis will provide "a detailed description of each case and themes within

the case” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). Then, “a thematic analysis across the cases” will be used to “search for themes that emerge as being important to the development of the phenomenon” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). The aim will be to develop an awareness about a topic where there is insufficient research and knowledge that specifically relates to organizational design in hybrid (combined virtual / traditional office) transnational organizations (Wilson, 2010).

Limitations of the Research

Generally, research is not transferred or transferable to the workplace. Rousseau (2006) has identified a ‘research-practice gap’ where organizations are less likely to use ‘evidence-based management’ that is based on rigorous research practices. Instead, managers tend to rely on past experience (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). The Bonabeau (2003) study reported that “45% of managers prefer to rely on their instincts rather than facts and figures when making business decisions...” (Snowden, 2015, p. 269). Whether that past experience provides an advantage is not always a priority; generally time is the critical factor.

Accordingly, the approach for Joan Woodward’s ‘Management and Technology, Problems of Progress Industry’ (1958) was based on “the belief that responsible officials on both sides of industry feel the need to digest and use new research material but have not the time to browse through full-length volumes” (Preface, 1958). Woodward’s objective was “to present briefly and simply the results of new research into the social, economic, and technical problems of progress--problems arising from automation and other advances in techniques, and problems of management and human relations” (Preface, 1958). Generally, the time to browse and digest new information is dependent upon the reader; therefore, for some, the length of a presentation will be viewed as a limitation of the research design.

Expected Findings

The expected findings will likely identify changes to organizational design in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations. Whether these changes are recognized is another factor to be considered. In some cases, no formal revisions to the existing organizational design are made. Hence, the actual processes may no longer reflect the existing design. In others, design changes are recognized; and the formal organizational design is changed. In that case, processes, particularly those that no longer align with the internal and

external environments, are also revised on a formal basis. Nevertheless, given the impact on productivity and profitability, revisions to design require a cautious approach to interpretation and action taken upon findings (Wilson, 2010).

Exploratory Case Studies

Whereas organizational structure is defined as the framework of the relations of jobs, systems, operating processes, people and groups making efforts to achieve the goals; organizational design is the manner in which management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization's operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in the environment (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

The following list of case studies will highlight those transnational organizations with a combined virtual 'offsite' and traditional 'brick and mortar' setting. The case studies, from a variety of sources, were selected for several reasons. One, because of the public availability of data and information. Two, because of the level of uncertainty in their environment.

The research questions are: What are the changes, if any, to the organizational design in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization? If formal organizational designs remain unchanged, do the actual practices portray a different design?

Case Studies: Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional Office) Organizations

#1: IBM

Within-Case Detailed Description and Theme Analysis

IBM's loss of its once-strong position in the industry was seen as being based on problems in the areas of decision making and knowledge generation / sharing. Hence, IBM executives determined that the best way to encourage agility and flexibility in decisions as well as to generate and share knowledge was to require virtual workers to report to traditional offices. The uncertainty in their external environment, competition, i.e. "challenges from other cloud-based vendors"; and their internal environment, processes, i.e. decision making; are contributing factors for the change in IBM's policy (Marks, 2017).

For example, IBM's decision to require 2,600 people in the Marketing Department to relinquish their virtual offices and return to a traditional office setting was based on the changes in marketing (Kessler, 2017). In essence, marketing was no longer a 'waterfall'

process where work was handed from one individual to the next. Marketing required a dynamic, proactive response to changes in the evolving, global economy. Therefore, IBM determined that working shoulder-to-shoulder would promote the real-time decisions needed to address changes in the global market. On the other hand, the 2,600 workers were still virtual to some extent in that they were required to co-locate to one of six different locations in the United States - Atlanta, Raleigh, Austin, Boston, San Francisco, and New York (Kessler, 2017).

In response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment, e.g. competition; IBM revised its organizational design. Overall, “during high times of uncertainty for organizations, greater organizational effectiveness is achieved through high differentiation coupled with high integration” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). At IBM, differentiation, was evident in the Marketing Department’s concentration on its aspect of the organization’s operations. In addition to the decision affecting the Marketing Department, IBM took a series of similar actions to accelerate the organization’s transformation to reorganize around analytics, cloud, social, local, and mobile (Kessler, 2017). Virtual workers in the “design department, security department, procurement department, and teams that work on Watson, Watson Health, Watson Internet of Things, and Cloud Development”, were also required to report to co-located traditional offices. Hence, the differentiated units were integrated “to achieve unity of effort in working toward the organization’s goal” to address changes in the global market (Business Dictionary.com, n.d).

#2: Bank of America.

Within-Case Detailed Description and Theme Analysis

Virtual employees in the Global Technology and Operations Division in the Charlotte-area offices of Bank of America were directed to report to a traditional office. Bank of America spokesman, Mark Pepitone, said the decision to “scale back its 10-year-old telecommuting program...is part of an ongoing evaluation of the Bank’s business needs as it tries to best serve customers and clients” (Roberts, 2014). According to a 2014 PricewaterhouseCoopers survey, external global trends; such as changing customer behavior, will create disruptions for organizations (Neilson, Estupinan, & Sethi, 2015). For Bank of

America, the impetus for revoking part of their virtual work policy is to better serve customers and clients.

The business process reasons for changing the 10-year policy is the “Bank’s commitment to an environment that fosters teamwork and integration” (Roberts, 2014). That commitment “includes providing opportunities for in-person collaboration and bringing employees together in the same physical space” (Roberts, 2014). According to an interview with Cathy Bessant, head of technology and operations, “there were some places in the organization...where we had over deployed” people to work from home (Rothacker & Roberts, 2015). For example, three-quarters of the workers in some teams were working from home. “When you have a distributed workforce and what you are trying to do requires collaboration”, some workers need to return to the traditional office (Rothacker & Roberts, 2015). Accordingly, Bank of America’s objective was “to build a workforce and a culture for the future, and building a culture is a very difficult thing to do if your workforce is overbalanced to working from home” (Rothacker & Roberts, 2015).

In addition to the manner in which a management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations in response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment; organizational design is also a step-by-step methodology which identifies dysfunctional aspects of workflow, procedures, structures and systems, realigns them to fit current business realities/goals and then develops plans to implement the new changes. Bank of America appears to be utilizing that methodology to determine dysfunctional aspects, realignments, and future plans. At the time of this report, only the Charlotte-area employees were affected by the decision (Roberts, 2014). According to Cathy Bessant, at Charlotte, they have finished their recall of virtual workers to the traditional office. However, “that may be fine-tuned over the next year” (Rothacker & Roberts, 2015).

#3: Microsoft.

Within-Case Detailed Description and Theme Analysis

“According to a 2017 survey by Gallup, the IT industry ranks second in the industries embracing a remote work model” (Loubier, 2017). Stacy Elliott, Executive Communications Director at Microsoft, who has worked “as a remote team member for over 14

years, believes it all comes down to effectively using a combination of virtual technologies” (Loubier, 2017). In addition to the instant contact available whenever and wherever via multiple technologies, Elliott “still believes it’s important to set up weekly conversations with your key team members and making it a point to connect with your network either over Skype or in person to keep those relationships current” (Loubier, 2017).

In order to understand the changing ways that people work and the influences on the organization, Microsoft brought “together experts from the fields of social change, workplace design, technology, public sector development and economics to identify several characteristics of businesses and organizations that are best placed to thrive in uncertain times” (Dodd, 2011). That is, Microsoft applied the concept of organizational design as a step-by-step methodology to identify aspects of workflow, procedures, structures and systems; realign them to fit current business realities/goals; and then to develop plans to implement the new changes. The methodology helped to achieve the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization’s operations to the level of uncertainty in the technology environment; as well as to integrate people, information, and technology in the hybrid venue.

#4 Honeywell.

Within-Case Detailed Description and Theme Analysis

Honeywell’s decision to ban virtual work office privileges for all employees not in sales or field service was announced “at a time of lackluster growth in the global industrial sector and at a time of restructuring” of the large New Jersey-based organization (Depass, 2016). Basically, Honeywell Executives claimed that “the change was needed ‘to encourage the high level of collaboration’” in order to outperform competitors (Depass, 2016).

The objectives for the recall of the workforce to traditional offices was to foster teamwork and promote idea sharing; as well as to encourage quicker decisions and agility “when addressing changes in the global markets” (Depass, 2016). Organizational design is a formal process of integrating people, information and technology together in the right mix to achieve objectives. In this case, Honeywell determined that it was necessary to integrate operations, including people, information, and technology; within traditional offices in order to respond to the level of uncertainty in the global environment.

Cross-Case Theme Analysis

Similarities

In three of the case studies, the manner in which management achieved the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization's operations, was to require their virtual workers to report to traditional 'brick and mortar' offices. The organizations' responses were fundamentally based on the uncertainty in their external environments. Regardless of whether the changes were recognized formally or informally, there were revisions to organizational designs to fit current business realities/goals.

For example, at IBM, several departments were affected by the decision to require virtual workers to return to the traditional offices. The combination of differentiation (marketing) and integration (teams that work on Watson, Watson Health, Watson Internet of Things, and Cloud Development) of the organization's operations were considered to be an effective response to the level of uncertainty (competition) in its external environment. Similarly, Honeywell determined that integration of its operations, including people, information, and technology within traditional offices was needed in order to respond to the level of uncertainty in the global environment.

Differences

In cases where the virtual portion of the hybrid venue was revised or revoked, there are differences in the spatial positions of the physical offices. Whereas IBM's virtual employees in the Marketing Department were co-located in six traditional offices spanning the United States, Atlanta, Raleigh, Austin, Boston, San Francisco, and New York; only the Charlotte-area employees at Bank of America were affected by the decision. That is, the IBM employees who were co-located to six offices remained, to some extent, in a virtual setting.

Discussion Points: Organizational Theories

Overview

Although the Classical Theories were best known for scientific management and bureaucratic structures, there was some recognition that organizations were flexible and that the hierarchy did not always know best. Later, the Neoclassical Theories "displayed genuine concern for human needs"; e.g. "creativity, individual growth, and motivation" (Walonick, 1993). The Contingency Theories, frequently applied in organizational design theories,

recognized “that organizations are most effective when the design of their structures and processes is internally coherent and fits or matches their environment” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 395). The principles of Modern Systems Theories recognize organizations “as open systems that operate in an open equilibrium” with “components that interrelate nonlinearly”. Thus, “making a small change in one variable impacts many others” (Wright, n.d.).

Classical Era Theorist, Mary Parker Follet (1924)

In contrast to the scientific management, bureaucratic approach of the Classical Theory Era; Mary Parker Follet (1924) “focused on the science of getting people to cooperate” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003). Instead of “power over, Follet believed that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003).

At IBM, the uncertainty in their relationship with the external environment; competition “from other cloud-based vendors”; was viewed as a result of problems in the areas of decision making and knowledge generation / sharing. In this case, IBM executives determined that the best way to encourage agility and flexibility in decisions as well as to generate and share knowledge was to require virtual workers to report to traditional offices. Fundamentally, the organization underwent a complete redesign as their longstanding virtual / traditional practices were changed. The stated reason for the redesign, particularly the development of “small, self-directed, agile teams”, located in traditional offices, was to keep up with market changes (Isidore, 2017).

Yet, the question remains as to whether IBM’s design ever fully accommodated the development of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) organization. In 2007, a report issued by IBM noted that 40% of its 400,000 worldwide employees did not work in a traditional office (Isidore, 2017). Now, “after 20 consecutive quarters of loss / decline”, IBM determined that calling remote workers back into the office would encourage interaction; that would, in turn, “lead to new business insights which increase business momentum” (Boss, 2017). Realistically, all they’ve done is “shuffle people around into different boxes, they haven’t changed behavior which is their real intention” (Boss, 2017).

Furthermore, “where people work isn’t as important as how or why they work” (Boss, 2017). Lessons on this can be drawn from the renowned SEAL teams. For SEAL teams,

deployed across the globe, “it wasn’t where they worked that fostered collaboration, it was how” (Boss, 2017). Their process included a daily, 90 minute virtual teleconference meeting of 80,000 people (Boss, 2017). Primarily, they recognized that, “much like in business, the decisions in one area impact decisions in another” (Boss, 2017). Therefore, teams relied on the daily meetings to share information such as “theater-specific intentions, lessons learned in the field, and strategic intent which reduces the telephone effect when messages get passed through the ranks” (Boss, 2017). The consistency, in the meetings held daily and in sharing information, built trust. Fundamentally, success is built on trust.

At IBM, the decision to recall remote workers to the office was to encourage interaction, communication, ideas, and to improve decision-making. While IBM has seen some improvements in these areas in their small, agile teams, the results of the redesign on the organizational level remains to be seen. Perhaps, in 1924, Mary Parker Follet identified factors that remain relevant today. The issue is not where work takes place but to “focus on the science of getting people to cooperate”; instead of “power over, believe that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003).

Neoclassical Theorist, Kurt Lewin (1940)

During the neoclassical era, Kurt Lewin’s force field theory viewed people’s activity as affected by forces in their surrounding environment, or field. For Bank of America, one force influencing revisions of their 10- year virtual work policy was to better serve customers and clients. Another driving force was to foster teamwork and integration to improve collaboration. However, articles in *American Banker* describe the forces affecting people’s activity from another perspective (Kite, 2013; and Burns & Alix, 2018). For example, Robert Voth, a managing director in Russell Reynolds Associates consumer financial services practice, noted that, “There will be a ‘price to pay’ for banks that refuse to implement remote working, as more industries embrace the concept. They will lose out on a subset of talented workers” (Burns & Alix, 2018).

According to ‘industry watchers’, “larger banks are more apt to offer remote working” (Burns & Alix, 2018). At SunTrust Banks in Atlanta, “customer calls concerning fraud are entirely remote” (Burns & Alix, 2018). And, when Natalie Bartholomew, chief marketing

officer, “joined the \$441 million-asset Grand Savings Bank in Grove, Oklahoma, she was given the option to work from home, as needed, to avoid having her burn out from a lengthy commute” (Burns & Alix, 2018).

As for forces in the surrounding environment, Voth also recognizes the “inherent struggle in building affinity and loyalty--let alone culture--if an executive and / or mid level manager is in a place where there’s zero connectivity to the bank” (Burns & Alix, 2018). Hence, “it’s important to invest in tools that will help those employees do their jobs remotely” (Burns & Alix, 2018). Fortunately, since technology and firewalls have improved, “regulators have warmed up to telecommuting at banks” (Burns & Alix, 2018).

Contingency Theorist, Joan Woodward (1950-1959)

Basically, “the contingency theory of organizational structure provides a major framework for the study of organizational design” (Donaldson, 2006). The theory is significant because “by solving organizational design problems, while also solving problems in other aspects of the organization; management can gain a competitive advantage over rival organizations” (Donaldson, 2006, p.).

For instance, renowned contingency theorist, Joan Woodward (1970), “argued that differences in the organization of work and in behavior at work could usually be traced to the immediate work situation itself” (Oxford Reference, n.d.). The behaviors include “the number of levels of management, areas of responsibilities of supervisors, division of functions among specialists, clarity with which roles and duties are defined, amount of written communication, and such like” (Oxford Reference, n.d.). The organizational design problems include the formal process of integrating people, information and technology together; e.g. organization of work and behavior at work, in the right mix to achieve objectives.

Microsoft, where the hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy remained in place, is an illustration of differences in the organization of work and in behavior at work that were traced to the immediate work situation. Rather than revoke the virtual work portion of their hybrid organization, Microsoft sought ways to understand the changing ways that people work and the influences on the organization. The results were based on outputs not inputs. In this case, at “Microsoft’s Amsterdam office—a prototype of the hybrid organization structure—sales have

increased 50% since employees have been free to work where and when they like, using mobile technology” (Dodd, 2011).

Modern Systems Theorist, Niels Andersen (2001)

Systems Theory recognizes that when changes are made in one variable, many others are affected. Thus, changes to the location of the workforce may generate unplanned results. For example, at IBM, after 20 consecutive quarters of decline, a ‘top-down’ directive was issued that required virtual workers in several divisions to return to traditional offices. The stated objective was to have teams work shoulder-to-shoulder to improve communication and collaboration in order to generate ideas and to facilitate decision-making. Realistically, the shoulder-to-shoulder teams were co-located in 6 offices located throughout the United States; therefore, to some extent, the work venue remained virtual. Another variable affected by the decision was Human Resources; the results included layoffs and voluntary attrition to avoid relocation (Kessler, 2017).

Systems Theory views communication “as a system binder, crucial for the survival and growth of the organization. Binding the subsystems together facilitates internal stability and control. By binding the total system to the external environment, communication promotes organizational growth and goal attainment” (Almaney, 1974, Abstract). However, communication as a system binder is evolving as organizational communication has changed from a ‘top down’ voice to a multilevel one with multiple avenues for input. That is, the homophonic organization, where the code formed by management is a given; has been replaced by the polyphonic organization that encourages listening for conversations from multiple venues in order to gain a broader understanding of the issues.

The communication challenges are not limited to United States-based transnational organizations. In Japan, “teleworking is a key part of the government’s work-style reform”; hence, organizations are adjusting and adapting to these changes in their environment by facilitating “communication between those clocking in from home and those at the office” (Kyodo, 2018). For example, in organizations, such as Nippon Telegraph and Telephone East Corporation, a subsidiary of telecommunications giant Nippon Telegraph and Telephone

Corporation, avatar robots are being used to smooth out the communication processes (Kyodo, 2018).

In addition, Systems Theory recognizes that organizations operate as open systems in dynamic equilibrium as they constantly adjust and adapt to changes in their environments. To illustrate, Nils Vinje, of Glide Consulting, recognized that in order to make his virtual teams more efficient, he had to “revamp his system and come up with one that worked much better for the remote workers” (Kanbanize, n.d.). Hence, Vinje did “away with traditional meetings, honed his communication and team coordination, and kept everyone in the loop” (Kanbanize, n.d.).

Recommendations for Future Research

Beginning with a study of organizational design in the traditional ‘brick and mortar’ setting may be a prudent step to take prior to transitioning to the combined virtual / traditional venue. For example, in their research of a traditional office, Knights and Sturdy identified organizational changes that resulted when processing moved from a manual system to a batch-processed, automated system. Ultimately, “a reorganization of the department, leading to the abandoning of the clerical section, which had become unnecessary...added to the disruption” (Varcoe, McNeill, & Yearly, 1990, p. 139).

While several factors contributed to the disruptions, including technology and supplemental training, the crux of the situation appears to be based on the ‘shift’ of the work from the old system to the new. That is, the job processes had changed; however, the administrative mechanisms to control and integrate work activities had not. In this case, the methodology of organizational design could have provided a framework for identifying aspects of workflow and procedures that would be affected by the automated processes. Then, the application of the methodology could have been used to realign the former workflow and procedures to the new system; as well as in developing plans for implementing changes; thereby, mitigating disruptions beforehand.

Conclusion

The issue of concern is the organizational designs in transnational organizations with hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional physical offices) policies. In this paper, the discussion

centered on those transnational organizations revising the virtual portion of their hybridity. As a result of changes to their hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy, particularly those that have been in place for a period of time, the organizational designs are transitioning. Whether the design ever accommodated the hybridity is an issue, as well.

From a business perspective, the organizations depicted in the case studies were striving to maintain their market niche. Hence, at IBM and Honeywell, with long standing policies that supported the hybrid (virtual / traditional) option, virtual workers were required to return to the traditional offices. Bank of America also recalled virtual workers; albeit a limited number from their Charlotte location. And, Microsoft's decision to maintain their hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy was made only after experts were brought together to understand the changing ways that people work and the influences on the organization.

For the most part, from a human resource viewpoint, senior level management determined that, in order to adapt to changes in the market, employees needed to work shoulder-to-shoulder in traditional offices. Fundamentally, the traditional office setting was viewed as a way to improve the communication, collaboration, and decision-making required to stay ahead of the market demands.

Ultimately, the first step is in recognizing the influence of changes on the organizational design. Then, there are the challenges in redesign; e.g. alignment with strategy, stimulating employee commitment, building distinguishing capabilities, and attracting a worldwide customer base, that need to be considered. Overall, regardless of where people work, the test of the design will be to achieve the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization's operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in the environment.

Appendix A Bartlett and Ghoshal's Four Models of Multinational Organizations

Admin (2009). Global strategies for MNCs. Christopher A. Bartlett and Sumantra Ghoshal. From <http://www.businessmate.org/Article.php?ArtikelId=13>

Transnational (Admin, 2009).

High pressure for integration - High pressure for differentiation

Strategy tries to maximize both responsiveness and integration, where knowledge and innovation is sought developed and dispersed within the entire network.

Distribution of resources is decided upon, as follows: Some are best-centralized within the home-country operation for several reasons: realize economies of scale, protect core competencies, and provide necessary management. Others may be concentrated but not necessarily at home, such as: world-scale production plants built in low-wage countries for labor-intensive products (Bartlett, Ghoshal & Beamish, 2008).

The structure of the MNC is regarded as a network, and each subsidiary is given responsibility compared to its capabilities and strategic mission.

The MNC is controlled by the movement of people within the MNC that may facilitate the mutual development and dispersion of innovation and knowledge.

Multidomestic / Multinational (Admin, 2009).

Low pressure for integration - high pressure for differentiation

Strategy is based on responsiveness to local market demands.

Resources are dispersed among the different national operations to be able to respond to local needs (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

Structure of the MNC will be a portfolio of rather autonomous national companies containing their entire value chain.

The innovation and knowledge developed at these national companies will most likely stay there, and will most likely not be dispersed to other companies within the MNC.

International (Admin, 2009).

Low pressure for integration - low pressure for differentiation

Strategy is based on home country expertise.

Resources are generally centralized in the home country for developing key innovations; however, other resources may be decentralized to allow innovations to be adapted worldwide (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

Structurally, the majority of the value chain will be maintained at the headquarters. The control of technologies used for e.g. production and general management systems will be structured and developed at home.

The development of knowledge and innovation will stream from the home organization to the subsidiaries.

Global (Admin, 2009).

High pressure for integration - low pressure for differentiation; Strategy is heavily based on scale of economies.

All of its resources are concentrated either in its home country or low-cost overseas location (Bartlett, Ghoshal, & Beamish, 2008).

From a structural standpoint, the subsidiaries of the MNC are rather weak and a full value chain will only exist at home. The subsidiaries are heavily dependent on resources and know-how from the home organization.

Innovation and development will be created at home, and later diffused to remaining subsidiaries.

Appendix B Transnational Organization Defined

Reference for Business (n.d.). Transnational organization. From

<http://www.referenceforbusiness.com/management/Tr-Z/Transnational-Organization.html>

Transnational Strategy

- “The overseas components are integrated into the overall corporate structure across several dimensions”
 - “Each of the components is empowered to become a source of specialized innovation”
- “It is a management approach in which an organization integrates”
 - “Its global business activities through close cooperation and interdependence among its headquarters, operations, and international subsidiaries”
 - “And its use of appropriate global information technologies” (Zwass, 1998).

Principal Characteristics of Transnational Strategy

- “The differentiated contributions by all its units to integrated worldwide operations”
- “A joint innovation by headquarters and by some of the overseas units leads to the development of relatively standardized and yet flexible products and services that can capture several local markets”
- “Decision making and knowledge generation are distributed among the units of a transnational organization”

Transnational Key Philosophy

- “Adaptation to all environmental situations”
- “Achieving flexibility by capitalizing on knowledge flows (which take the form of decisions and value-added information)”
- “Two-way communication throughout the organization”

Appendix C United States-based Hybrid (Combined Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’ Office) Transnational Organizations

2016 Top 10 Telecommute-Friendly Companies: Based on High Frequency and Variety of Telecommute Jobs From

<https://www.virtualvocations.com/blog/telecommuting-news/virtual-vocations-2016-year-end-report/>

- UnitedHealth Group, Minneapolis, MN
- IBM, Armonk, NY
- Dell, Inc, Round Rock, TX
- Xerox Corp, Norwalk, CT
- Salesforce.com, San Francisco, CA
- Humana, Inc, Louisville, KY
- Oracle Corp, Redwood Shores, CA
- Connections Academy, Baltimore, MD
- K12 Inc, Herndon, VA
- Kaplan, Inc, Fort Lauderdale, FL

The Hybrid Work Environment: The Business Process Argument
For Adapting Organizational Structure
Version September 2017

Abstract

Whereas studies support the need to understand the fluid nature of business processes and the effect on organizational structure, critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on organizational structures have been left unanswered. Multiple case studies will be used to identify the hybrid work practices with regards to the changes to job and work designs, and the effects, if any, of these changes on business processes and, thus, on organizational structure. The purpose is to understand the influence of the fluid nature of hybrid work on organizational structures for United States-based multinational organizations. The central questions are: How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What effect is there, if any, on the organizational structure?

Introduction

In 1776, Adam Smith, in the *Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*, sustained that workers, through the division of labor, could achieve greater skill and ability in performing their task. Smith (1776) concluded that, as a result of the division, organizations are able to “create more value per participant than each of them could create individually” (Jost, 2011, p. 7). Early in the 20th century, Max Weber described the design of organizations as mechanical structures; largely depicted by layers of report-to hierarchies and specific functional assignments for the workforce. Frederick Taylor’s Scientific Management theory sought to identify the best way to organize work and to assure that this was not challenged or changed (Burnes & Randall, 2016). Even the theories of the ‘Practical Theorist’ of change, Kurt Lewin, were fundamentally viewed as goals to achieve stability (Burnes & Randall, 2016). Later in the 1940’s, Philip Selznick’s theory of organization recognized the “unavoidable reality of the emergence of informal structure” (Kraatz, 2015, p. 155). In contrast to Weber, who

endorsed bureaucracies as a rational solution for the execution of long-term goals; Selznick contended that structure continually evolves from the informal order of the organization and its changing goals (Kraatz, 2015, p. 155).

After the 1970s, studies on the effects of technology on organizations decreased when researchers moved away from studying the influences of the internal operations to the external, environmental influences. At about that same time, the internal operations were changing rapidly due to developments in technology that allowed people to work differently; thereby, changing organizational routines and operations. According to conclusions drawn from a November, 2003 internal study conducted by Intel, “wireless mobility changes the way employees work” (McLennan, 2008, p. 175). These technological changes also influence the daily functions of the organizational structure; yet there is minimal systematic knowledge of whether or how this technology has altered structural patterns or conditions that may lead to changes thereof (Tolbert & Hall, 2009).

Today’s organizations, challenged with a dynamic global market that cannot wait for layers of management to make decisions or for new products or services to be placed on hold for years while waiting for an infrastructure to catch up, must adapt continually to new technology. In response, there is an array of structural design alternatives that have begun to appear; most with fewer hierarchical levels that move away from “authoritarian management styles and the separatist titles and privileges of a multilevel hierarchy” (Gallos, 2006, p. 566). More recently, that early bureaucratic stability has morphed into a flexible, adaptable structure that includes a hybrid (traditional physical office / virtual off-site) workforce.

The advantages derived from the combination of a virtual and physical workplace ranges from reduced hard costs, such as real estate; to a reduction in soft costs related to high-turnover rates (Ware & Grantham, 2010). The combination also enhances productivity as it improves employee input and collaborative efforts (Montero & Montero, 2010/2011). For example, with the implementation of technology, economies of scale may be realized in the processing of contracts by the sales department (Jost, 2011). However, when technology also includes a virtual workforce, the flow of information may be changed; thereby, requiring restructuring.

That is, there are challenges from the internal environment as job, work, and business processes, particularly standardized processes, are changed.

The external environment, diverse and ever-changing, creates its own set of far reaching sociopolitical, geographic, and economic implications and threats that vary in severity and frequency (Bhamra, 2016). Hence, efforts must be made to develop “robust and resilient organizational systems capable of withstanding and responding to the uncertainties and challenges” (Bhamra, 2016, p. 4). To use these changes to their advantage, the organization must continually ‘fit’ both internal processes, strategies, and structures; as well as the range of external environments. The test is to thrive while remaining viable as changes are taking place around and within the organization (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012).

With the increase in hybrid work practices, the ‘fit’ between those environments is changing. The lack of current theoretical studies on organizations, and job and work content, makes that ‘fit’ even more challenging. To address the issues, further studies are needed to identify changes introduced by the hybrid work environment and the effects, if any, of these changes on business processes and on the organizational structure (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005).

Background.

Compared to the earlier classical organization theory that was based on management control with division of labor and deskilled work, the 1980s introduced flexible firms “in terms of organization structure, production systems, work design, technology, and the use of labor” (Luhman & Cunliffe, 2013, p. 650). The horizontal structure and flexibility allowed for quick responses to a competitive, dynamic market contrast. Managers transitioned from positions of authority that controlled every decision in the organization to coaches who instill a culture of learning that encourages constant improvement and innovation. Rather than a top-down decision-making protocol, the current managerial approach is one that encourages workers’ suggestions and decisions at the point of work. Conversely, this point of work decision-making has had its share of challenges. For instance, whereas Southwest Airlines has been successful in empowering their employees to make decisions; other airlines have experienced roadblocks. In this latter case, the roadblocks appear to be due to stringent guidelines for answers that can be offered by employees (Saylor Academy, 2012).

Nevertheless, in order to survive long-term in the global market, the structure will need to continually adapt to the external business environment and the internal organization demands (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p.194). The current trend is to acknowledge that there is no 'one-size-fits-all' structure that will accommodate an organization's multilayered obligation to meet strategic goals (Soyka, 2012, p. 153). Unfortunately, the shift from the 'old' to the 'new', constantly being felt throughout an organization, is not necessarily positive. The turmoil has caused some employees to find new jobs that do not involve the challenges of multiple transitions and change; including the uncertainty that accompanies it (Choi & Click, 2007). From the business perspective, in situations where United States multinational corporations are pressed to implement some of these changes in their offshore facilities, opposing foreign regulations and policies have thwarted plans.

The regulations to create a targeted organizational structure are based on processes that reflect the strategic logic or system of roles (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013). Frequently, as is being seen in the hybrid environments, the actual system of roles underlying the organizational processes deviate from the scheduled organizational process that are the foundation for the formal organizational structure (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013). Recent articles recognize the importance of business processes on structure; going so far as to suggest that the structure should be based on processes and not the other way around (Jeston & Nelis, 2008b). And, contemporary organizational theorists continue to research conditions where individuals are likely to deviate from existing structures and when those deviations require changes to the documented structures (Tolbert & Hall, 2009, p. 21).

The changes have resulted in mismatches in the design of work, jobs, processes, and organizational structures. Researchers, Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012), recognize the importance of structure and the influences of business processes. Their methodology addresses the resulting mismatch between processes and structure with "activities by phases and functions and tools" that are categorized to identify "the organizational structure of a company that is needed to perform its business processes well" (pp. 5413, 5411).

Underlying this complexity of mismatches is that the science of organizations, job, work, and organization design; have been largely ignored since the 1970s and 1980s (Sinha & Van de

Ven, 2005). Ironically, the basis for the gap in research is the general opinion that the questions regarding theoretical and practical research on job design are complete (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010). Conversely, the hybrid work venues have changed the way that people work; therefore, the theories and empirical studies do not accurately reflect the current workplace (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010). These changes to work modules, including job design, often associated with changes in the organization's structure, create a disconnect between jobs, processes, and structure (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005).

The changes to work and job designs in the hybrid workplace as well as the influence on organizational structure requires revisions to the integration and differentiation of processes. According to the Contingency Theorists, Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), integration is “the process of achieving unity of effort”; and differentiation is “the state of segmentation of the organizational systems into subsystems” (pp. 1-30). Their theory, frequently referred to as structural contingency theory, is applied in most studies to “characterize the organization in structural terms” with regards to their environment (Foss & Saebi, 2015, p. 90). The underlying processes and the informal systems through which work actually gets done is not a priority (Foss & Saebi, 2015). However, in the twenty-first century, organizations and their structures will need to be able to keep up with the fast pace of change in underlying processes and informal systems to integrate new methods and ideas; including those introduced by a hybrid workforce (Choi & Click, 2007).

A major challenge to process innovation is the mismatches, inherently caused by the way that people reorganize their daily jobs, between work process and organizational structure (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 154). While institutional theory does recognize limitations for the type of structure and the conformity to procedures; organizations also impose limitations as there is a tendency to “take for granted the institutional processes to which they adhere” (Greenwood, Oliver, Sahlin, & Suddaby, 2012, Vol 1, p. 273). Likewise, business organizations are prone to define structure by activities; such as marketing, finance, and information technology (Greenwood, Oliver, Sahlin, & Suddaby, 2012, Vol 1, p. 272). In their studies, Lawrence and Suddaby (2012) urge researchers to look behind the scenes of the outward appearance of

permanent processes in the organization; and to focus on the gap between structure and action (Greenwood, Oliver, Sahlin, & Suddaby, 2012, Vol 5).

Hybrid work changes do offer an opportunity to review end-to-end processes; frequently, identifying ways to optimize supporting work and job processes (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). In light of this issue, researchers Oldham and Hackman (2010) recommended methods; such as investigating how organizational contexts and work processes may influence our knowledge of job designs; and to understand the juxtaposition of organizations and job / work / business process designs (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010). Their suggestions highlight that many of the new changes to jobs present recurring challenges to the emerging theoretical perspectives that have deep roots in classic scholarship; including the aforementioned structural contingency theory (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010).

Problem statement.

The early theories proposed by, Smith, Weber, Taylor, Lewin, and Selznick, strengthened with “behavioral approaches and systems theories”, have had a long-lasting effect on “management thinking right up to the present” (Murphy, n.d.). Adding to this issue is that current organization theories are based on 1870s neo-classical, micro-economic theory (Murphy, n.d.). Further complicating the expansion of the hybrid work option is that "...a number of scholars have recently pointed out that current theoretical models and empirical studies of job design no longer reflect--and have yet to integrate--the impact of the dramatic changes in work contexts that have taken place" (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 145). On the other hand, whereas revised job / work / business processes may be beneficial, they do not necessarily create value (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a).

Nonetheless, the reality is that the organizational landscape has been changed by the rapidly increasing hybrid workforce and their methods of work. Generally, structural reorganization is considered before process redesign. In contrast to the visual diagrams that can be used to explain the change and outcome of structural reorganization, the process redesign and the effect on job and work design tend to be more difficult to envisage and the results are more difficult to describe (Burnes & Randall, 2016). (See Appendix A Conceptual Map.)

Outdated bureaucracies and structural components may slow responses to an evolving marketplace; resulting in lower productivity, profits and even business failure (Werther, 1999). Whether the organization recognizes when change is imminent or adheres to existing processes and structures is the crux of the issue. Although studies support the need to understand the fluid nature of work processes and the effect on organizational structure; critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work on business processes on organizational structures have been left unanswered.

Purpose statement.

The multiple case studies will be used to identify the hybrid work practices with regards to the changes to job and work designs, and the effects, if any, of these changes on business processes and, thus, on organizational structure. The purpose is to understand the influence of the fluid nature of hybrid work processes on organizational structure for United States-based multinational organizations. The hybrid work environment will be defined as a combination of traditional (physical office) and virtual (off site) workers in multinational organizations, in various geographic locations. The study will be based on multiple types and sources of information; therefore, it is anticipated that different perspectives and patterns will be discovered.

Research questions.

The research questions are based on the business need to understand the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on organizational structures. While the changed business processes are found to increase productivity; some organizations are not prepared to accommodate the subsequent changes. Organizations, such as Yahoo!, have recently revoked their hybrid work policy; requiring all employees to work from the traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office to improve collaboration; thereby, implying that the method of work is the issue. Other organizations, such as Chiat-Day in Venice, California also returned to the traditional one person per desk ‘brick and mortar’ office. Chiat-Day learned that it wasn’t the people who couldn’t let go of the past as much as it was the organization’s “traditional organizing practices” that encouraged people to show up early at temporary office spaces to claim a desk (Ellison, 2004, p. 5). That is, instead of encouraging a traditional / virtual venue, employees “created ‘work

arounds' to counter the effects of poor design" to avoid the virtual office option (Ellison, 2004, p. 4). From those perspectives, the implication is that the hybrid traditional / virtual workforce may inhibit a company from achieving goals.

Hence, the central questions identify the changing business processes in the hybrid venue and the effect on organizational structure. How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What effect is there, if any, on the organizational structure?

Rationale for methodology.

The hybrid workforce redesigns "processes that are at the heart of what the company does and which cut across organizational boundaries" (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012, p. 200). At the job level, the hybrid workforce changes to processes have affected the way that transactions between and within departments are sent and received (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 154). The foundation of the organizational structure, other business units and inter-related functions, are affected as well. According to Hickson, Pugh, and Pheysey (1969), the influence on the structure of the organization will be affected by size; that is, in the multinational organization, the "effects will be confined to job-counts of employees on activities linked with the workflow itself, and will not be detectable in variables of the more remote administrative and hierarchical structure" (Tolbert & Hall, 2009, p. 53). In comparison, the research of Van de Ven, Delbecq, and Koenig (1976) found that as tasks increased in uncertainty, the hierarchal forms of control were replaced with horizontal controls or structures (Tolbert & Hall, 2009). In this case, the variables of the remote administrative and hierarchical structures were detected. The issue is to determine if, for a multinational corporation, the variables of the hybrid job / work / business process structure can be detected. Then, the challenge is to determine if revisions are required at the organizational level (Lin, 2011).

This redesign of structure requires key steps, including (1) preparing the organization, (2) rethinking the way that work is done, (3) restructuring the organization around the new business processes, and (4) implementing new information and measurement systems (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012, p. 200). In organizational theory, the changes to structure can be a directed, 'top-down' initiative, one that is generally economic-based; or facilitated where staff members provide input to and shape the change (p. 194). The implementation of a hybrid workforce

presents the opportunity for changes to structure; however, instead of a directed, top-down initiative, the change may be a facilitated one that includes many members of the organization, shaping what needs to happen (p. 194).

The specific objective of this study is to determine the new processes or the way that work is done, as implemented by the hybrid workforce, that effect organizational structure. In order to meet this objective, the qualitative method will be applied to describe the characteristics of the population; specifically, the hybrid (traditional / virtual) workforce, their influence on business processes, and their subsequent affect, if any, on organizational structure (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). The analysis is complicated in that several of the researchers noted in the literature review recognize that there is no ideal ‘fits all’ structure. Considering the array of possibilities, the methodology will need to allow the development of a rich description of the hybrid work processes in an organizational setting (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). While there is considerable expense and time involved in adapting a structure, the cost may be offset by the savings accrued from the hybrid workforce. However, due diligence is required to continually identify any unexpected costs that may mitigate the value of restructuring (Thompson & Caputo, 2009). Given the possibility of long-term effects on productivity and profitability, this study is both relevant and significant to the business, the stakeholders, and their customers. (See Appendix B Cranet Survey Increased Hybrid Workforce).

Research design.

“Widely used in organizational studies and across the social sciences”, the case study will provide the framework for an in-depth analysis of United States-based multinational organizations, with a formal hybrid work policy (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 3). The application of Yin’s (1984) replication logic to the multiple case study research strategy “will strengthen the patterns of the findings” (Vohra, 2014). The rationale for the basically qualitative design is to allow “the study of things in their natural settings, then attempt to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them” (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011, p. 3). The methodology will facilitate the identification of variables for job / work / business process changes resulting from the hybrid work venue in United States-based multinational organizations and the effect on its structure.

Assumptions, limitations, and delimitations.

A major assumption is that corporations are ready, willing, and able to promote a hybrid work policy. However, studies have identified that some work simply is not suited for a hybrid environment; regardless of the organization's willingness to change. Or, different opinions within the organization may impede the implementation of the hybrid work policy. For example, in a study by Lautsch and Kossek (2011), an interviewee noted that there may be a difference in the perception of the job responsibilities and tasks in the workforce; particularly with regards to managing. In this case, the employee, who would have preferred more than the allowed 4 days per month to work virtually, felt that the difference between the formal job structure and perception of the work actually done may have been the basis for the disagreement with management. Overall, the employee felt that it was just a matter of opinion as to the best location—traditional office, home office, or client site—for the job to be done (Lautsch & Kossek, 2011).

There are delimitations to this study as "relatively few major steps have been taken to break theoretical and empirical ground to orient job design research towards fresh topics and phenomena"; including the orientation of job design to the hybrid work environments (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 146). In itself, job design research has been somewhat stagnant over the past few decades. Hence, the variables for work design / job design may indicate that organizational structure changes are required; however, those changes may be based on information that no longer accurately describes the way that work is being done.

On a related note, there appears to be a schism between research and practice in the business world. That is, research is not transferred or transferable to the workplace. Rousseau (2006) has identified a 'research-practice gap' where organizations are less likely to use 'evidence-based management' that is based on rigorous research practices. Instead, managers tend to rely on past experience (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). The Bonabeau (2003) study reported that "45% of managers prefer to rely on their instincts rather than facts and figures when making business decisions..." (Snowden, 2015, p. 269). While there are several reasons, ranging from differences in research orientations to differences in language, for the lack of

incorporating research into business practices; other disciplines such as science and education rely heavily on research evidence (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012).

From a global perspective, when changes to the business processes influenced by the hybrid workforce do change structure; off-shore facilities may be faced with additional roadblocks. For instance, in Germany, the Worker's Council must approve all decisions that affect the workforce before being implemented (Jeston & Nelis, 2008b). The positive element to the effects of off-shore regulations is that "organizations can benefit from best practices from around the world" (Jeston & Nelis, 2008b, p. 115). However, incorporating those best practices, including a hybrid workforce, requires assessing business process and structural changes in that light (p. 115).

The general purpose of this research will be "to gather information to aid business-related decision-making" regarding the changes to business processes and the influence on structure in the traditional/virtual work venue (Wilson, 2010, p. 3). Given the impact on productivity and profitability, decisions that are based on the research findings require a cautious approach to interpretation and action taken upon those findings (Wilson, 2010). Though the exploratory case study will encourage different perspectives; the generalization will be limited by those factors that are not considered; such as variables for financial and political stability. In summary, while the framework of the study may be transferable to other organizations, the generalizability of the results will be limited by the design.

Literature Review

Introduction to the literature review.

Organizational structure determines the way that people work; the arrangement of job and work processes; the collaborative efforts of the workforce members; the order for decision-making, power, and authority; and mechanisms for controlling the exchange of communication and information (Gutterman, 2013). Current trends challenge this formal arrangement as flexible organizational structures are proven to enhance profitability in the competitive, global market (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010). Other viewpoints offer that flexibility overlook the practicality of the guidelines for work provided by organizational processes and

boundaries. From this other view, the formal process and boundaries promote operational effectiveness needed to achieve corporate goals (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010).

The organizational structure also affects and is affected by the way that work is done in the move from the traditional 'brick and mortar' office to a hybrid of traditional and virtual locations. For the most part, the transition improves corporate strategy and goals (Grantham, Ware, & Swanberg, 2009). In other cases, particularly when companies change to the hybrid workplace with little or no prior planning, there are negative outcomes; such as legal litigation, mismanagement, and ultimately failed team efforts. For example, tax laws require that taxes are based on the employee's virtual office location. Without official recognition of the virtual office policy, the corporate tax assessment might be challenged. (See e.g. Internal Revenue Manual 6.800.2 at https://www.irs.gov/irm/part6/irm_06-800-002.html). Furthermore, the hybrid work can result in a mismatch of business processes and organizational structure that prevent a company from reaching "operating achievements" (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5411). Unfortunately, in studies where the focus of research is on business processes for traditional or virtual work, the emphasis for reaching operating achievements was on cutting time and expense. Any issues regarding the interrelationship of hybrid job, work, and business processes, with existing organizational structure were not considered (Hong et al., 2012, p. 5411).

Organizational success or failure is often explained by the ability or lack thereof to achieve a system that fits both internal and external environments (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013). Maintaining this 'fit' is becoming more problematic as these internal and external environments are evolving. For instance, the introduction of a hybrid workforce can be quite successful in achieving 'within division' project goals; however, organizational structures that are unable to accommodate any subsequent changes in end-to-end processes between divisions can be problematic (Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015). Nevertheless, an understanding of the changes to end-to-end processes may lead to improvements in existing structure. For example, in an insurance firm transitioning to a hybrid workplace, the applications processed from the virtual office produced a bottle-neck of work for the next traditional 'brick and mortar' office based

department. Subsequently, the reason for the overflow of work was discovered and changes were made to the job, work, and business processes, as well as the structure.

Consistent with the research of Teece, Pisano and Shuen (1997), the ability to proactively adapt to these changing environments is key to achieving long-term profitability. This adaptability is required at many levels of the organization as innovative business processes are introduced by hybrid work. In some business processes, with the exception of legal requirements for hard copy print-outs, an organization's electronic version of the form may replace the need for printing the paperwork. Whereas each step of the application processing formerly included printing and filing, the electronic transmission of forms from a virtual worker to the traditional office may require a rework of end-to-end processes. While the hybrid work changes complicate the integration or coordination across key organizational systems and structures, the hybrid environments are also known to encourage coordinating efforts to support adaptability and flexibility. This demand for coordinating efforts toward flexibility should not stop at the specific area(s) of the business process directly using the hybrid environment—it needs to extend throughout the entire organization. On the other hand, some companies lack coordination on many levels; thus, the organization misses an opportunity to improve business processes, productivity, and profitability because revisions are not considered to be suitable for the existing structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

Overall, whereas studies support the need to understand the fluid nature of business processes and the effect on organizational structure, critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on organizational structures and strategies have been left unanswered. Accordingly, the way that people work, and related job responsibilities, have changed significantly over the last two decades (Gutterman, 2013). Specifically, further research is needed to identify the influence of hybrid work practices; including the changes to job and work designs, and the effects, if any, of these changes on business processes and, thus, on organizational structure.

The information in the literature review regarding the interrelationships of hybrid work, business processes, and organizational structures is based on search words from a variety of resources. In the JSTOR database, search words included: organizational structures,

multinational organizations, virtual teams, virtual and traditional teams, organizational science theory, hybrid work environments, and workflow in organizations. A review of the references in several of the texts, resulting from these search words, offered additional resources. In addition, The Pennsylvania State University-Harrisburg online search tool was used to locate printed materials in the campus library. Extra resources were located by viewing the books located around those results; such as all texts located in the sections surrounding HD 58.8. Generally, the search revealed developing theoretical models, empirical analysis, and qualitative case studies, that concentrate on the evolving internal and external environments; particularly the business process changes brought on by the hybrid workforce and its influence on organizational structure.

A review of the information led to the development of the following for the literature review: 1) the conceptual framework offers a theoretical overview of the evolving nature of organizational structure and business processes and 2) the literature review describes the interrelationship of the hybrid work environment, business processes, and organizational structure and their potential to significantly influence sustainable productivity and profitability. This literature review section includes subtopics covering the relationship of business processes and organizational structure; job and work designs; coordination of the innovative hybrid work environment; and the limitations and challenges of the hybrid work environment.

Related methodologies and meta-analysis are also covered. For instance, the significance of the relationship between hybrid work processes and organizational structure, are explored with methodologies developed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) and Reiff-Marganeic (2012). The meta-analysis of case studies and reviews of prior studies, such as completed by Grant, Fried, Parker, and Frese (2010), further informs the conceptual and operational variables related to hybrid job, work, and business processes; and organizational structure. The literature review also includes a synthesis of research findings; a critique of the previous findings; and a summary.

Conceptual framework.

Early organizational theorists such as Max Weber, Frederick Winslow Taylor, and Henry Fayol all asserted that organizational structure should be based on universally accepted and

practiced rules, regulations, and principles (Gutterman, 2013). From that perspective, the organizational structure was considered to be analogous to a well-oiled, mechanically-run machine that relied on a hierarchy of a top-down style of management, the assignment of specialized tasks to all workers, all based on a formal set of rules to be followed (Gutterman, 2013). Unquestionably, in the first-half of the twentieth century, the predominant line of practice was to design and maintain a one-size-fits-all traditional structure (Distelzweig, n.d). During the late twentieth and early twenty-first century, organizations began to realize that in order to remain competitive; an adaptable, flexible structure was required. Although flexibility is considered to be essential to sustaining productivity and profitability, changing organizational structures is expensive and time-consuming; hence, the need for understanding the dynamics and implications (Distelzweig, n.d).

The ideology of the contingency theory, which accounts for the interrelationship of work and organizational design, provides a foundation for understanding the dynamics and implications. Generally, “the contingency theory proposes that organizations are most effective when the design of their structures and processes is internally coherent and fits or matches their environment” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 395). A study by “one of the most influential contributors to the Contingency School, Joan Woodward, focused on the relationship between organizational structure and organizational performance” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). The results of Woodward’s comparative empirical study (1950-1959) of 100 manufacturing organizations in England indicated that the “relationship between structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). Theorists, Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), Thompson (1967), and Galbraith (1977) related the study of the variables, work and organization design, at the organizational level. Later, Hackman and Oldham (1975), in their renowned Job Characteristics Theory, related the variables at the job design level.

Ideally, the organization fits or matches their internal and external business processes to structure. In the midst of changing work and structure, the ability to link different departments may become a dual challenge (Hunter, 2002). On one hand, differentiation represents the variety of approaches to doing business (i.e. the marketing department may be very different from the

sales teams in the approach to developing customer relations). On the other hand, integration is the coordination between these departments. Realistically, the complexity of the internal and external environments coupled with the changing ways of work in a hybrid venue indicates that organizations can no longer remain attached to their processes and structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

Current theories recognize that the operating environments, both internal and external, are a prominent factor in designing organizational structure (Gutterman, 2013). Due to the uncertainty of those operating environments, there is no one ideal organizational structure that can meet the evolving nature of business. The challenge is in designing a unique structure that proactively recognizes changes in the internal and external environment; with flexibility to adapt that structure as needed.

The hybrid workforce redesigns processes to fit their traditional and virtual places of work. The opportunities provided by the virtual work sector of the hybrid venue is the focus of attention as it encourages new methods that improve productivity (Reiff-Marganec, 2012). However, the studies by Piccoli, Powell, and Ives (2004) indicate that the complete transfer of current practices used for traditional teams in the workplace to the hybrid environment can potentially be problematic. That is, proactive revisions that recognize new practices contribute to the success of the hybrid work policy (Piccoli, Powell, & Ives, 2004).

Taking the history of organizational structure into consideration, the hybrid work environment imposes new questions regarding the feasibility of current structures. To illustrate that point, several research studies presented in this literature review indicate that further analysis is needed regarding the effect of hybrid work environments on organizational structure and strategies. For instance, the definition of the term organizational structure includes task allocation, the coordination of processes between internal and external units and members, and the role of decision-makers; therefore, any changes to tasks, coordination, and decisions in the hybrid work environment need to be considered (Gutterman, 2013).

From a corporate strategy viewpoint, offering a hybrid work policy, increases productivity, improves employee morale, and lowers overhead costs (Grantham, Ware, & Swanberg, 2009). The hybrid work policy also sustains the bigger picture for corporations to

leverage the talent wherever it is located, with whatever tools are needed for collaboration, to remain profitable (Bullock & Klein, 2010). Yet, the subsequent mismatch between business processes and structure may actually hinder the company from achieving operating goals. Therefore, adapting processes, strategy, and structure; directly and indirectly influenced by changes shaped by the hybrid work policy, is important to successful implementation (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

The introduction of an innovative approach to work; as in a hybrid work policy, requires coordination within the organization as well as with the external environment (Lin, 2011). Within the organization, the structure must adapt to the new methods introduced by hybrid work (Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015). These changes must also align with the external environment; including customers, stakeholders, and markets. Although the research results support the need to understand the fluid nature of work processes and the effect on organizational structure, specific questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on business processes and organizational structure have not been fully answered (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010).

Review of research literature.

The focus of this study is the interrelationship of the hybrid work environment, business processes, and organizational structure. Hence, the literature review includes prior research on the broader topics of organizational structure; business processes; job design; coordination of new ways to work; and limitations and challenges for management. Based on those past studies, section subtopics evolved to cover the relationship of business processes and organizational structure; job and work designs; coordination of the innovative hybrid work environment; and the limitations and challenges of the hybrid work environment.

Basically, structures revolve around business units that are formed around functions; and the people and functions are interdependent. (Distelzweig, n.d.). Early in the twentieth century, process interdependence was supported by a bureaucratic, hierarchical organizational structure to facilitate mass production. Organizational structures were based on strict job specialization, a top-down chain-of-command, and the “subordination of individual interests to the superordinate goals of the organization” (Distelzweig, n.d.). The graphical form of this structural model could

be depicted by a hierarchy or pyramid chart (Distelzweig, n.d.). However, after World War II, organizations increased in size and complexity—and “problems in United States’ business structures began to appear” (Distelzweig, n.d.).

Currently, twenty-first century organizations are adapting to horizontal structures to improve functioning (Distelzweig, n.d.). The use of technology enhances the horizontal model through the speed of communication and decision-making; it is also an influential factor in the expansion of hybrid work environments. Research on hybrid work environments indicates that members of organizations and their job responsibilities are evolving in ways that influence the way that work is done, business processes, and structure. The foundation of the organizational structure, the business units and their interrelated functions, are affected, too. The changed work arrangements, influence business unit end-to-end processes; thereby, requiring changes to structure and strategy (Lin, 2011). Since changing a structure is an expensive and time-consuming venture that impacts productivity; identifying the concepts and designing a methodology to discover if there are sufficient, sustainable reasons for revision is far-sighted and practical.

Business processes and organizational structure.

Structure influences the organization’s workforce and business units; thereby, affecting internal and external business processes (DeCanio, Dibble, & Amir-Atefi, 2000). The issue is whether these processes can be used to define reasons for adapting structure. Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) identified that the dynamics between the organization’s processes and structure can determine whether a company is in a position to achieve its goals—or not (p. 5411). Conversely, in studies where the focus of research is on business processes, the emphasis was on the standard issues of cutting time and expense; barely acknowledging any connections between process and structure. Thus, the impact of the work of one department on another was largely unnoticed. Fundamentally, the concepts underlying the framework for discovering those important dynamics between business processes and structure were not considered (p. 5411).

In order to address this mismatch between processes and structure, the methodology proposed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) searches for an organizational structure that will help the company to improve its business processes (p. 5411). In this methodology, the

researchers' transfer-of-work metrics is relevant to the research question as it identifies the end-to-end processes of work from one unit to another (p. 5412). Since their analysis goes beyond the implications of social relations, the importance of the organizational structure in the business process analysis is recognized (p. 5423). With this approach, they provide a tool to diagnose the critical factors of existing problems before organizational improvements or changes, such as a hybrid work policy, are implemented (p. 5423).

Primarily, their methodology identified the business processes by phases, functions, and tools (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413). Phase one begins with business process models, based on business logs measured for transfer-of-work metrics, to develop a matrix. For phase one, business logs both before and after the development of a hybrid work policy can indicate where the transfer of work between departments or units change. Transactional information and data in the business log will take the place of what people 'think' is happening (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 140). In phase two, a process network, based on the matrix, is developed (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413). In this phase, issues such as bottlenecks in the processing network are discovered (p. 5414). In the third phase, a problem oriented diagnosis of the process network is completed (p. 5413). For instance, the diagnosis for the bottleneck may reveal that working from home expedites the work process; thereby, creating a work overload for the next point of process. And, in the last phase, the researchers suggest how the resulting redesign guidelines will be used to change the organizational structure; as well as alternatives to or partial redesign (p. 5413).

Given that research on the implementation of a hybrid work environment indicates that the resulting changes influence a variety of levels in the organization, a methodological approach to analyzing pre-existing problems may ensure a successful implementation thereof. Then again, the analysis of pre-existing problems may be misleading; particularly since inclusion of organizational fixed-effects in the methodology may or may not correctly impact the outcome (Zoghi, Mohr, & Meyer, 2010, p. 638). Consequently, as with any study, a critical analysis of the results is practical.

Job and work designs.

"Organizational structure affects both the overall behavior of firms and the situations of individuals and subunits within firms" (DeCanio, Dibble, & Amir-Atefi, 2000, p. 1285). Relative to that ideology is that research on hybrid work environments indicates that individual members of organizations and their job responsibilities are evolving in rapid ways. The foundation of the organizational structure, the business units and their related functions, are affected (Gutterman, 2013). Sinha and Van de Ven (2005) emphasized the idea that the science of organizations, such as work design, has had an overwhelming effect on individual workers and organizations as well as on global productivity and economies (p. 389). The results of the study of 22 papers by Grant, Fried, Parker, and Frese (2010) indicated that theory and empirical studies of job design do not represent and, therefore, do not integrate the changes in the context of work; i.e. hybrid work environments (p. 145).

Even with revised job designs, the hybrid work option may not be suitable. Drawing on the experiences of Fortune 500 companies to identify the business reason advantages and disadvantages for the hybrid work options, Cascio (2000) maintained that although all indications are that the hybrid work environment will grow; the virtual portion of the hybridity may not be appropriate for all jobs (p. 81). Overall, before embarking on a hybrid work policy, organizations must know the intricacies of their job / work / business processes before considering the transition to a combined physical and virtual workplace (Cascio, 2000, p. 83).

Unfortunately, since the empirical research of the 1970s and 80s, work and organization design has not been researched with any scope or depth (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 389). While job and work processes have changed dramatically with advances in technology, the design of the processes were not kept up-to-date. Essentially, the studies support the evidence that job design research has not progressed to include new ways of work; such as the changed processes resulting from the hybrid context and the influence on organizational design (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 146). The fact that the studies span more than a decade is a concern. Not surprisingly, the results of Sinha and Van de Ven's (2005) longitudinal study called for future research that focuses on job and work design (Abstract).

Coordinating the innovative hybrid work environment.

Lin's (2011) comprehensive literature review used the organization's viewpoint of adaptability and innovation, to analyze key issues; including the influence of information technology and virtual office adoption on the organization's innovation performance (p. 237). In the hybrid workplace, these influences demand cooperation and integration at the workforce, departmental, and organizational levels; including external partners and environments (Lin, 2011, p. 238). The review resolved that information technology has had a major influence on the transformation of organizational structure, the way that work is done, communication, and the reciprocal relationship with internal and external environments (Lin, 2011, p. 236).

Likewise, there is the importance of integration or coordination to ensure that organizations work to achieve goals throughout their systems and structures. However, with the adoption of the hybrid workplace, differentiation, or differences in policies and practices, is likely to increase; possibly requiring changes to organizational structures and systems (Cohen & Gibson, 2002, pp. 11-12). While hybrid work environments can challenge cooperative efforts to integrate and coordinate work across organizational units, the demand for flexibility to address these challenges cannot stop at the specific area(s) of the business process directly using the hybrid environment—it needs to extend throughout the entire organization.

The challenge for any organization is the ability to increase agility to embrace change. Internal and external environments in which organizations operate are increasing in complexity; thereby, necessitating the development of designs, competencies, and associated behaviors to encourage adaptability, flexibility and fluidity (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010, p. 1251). Organizations with a modular structure are faced with an additional challenge when the technology framework used to build the hybrid work environment also leads to new product architecture. Modular organizations tend to falter as the job / work specialization of modular structures have the tendency to create a myopic viewpoint; causing full or partial rejection of the new architecture (Gans, 2016). In order to absorb and exploit innovations, the hybrid work environment will require agility that also builds an inclusive identity that transcends where and how work is done (Gans, 2016).

This agility is particularly advantageous in the business processes, where the capability to customize a core model to adapt to various requirements and to accommodate the variability of a business domain is required (Reiff-Marganeic, 2012, p. 22). Hence, Reiff-Marganeic (2012) used a “model virtual organization to understand and analyze their behavior and structure more formally” (p. 23). The virtual organization model was based on two applications: APPEL where triggers occur through communication or events in the system; and StPOWLA which recognizes changes to workflows or tasks to understand and analyze the behavior and structure (Reiff-Marganeic, 2012, p. 25). This approach can also be applied to understand and analyze the processes and structure of hybrid (traditional and virtual) workflows or tasks; thereby, offering a method to proactively identify and support revisions.

Limitations and challenges of hybrid work environments.

From a business perspective, hybrid work environments provide firms with advantages; however, major improvements are needed for the way that they are currently viewed and supported. For starters, the organization’s strategy must systematically support the creation and management of hybrid work teams as well as understand what the hybrid initiative provides to an organization’s structure and strategic goals (Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015, p. 196). An organizational level strategic initiative to formally promote the use of hybrid teams will be required (Morley et al, 2015, p. 196). To derive the full benefits, a general framework that provides a plan to address problems and incorporate solutions will improve the long-term collaborative efforts of the hybrid work initiative (Morley et al, 2015, p. 189).

To illustrate, when end-to-end interdepartmental work processes are confronted with hybrid work processes that differ, the receiving departments may reject revisions (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 154). On the other hand, opportunities for improvement can be realized in understanding the work processes that move from one department to the next (p.154). Functionally, although there may be a challenge to maintain the status quo; any mismatch due to previously unrecognized or out-of-date processes may offer an opportunity to improve and expand current designs. A better understanding of the end-to-end process may also recognize an opportunity to improve existing structure. In sum, the resulting mismatches between the work processes and the inflexible structures presents a challenge to hybrid process innovation;

possibly blocking the full range of benefits that may be derived from hybrid work as well as foiling long overdue changes at the organizational level (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 154).

In their study of the Ireland branch of a large multinational device organization with a hybrid work environment, Morley, Cormican, and Folan (2015) developed a methodology to recognize and implement change at an organizational level. The workforce sample included a range of functions from product design to senior management; the data collected was practical as well as context-dependent (Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015, p. 192). Their study utilized a three-step adaption of the TOWS (external threats and opportunities; internal weaknesses and strengths) methodology to analyze the current organizational standards to hybrid virtual / traditional office teams. Potential strategies were identified and evaluated; results adapted to the TOWS matrix structure; and a model for implementation was developed (p. 193). Similar to Reiff-Marganeic's (2012) proposed methodology, Morley, Cormican, and Folan's (2015) study can be applied to a hybrid environment; thereby, allowing identification and evaluation of potential strategies to support (or not) changes to the structure due to the hybrid work processes.

Although organizational structure could be adapted to sustain innovative processes brought on by hybrid work environments, an association between the work environment and structure might be due to unobserved heterogeneity. Consequently, changing structure may not produce the desired business outcomes. For example, as part of their study of workplace organization and innovative processes in 3,200 establishments that spanned a period of five years, researchers Zoghi, Mohr, and Meyer (2010) found that causal references, particularly with regards to cross-sectional results, can be problematic. Thus, any association between practices, such as hybrid work processes and an existing work process might be due to unobserved heterogeneity (Zoghi, Mohr, & Meyer, 2010, p. 623-624, 631).

While their study regarding the decentralization of decision-making and information-sharing is applicable to the dynamics of the hybrid work environment; the results offered no clear indication as to the association with decentralization and information-sharing to changes of the existing work processes (Zoghi, Mohr, & Meyer, 2010, p. 634). That is, though the implementation of a hybrid work environment may introduce changes to work practices; there is no clear correlation with decentralization and information-sharing. Their study results

indicate just a few of the questions that need to be considered when introducing a hybrid work policy.

Some companies have decided that a complete reorganization of strategic and operational goals is needed to regain their market; thereby, requiring all workers to report to the traditional 'brick and mortar' offices. For instance, Yahoo!'s CEO believes that traditional office work is necessary for the business to recover its niche. Reportedly, CEO Marissa Mayer's memo rescinding the hybrid work policy, stated: "To become the absolute best place to work, communication and collaboration will be important, so we need to be working side-by-side. That is why it is critical that we are all present in our offices" (Pepitone, 2013, Feb).

Similarly, Best Buy made an announcement revising their flexible hybrid work policy that allowed workers to opt to choose to work virtually or in the company offices. Opposite to Yahoo!'s announcement requiring all employees to return to traditional working arrangements; the Best Buy virtual / traditional office work option will continue to be allowed; though, workers will need management pre-approval to work virtually. Comparable to Yahoo!, Best Buy also hired a new CEO to address the profit-margin and productivity problems (Pepitone, 2013, Mar).

Nonetheless, the change of hybrid work options at Yahoo! and Best Buy may indicate that the practice is on the decline. Not so. According to quantitative statistics from leading corporations, the hybrid work options are on the increase. From a practical, business perspective, SHRM [Society for Human Resource Management Global Diversity & Inclusion Division] "advocates that companies should be managing by results, not 'butts in seats'" (Meinert, 2011).

Review of methodological issues.

The evidence discovered in the literature review conceptualized business processes and organizational structure relative to the hybrid work environment. For the most part, the study results supported flexibility and adaptability in structures to accommodate business process changes. Other studies found that the relationship between changed business processes in a hybrid work environment; and organizational structure were negligible. By and large, whereas the research on hybrid work environments may differ in their identification and impact of the job and work practices / business process / structure mismatches; they do agree that a proactive

stance, with a flexible and adaptable approach toward changes can help to sustain organizational goals.

In order to provide substantial reasons for adapting structure, the study will rely on several theoretical models to conceptualize and operationalize variables; as well as provide results that are statistically significant in a practical and realistic sense. The practical and realistic point is important in that the business community has been calling for studies that engages with stakeholders beyond the research community (Ellis, 2010). For all consumers of research, understanding the results is imperative to making sound decisions. Therefore, the relationships of the variables, factors that may influence that relationship, and transferability to other settings; particularly the statistical analysis; will be reviewed in the following paragraphs.

From a statistical standpoint, the difference between the causal and correlational relationship is that in order to examine causality, variables need to be controlled and even manipulated (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 226). Manipulating some variables; such as randomly assigning the hybrid work option, could result in a violation of human resource policies and labor laws. Fortunately, the correlational design provides an acceptable method to examine the relationships between variables that are not all controllable (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 226). The correlational design will allow the examination of “the relationships of uncontrollable variables (changing business practices in the hybrid venue) with other variables (organizational structure)” (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 226).

However, the external validity, the “extent to which a study’s results can be generalized to other samples, settings, or procedures”, is an issue (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 58). Realistic settings and procedures influence the degree of external validity (p. 73). Researchers Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) concluded that their study, based on business process models, required analysis with actual business process logs, to improve external validity (p. 5423). Their results are not representative of the effects of real world variables (Utts, 2005, p. 92). The researchers also suggest that the use of a variety of organizational structures, along with real data, will improve their methodology.

Then, whether the statistical significance of the results, as based on the sample, can be extended to natural settings, is an issue, as well. The studies of Morley, Cormican, and Folan

(2015) concentrated on one geographic area of a multinational organization: Ireland. In addition, although their sample workforce spanned many functions; that off-shore facility produced specific devices. Whether the results of the Morley, Cormican, and Folan (2015) study of one organization in Ireland is statistically significant is a valid question / concern; nonetheless, the methodology does offer a framework for other studies.

Since the corporate environment, in general, is not well-versed at conducting and analyzing studies, there is the issue that executives might be prone to misinterpret results (Ellis, 2010). Accordingly, in a study published in the *Journal of International Business Studies* (2010), researcher Paul Ellis, “found that the average effect size of international business research is small” (Abstract). That is, the interpretation of results may indicate statistical significance, when, in fact there is substantive significance and vice versa. Statistically significant means the observed sample relationship is unlikely to have occurred unless a relationship exists in the population (Utts, 2005, p. 243). The end-result is unacceptably high Type II error rates which have led to invalid inferences regarding real-world effects (Ellis, 2010).

There are also heterogeneous influences to be considered. The alternative explanations as to why changes in these variables are indicative of changes to the organizational structure variable must also be considered in order to rule out coincidence or other variables not included in the testing. Even when organizational structure could be adapted to support innovative processes brought on by hybrid work environments, an association between the work environment and structure might be due to unobserved heterogeneity. Thus, changing structure may not produce the desired business outcomes.

Researchers Zoghi, Mohr, and Meyer (2010), identified that unobserved heterogeneity may be a factor when references are based on cross-sectional results (p. 624). For example, when identifying job design as a variable in the relationship; there is the issue that any job redesign may be affected by alternative concepts; such as work design. Whereas job design is the functional daily role of the process, the work design “goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390). When determining that job design is changing due to new processes wrought by the hybrid work environment; thereby,

influencing existing business processes and organizational structure; any moderator variables, such as work design, needs to be considered.

In this case, a third variable could be responsible for what was originally considered to be the association of changes in one variable, virtual job processes, with another one, work processes (Utts, 2005, p. 209). For example, the installation of a new application processing software program, to be used in both the traditional and virtual setting, may have nothing to do with the transition to a hybrid venue; however, it may cause a job and work redesign. In this case, the increased job productivity in the virtual setting may be influenced by a third variable, the software program. Overall, if the variables are not clearly defined and measured, the resulting changed organizational structure may or may not be a significant factor in achieving the company's goals.

Synthesis of research findings.

While the researchers agreed that a change to business processes effects structure; they have different perspectives in determining the reasons that substantiate redesigning structure. Also, not all agree on the interpretation of the conceptualization or operationalization of variables. Some concepts, such as work / job design, are based on the results of prior studies in the 1970s and 80s; others such as variables for describing organizational structures may yield different results in different contexts. That is, the operationalization of the variable may not relate to the hybrid workforce and organizational structures being studied.

In order to address this mismatch between processes and structure, the methodology proposed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) “helps to seek the organizational structure of a company that is needed to perform its business processes well” (p. 5411). Their analysis goes beyond the implications of social relations; therefore, their methodology focuses on the importance of the correlation of job / work / business process analysis and organizational structure (p. 5423). Nonetheless, the conceptualization of variables relating to organizational structure does differ. As a case in point, whereas Pleshko (2007), Fredrickson (1986) and Hatch (2006) used the variable complexity for describing organizational structures; structures are influenced by context. Therefore, the variable complexity may derive different results in different contexts (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013, p. 255). Given the challenges of conceptualizing

variables, some researchers have suggested beginning with a meta-analysis of priori thereof (p. 257).

In addition, changes to job / work / business process design in the hybrid environment have contributed to an increase in differentiation; thereby, leading to more complex organizations. Unfortunately, the argument is based on conceptual and empirical studies of work and organization design completed in the 1970s and 80s (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 389). Although the way that people work changed dramatically, the design of work is not up-to-date. Not surprisingly, the results of Sinha and Van de Ven's (2005) longitudinal study called for a "renewed research focus on work design" to improve reliability and validity of results (Abstract).

Furthermore, the contingency theory, "proposes that organizations are most effective when the design of their structures and processes is internally coherent and fits or matches their environment" (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 395). However, the vast changes in the organizational context and structure challenges the ability to identify all of the characteristics in any description; therefore, determining whether the design and environment is a 'fit' is difficult (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013, p. 120). Building the study on past research is further complicated by applications of the contingency theory that may not fully address current organizational structures and strategies. In summary, the external fit to demands and the internal structure has an inherent impact on strategy and structure that requires an in-depth application of contingency theory (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 400).

Unfortunately, particularly in the 1970s and 1980s, "much of the conceptual richness of the contingency theory was stripped away as researchers adopted simplified (or simplistic) models of the theory on their empirical studies" (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 396). Hence, the existing contingency results indicate the relative simplicity and stability of jobs and organizations; while the complex nature of jobs and organizations has had limited support (p. 396). That is to say, basing future research on past contingency theory results may not embrace the complexity of the hybrid job / work / business process designs and the influence on structure.

Critique of previous research.

An alteration of organizational structures needs to be understood from the basis of changes in more than a single variable, such as job / work design or revised business processes

(Cordes-Berszinn, 2013, p. 144). In addition, Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) recommended that since there is a diversity of organizational structures, future research needs to acknowledge the influence of their differences (p. 5423). Based on the studies presented in the literature review, the research involving the more complex issues regarding job / work design, business processes, and organizational structure may identify the scope of the evolving hybrid work environment. Comparatively, much of the research, including contingency theory studies, limit their scope of the complexity (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 396).

Empirical analysis is needed to link the complex relationships as well as disconnects in the functional structure (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 156). The analysis is complicated in that several of the researchers noted that there is no ideal 'fits all'; structure. In the hybrid venue, the strategic grouping, where formal and informal processes and structures are linked to coordinate task interdependence between units and subunits, is subject to change. For example, when the traditional work environment is changed to a hybrid one, study results indicate that the changes to the way that people work does create changes to business processes. The question remains as to what, how, and when these changed processes require revisions to the organizational structure and, possibly, strategy, as well.

Furthermore, whereas organizational structure could be adapted to support the changed business processes due to the hybrid work environments, changes may not produce the desired business outcomes. According to Cascio, organizational leaders should "think carefully about whether telecommuting actually fits with the strategy of their business and its operational needs. Without that strategic fit, telecommuting may cost a lot more, in the long run, in terms of lost business opportunities" (Meinert, 2011).

A point of illustration regarding the need to understand the match and mismatch of hybrid work, changed processes, and organizational structure, are the relatively current headlines of some major corporations. For instance, Yahoo! cancelled its hybrid work policy; Best Buy limited its policy; and Hewlett-Packard 'invited' its virtual workers to return to the traditional office. While a few of the studies in this literature review mentioned the challenges faced by these companies, the researchers did not include those cases in their analysis of actual causes

underlying decisions to revise the hybrid work policies. That is, they did not link theory, whether their own or from a review of prior studies, to statistical and practical significance.

For example, Ms. Mayer's announcement to recall Yahoo's 200 hybrid workers, cited a line of reasoning "that 'people are more productive when they're alone,' and then stressed 'but they're more collaborative and innovative when they're together. Some of the best ideas come from pulling two different ideas together'" (Tkaczyk, 2013). In the meantime, even with new product acquisitions and new hires, Yahoo! continues to struggle. The exciting and innovative 'start-up' culture that Ms. Mayer tried to instill became stagnant as a result of a combination of factors; such as antiquated employee micromanagement policies, employee assessments that discourage new ideas and deter challenging staid processes, and bad decisions regarding products and services investments (Tkaczyk, 2013).

Conversely, to understand the changing ways that people work and the influences on organizational structure, Microsoft brought "together experts from the fields of social change, workplace design, technology, public sector development and economics to identify several characteristics of businesses and organizations that are best placed to thrive in uncertain times" (Dodd, 2011). In contrast to Yahoo's policies that prioritized having all workers return to the structure of the traditional office to improve creativity, the Microsoft project concluded that the innovative and flexible hybrid workplace increased efforts. To support this fact, in the Microsoft project, the work is measured by outputs not inputs. The end result is that the hybrid environment frees people to work in a way that is most productive. The innovative and flexible workplace design, when supported with a range of technologies and tools that helped people do their jobs more effectively, is empowering; thereby, improving productivity and profitability to meet the demands of the rapidly changing market (Dodd, 2011).

In comparison, though Best Buy, once seen as a telecommuting leader, did not cancel its policy as Yahoo! did; employees now require management approval to work from home (Greene, 2013). Best Buy's decision is based on "sluggish sales" (Greene, 2013). Similar to Yahoo's decision, Best Buy also felt that having everyone work from the traditional office would help them recover their market share. Alternatively, several business reports, including Microsoft's, have identified quite the opposite. In fact, at "Microsoft's Amsterdam office—a

prototype of the hybrid organization structure—sales have increased 50% since employees have been free to work where and when they like, using mobile technology” (Dodd, 2011).

While the literature review identified that hybrid work policies have influenced processes and structure, research requires a more thorough analysis of the reasons for determining what, how, and when the organizational structure should, if at all, be modified. Maybe, as with Yahoo! and Best Buy, the status quo of the traditional workplace should be retained until the organization recovers or repositions its market share. Then again, the Microsoft studies indicate that goals to recover market share might best be attained with a flexible, adaptive organization—one that is ready to embrace the full potential of a hybrid work venue.

Summary.

The drive to accommodate a hybrid environment may be based several factors; such as, to promote the adaptability and flexibility needed to remain profitable and competitive. However, the literature review indicates that these advantages may be lost in the mismatch between the revised job / work / business processes introduced by the hybrid workforce and the existing organizational structure. Hence, the call for future research is promoted by several of the researchers referred to in this chapter. Some of the gaps in the existing research related to the hybrid work environment (traditional / virtual teams) include: the effects of existing work policies and workflow (Reiff-Marganec, 2012); cross-industry and longitudinal research on the effects on structure (Lin, 2011); and empirical research to update the design of jobs and work as based on the hybrid workforce relative to organizational structure (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005). In summary, further research is needed to identify the relationship of the hybrid work environment to the changes to job / work / business processes, and the effects, if any, of these changes on organizational structure.

Methodology

Introduction to the methodology.

In the hybrid environment, changes to existing task interdependencies may influence the coordination of activities; possibly requiring revisions to the organizational structures (Jost, 2011). In prior studies where the focus of research has been on business processes, the

emphasis has been on the standard issues of cutting time and expense; not on the connections between process and structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). In this study, the research will focus on that connection between processes, how they are conducted, by whom, and the influence on organizational structure (Wilson, 2010). The goals of the proposed study are to specifically explore the hybrid work environment, the changes to job / work / business processes, and the effects, if any, of these changes on organizational structure.

Internally, the structure assigns workforce activities, determines decision-making authority, and provides a framework for operational processes (Jost, 2011, p. 15). Externally, the volatile global market creates frequent changes in the context of the organization. Overall, organizational structure needs to have a combination of efficiency as well as flexibility in order to exploit resources to explore new endeavors (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013). Since some tasks require flexibility, while other tasks require stability; there is “practically no situation in which either of these extreme organizational structures, complete flexibility or stability, would be advisable” (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013, p. 114).

This research will seek to identify the effect of changes in the workforce; particularly the hybrid workforce business processes on existing structure. In addition, the alignment of the underlying business processes will be reviewed for productivity and cooperation between individual processes (Jost, 2011). Though process gaps resulting from the hybrid work environment may not be eliminated, the goal is to minimize gaps between departments (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). Given that the foundation for the research is multiple case studies of United States-based multinational organizations, the objective will not be to identify a structure that is advisable for any specific context (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013). Instead, suggested changes will describe restructuring to existing structures that are designed to support the organization’s strategic initiatives.

The mixed method research methodology will be used to develop a rich description of the hybrid work processes in an organizational setting (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). As an interpretive, inductive form of research, the multiple case study approach will be used to explore the in-depth meanings of experiences in a variety of contexts. The focus and results of research are relevant in that an organization’s decision to change structure, based on the interaction of job

/ work / business processes and the hybrid workforce, may potentially influence business productivity and profitability (Wilson, 2010).

The methodology proposed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) is used for conceptualizing variables. Their methodology relates to the purpose of the study in that it helps to identify the organizational structure of a company that is needed to perform its business processes well (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). Accordingly, DeCanio, Dibble, and Amir-Atefi (2000), propose that leaving out key factors that influence organizational behavior, including organizational structure, “will lead to inaccurate assessments of the effects of policy change” (p. 1298). In this study, the assessments of the effects of a policy change for the transition to a hybrid work policy will identify the influence on organizational structure.

Nonetheless, identifying the organizational structure that is appropriate for changes to job / work / business processes in a hybrid work environment is one issue; the other is recognizing the changes in processes that may have an effect on structure. To achieve these objectives, the research of Grant, Fried, Parker, and Frese (2010) regarding the mismatch of existing job design to current work; Reiff-Marganeic (2012) in identifying revisions in workflow; the methodology of Morley, Cormican, and Folan (2015) for organizational level changes; and the study of the effects of unobserved heterogeneity by researchers Zoghi, Mohr, and Meyer (2010); will be applied to discover key themes (Creswell, 2015).

This chapter will define the purpose and the research questions; then identify the target population; instrumentation to be used; data collection; identification of variables; and data analysis procedures. Limitations of the research design; expected findings; and ethical issues will also be recognized. The final section, the summary, will highlight key points and connect those points to the study’s purpose.

Purpose of the study.

The study will attempt to fill the gap in the literature on connections between hybrid workforce changes to processes and structure. Whereas studies support the need to understand the fluid nature of work processes and the effect on organizational structure, critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work on organizational structures and strategies have been left unanswered (Schreyögg, & Sydow, 2010). The purpose of the study is to explore the hybrid

work environment, the changes to job / work / business processes, and the effects, if any, of these changes on organizational structures. In association with that purpose, the definition of the hybrid work environment will include a traditional (physical office) and virtual (off-site location) workforce, in United States-based multinational organizations.

Research questions.

The goal is to identify the changing business processes in the hybrid venue and the effect on organizational structure. The central research questions are: How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What are the effects, if any, of these changes on organizational structure?

Research method.

Research on hybrid work environments indicates that members of organizations and their job responsibilities are evolving in ways that influence the way that work is done and business processes. The foundation of the organizational structure, the business units and their interrelated functions, are thereby affected. From an organizational research viewpoint, the “organizational dynamics and change are major areas of interest, and only qualitative methods are sensitive enough to allow the detailed analysis of change” (Cassell & Symon, 1994, p. 1).

The qualitative method will be applied to describe the characteristics of the population; specifically, the hybrid (traditional / virtual) workforce, their influence on job / work / business processes, and their subsequent effect, if any, on organizational structure (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). The rationale for using the qualitative design is that it will allow “the study of things in their natural settings, then attempt to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them” (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011, p. 3). The rationale is further strengthened because “qualitative analysis is not guided by universal rules, is a very fluid process that is highly dependent on the evaluator and the context of the study, and likely to change and adapt as the study evolves and the data emerges” (Pell Institute, n.d., Adapted from the National Science Foundation, 1997, User Friendly Handbook for Mixed Methods Evaluations.)

Sinha and Van de Ven (2005), maintain that integrating the job / work / business processes with organizational structure will require “methodologies that are strong on descriptive accuracy and designs that facilitate comparative analysis” (p. 400). The development of the

concept in research articles emphasize the use of multiple case studies and mixed methods to identify the effect of changing business processes on organizational structure. Several research studies presented in the literature review; i.e. Schreyögg and Sydow (2010) and Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012), indicated, respectively, that further theoretical and empirical analysis is needed regarding the effect of hybrid work environments on the organizational structure. While others, such as Grant, Fried, Parker, and Frese (2010), recommend meta-analysis of existing studies to clarify the identification and operationalization of variables.

Research design.

The case study approach has been selected for the following reasons: First, the goal will be to gain a holistic sense of the changes to business processes in the hybrid work environment and the subsequent effects, if any, on the organizational structure (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 484). Second, while there are questions as to why the phenomenon occurs, variables cannot be controlled. Controlling variables for a hybrid work policy for one department / employee and not for another may result in litigation (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 484). Third, primarily qualitative measures of variables, themes, and categories will be used to assess existing policies in several departments, including off-shore facilities (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 484).

The multiple case study research strategy is applicable in that there is no clear, single set of outcomes (Yin, 2003). “Widely used in organizational studies and across the social sciences”, the use of multiple case studies will provide the framework for an in-depth analysis of United States-based multinational organizations, with formal hybrid work policies (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 3). The research will be developed from a variety of sources; including open-ended blogs, surveys, organizational policy documents, and archival research. The aim will be to develop an awareness about a topic where there is insufficient published research and knowledge (Wilson, 2010).

To address the concern of several researchers covered in the literature review regarding conceptual clarity in organizational studies, e.g. Riemer and Vehring (2012), Grant, Fried, Parker and Frese (2010); this study will triangulate different kinds of data bearing on the same phenomenon to improve accuracy (Kohlbacher, 2006). The data triangulation will

counterbalance the weaknesses with the strengths of the research; thereby, generating a ‘thick description’ to include the context as well as the content of hybrid work environment; business, work, and job processes; and organizational structure (Kohlbacher, 2006).

Research population and sampling method.

The research population will be selected from multinational organizations representing several sectors; thereby, providing an array of content and contexts. Supporting demographic data will include the: company name, headquarters / home office location, and type of organization (Soyka, 2012). The study population is identified, as follows: the organizational data will be based on United States-based multinational organizations with off-shore facilities; and with a formal hybrid work policy.

The goal of this study is not to describe the entire population but to examine relationships; therefore, the nonprobability sampling method will be used. The procedure for achieving this type of sampling will be convenience sampling. That is, the sample will include organizations that are willing to participate; i.e. to provide new data; and / or those with existing organizational data; i.e. archived research data that is publicly available. Nonetheless, the method will be “consistent with Cooper and Schindler’s (1998) recommendation that samples are to be selected from a population that reflects the characteristics of the target population that it represents” (Vohra, 2014, p. 56).

Instrumentation.

In business research, the case study approach is used to conduct an in-depth analysis of a specific problem. In contrast to other qualitative approaches, the case study allows the collection and integration of both qualitative and quantitative data (Baxter & Jack, 2008). The qualitative data will include “multiple measures from different sources”; including open-ended blogs, organization policy documents, surveys and archival research (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 470). The examination will include more than one sub-unit; therefore, the basis of analysis will be embedded (Wilson, 2010). To illustrate, the research will be focused on multinational organizations; the units of analysis will include several departments, divisions, and/or subsidiaries. This embedded analysis is critical to identify bottle-necks or mismatches that occur as work is processed from one area to the next by the hybrid workforce.

Causal relationships will not be determined and the results of this study may not be generalizable beyond this study (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). On the other hand, because the measurements are based on behaviors in a natural setting and not in a controlled environment, the findings may be considered for generalization to common occurrences in the business sector. Accordingly, the business community has been calling for studies that engage with stakeholders beyond the research community; thus, the generalization of measurements from a natural setting as opposed to an experimental setting may be considered acceptable (Ellis, 2010).

Data collection.

Data preparation will be given considerable time and effort to assure that it is relevant to the analysis (Kudyba, 2014). Data credibility will be improved with the use of multiple data types and sources (Baxter & Jack, 2008). To improve reliability, the data will be organized in a database; thereby, allowing recorded details to be queried, compared, and contrasted (Baxter & Jack, 2008). The data sources will be joined in the analysis process to identify relationships; thereby, contributing to the understanding of the phenomena (Baxter & Jack, 2008).

Qualitative analysis will be used to “sort and summarize the data collection” from blogs, organizational policy documents, surveys, and archival research (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 140). (See Appendix C Blog Analysis.) The content analysis will be entered into tables to display the categories for further evaluation of relationships.

Secondary data, such as policy documents, including employee contracts, human resource policies, and formal work process descriptions, will be reviewed. (See Appendix D Sample Policy Documents.) The archival research will include information such as the percentage of increase / decrease in job productivity with the hybrid work option, any formal / informal changes to work / business process descriptions, and formal / informal changes to the organizational structure, i.e. departmental and managerial responsibilities. Notably, based on interviews conducted for my Master’s thesis, even one hybrid employee can change job and work processes; thereby, influencing structure.

Identification of variables.

Conceptualization of the variables is represented in the problem statement: Whereas studies support the need to understand the fluid nature of business processes and the effect on

organizational structure, critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on organizational structures have been left unanswered. The statement begets an image of the current growth of the hybrid workforce in organizations where documented job, work, and business processes have not been updated to reflect changed practices. The goal of this section will be to identify the operational variables for hybrid business processes and organizational structure.

The variables will be representative of the scenario; concepts, or key areas of research; i.e.: traditional / hybrid job design; traditional / hybrid work design; traditional / hybrid business processes; and organizational structure (Kudyba, 2014). In order to operationalize the concepts for measurement, the core, supporting, and strategic processes, as defined in the structures, will need to be identified (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a).

The operationalized variables, to determine the effect of hybrid business processes on organizational structure, are based on prior research and include the following (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 469): (1) Operational Variable: Job Design (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012); (2) Operational Variable: Work Design (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012); (3) Operational Variable: Business Processes (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a); (4) Operational Variable: Organizational Structure (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005).

Data analysis procedures.

The multiple case study approach allows for collection of data from a variety of sources; thereby producing large amounts of data that will need to be managed for thorough analysis (Baxter & Jack, 2008, p. 554). The data will be “organized in a database around certain topics and key themes; to be examined to determine how far they fit or fail to fit the expected categories” (Harley, 1994, 2004, as cited in Kohlbacher, 2006). There will be an in-depth analysis of information to identify within-case themes (Creswell, 2013, p. 209). The existing literature will also be referenced to determine if the findings of this study are consistent with or differ from extant research (Kohlbacher, 2006). Nonetheless, there are disadvantages that are recognized as coding the responses for categorical analysis can be prone to subjectivity, as well as time-consuming, and difficult (Wilson, 2010).

The categories, based on the methodology of Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012), will provide the foundation for the development of a matrix that will identify issues such as changes to links between processes. Because case studies are interpretive and inductive, the analysis can concentrate on the content of business processes as well as the context of the organization. The content of the business processes will rely on the descriptions in the formal job and work policies, actual functions, number of people involved, and end-to-end business processes. The context, or the surroundings of the organizational study of the hybrid work environment, includes the venue, the physical location, and the population (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016, p. 66). The goal is to identify prominent patterns in hybrid job, work and business processes; thereby, providing a foundation for developing a compelling profile that will link to the broader issue of changing organizational structure (TESOL, 2016).

To facilitate the analysis, qualitative data will be entered, processed, and reviewed immediately in the database; unimportant data will be filtered. The in-depth analysis of the coded data will be used to determine the following: whether this is any relationship(s) between the categories; the importance of the relationship(s); the consistency with previous research; and the differences or similarities between the categories (Wilson, 2010, p. 262). Coding will relate to the research questions of interests: How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What effect is there, if any, on the organizational structure? Categories previously developed by researchers, Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012), will be applied to create a priori or deductive coding (Wilson, 2010). Emergent or inductive coding will also be used to allow categories to develop during the examination of the data (Wilson, 2010).

Sub-categories, such as job design, will be linked to main categories, such as work design, with axial coding (Wilson, 2010). In order to establish consistency, the information will be double-coded; that is, the data will be recoded and results will be compared (Baxter & Jack, 2008). To identify subjectivity and to improve consistency, the coding process will also be used to establish a codebook that will “include a detailed description of each code, inclusion and exclusion of criteria, and examples of real text for each theme” (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000, p. 781). (See Appendix E: Codebook).

Throughout the coding process, the data will be examined; codes and categories will be explored; and patterns and themes will be identified (Wilson, 2010, p. 261). Content analysis will be used to examine the patterns in the data. The analysis of the content will also have to consider that context may change the meaning of the word; a problem that was identified by Grant, Fried, Parker, and Frese (2010) in the literature review. To substantiate the fundamental meanings of specific words, word analysis techniques, such as key-words-in-context, word counts, structural analysis, and cognitive maps will be practiced (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000).

Where applicable, the qualitative data will be quantified; such as, in counting the frequency of themes or categories (Wilson, 2010, p. 266). The risks associated with quantifying qualitative data will be considered. First, while counting strategies can help to organize data, a narrow-minded approach may lead to the loss of valuable information. Second, information that is not suitable for counting may be “discounted or ignored”. And, third, the possibility that the counted information would be considered more valid and reliable; thereby, ignoring the strengths of the qualitative approach (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016, pp. 441-2).

Research indicates that the transactions processed by the virtual / traditional workforce will be affected by changes to the job / work / business processes. Moderators, such as routine upgrades to computerized business applications, will influence the strength of the relationships; therefore, those variables will be identified and investigated, as well (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). For example, Putnam Investments, “early adopters of the telework initiative”, learned that instructions for a paperless workflow may influence the way that work is done and the number of transactions processed (Vega, 2003, p. 193). In the transition to a virtual / traditional option for their workforce, the processing operations at Putnam Investments experienced some differences in the interpretation of the instructions for getting the job done. In this case, the day shift and the night shift processed work under the same guidelines; yet, due to the interpretation of the procedures, the actual work differed. The day shift had transitioned to a “purely electronic task” approach (Vega, 2003, p. 195). On the other hand, though the night shift had the same set of instructions, their job and work task were not fully automated in that they continued to write down the “number of the item” that they worked on (Vega, 2003 p. 196). At the end of the night

shift, the handwritten pieces of information were manually entered “enter into a database in the supervisor’s office” (Vega, 2003, p.196).

At Clayton University, an increase in productivity of a virtual worker created a bottleneck for the next step of the process that was completed by traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office workers. Originally, three days were needed to complete the reports in the office; however, when that same employee transitioned to virtual work, the reports were completed within one day; thereby, creating a burden for those traditional office employees who were to follow-up in the next step of the process (Fenson & Hill, 2003).

While the transition to a hybrid (traditional / virtual) workforce is the topic of this study, any change in job tasks, appears to influence organizational structure as well. In their research, Knights and Sturdy identified organizational changes that resulted when processing moved from a manual system to a batch-processed, automated system. In that case, “a reorganization of the department, leading to the abandoning of the clerical section, which had become unnecessary...added to the disruption” (Varcoe, McNeill, & Yearly, 1990, p. 139). While several factors contribute to the changes, including technology disruptions and supplemental training, the crux of the situation appears to be based on the added requirements to ‘shift’ the work from the old system to the new. That is, the job processes had changed; however, the administrative mechanisms to control and integrate work activities had not.

Kahn’s 2000 study on record management identified the effect of sociotechnical systems and budgetary processes on innovation; however, the location of the offices, or spatial dispersion, also had an influence. In Kahn’s (2000) study, Campus Office A’s “geographic location near the center of the main campus” encouraged “alliance-building techniques” (p. 334-5). In due course, this alliance-building played a key role in the acceptance of the new system in that there was also a “shift in informal management structures” (Kahn, 2000, p. 344). This shift in administrative mechanisms crossed formal hierarchy resulting in a “flatter, more decentralized and informal organizational structure” (Kahn, 2000, p. 345).

Limitations of the research design.

Internal validity.

Generally, internal validity is determined by the results gained from “manipulation of the independent variable”; however, in this study, the independent variable cannot be manipulated (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 71). In a multinational organization, work policies may be subject to a number of local and government regulations; thereby, limiting the manipulation of the independent variable. Furthermore, perhaps with the exception of an explicit objective to test a formal pilot program prior to implementation; allowing hybrid work in one department and not in another to view the affect or changes could result in a violation of the Fair Labor Standards Act (FLSA) in the United States. (See e.g. <https://www.dol.gov/whd/flsa/> Search All DOL ‘telecommute’).

External validity.

Although there is a “growing confidence in the case study as a rigorous research strategy in its own right”, a case study is “generalizable to theoretical propositions and not to populations or universes” (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 4). Thus, whether the results of this qualitative case study might be generalizable to other geographic locations, types of organizations, and subpopulations with varying levels of hybrid policies for their workforce, is a problem that might encourage others to conduct empirical research on the central research questions (Adams & Lawrence, 2015). To sustain that fact, Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) noted that “the results of their analysis have to be proved by empirical, quantitative measures; such as actual logs of business processes” (p. 5423). From another viewpoint, because case studies are not conducted in an “artificial laboratory environment”, the results “may be more easily generalized to everyday life and thus may have greater external validity” (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 227).

However, the inherent differences between logical and statistical inference challenge the generalizability of qualitative findings (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016). Paul Ellis (2010) noted that many authors confuse statistical significance, suggesting that the findings are not due to chance alone; with substantive significance, concerned with what the meaning of the findings indicate about the population; when interpreting their research results. The power of statistical significance is based on finding an effect when there is an effect; that is, to reject the null

hypothesis when there is an effect (Ellis, 2010). Due to the lack of statistical power to detect small effects in the area of business research, there have been unacceptably high numbers of both Type I (incorrectly rejecting a true null hypothesis) and Type II (incorrectly retaining the null hypothesis) error rates; both causing invalid inferences regarding real-world effects (Ellis, 2010). Overall, invalid inferences by researchers and readers regarding the understanding and application of scientific and real-world effects are problematic (Ellis, 2010).

Transferability.

Whereas “generalizability usually applies only to certain types of quantitative methods, transferability can apply in varying degrees to most types of research”; including the qualitative analysis of this study (Writing@CSU, n.d.). The main issue is that “transferability is applied by the readers of research” when they make the connection between the study and their experience (Writing@CSU, n.d.). With regards to the connection between study and experience, “business disciplines are pushing towards relevance and engagement with stakeholders beyond the research community” (Ellis, 2010). That is, business is looking for research that is both scientifically valid as well as practical (Ellis, 2010). On the other hand, organizational processes have “multiple levels of meaning, embedded ambiguities, shifting zones of uncertainties, and emergent processes and outcomes” (Burnes & Randall, 2016, p. 100). The perspectives, views, interpreted experiences, and “emotive/political judgments” of the workforce further influence the transferability (p. 100).

Validation.

Credibility / Reliability.

In qualitative analysis, the arguments concerning content take priority over methodology; validity (accuracy) and not reliability (consistency) is of greater concern (Mayring, 2003, as cited in Kohlbacher, 2006). Since there are no hard rules for sample size in qualitative analysis, the sample size will be “determined by what the researcher wants to know, the purpose of the research, and what will be credible” (Vohra, 2014, p. 57). The qualitative content analysis approach will enhance rigor and validity (Kohlbacher, 2006). The multiple sources of data, along with the operational definitions of the variables, and the qualitative content coding, will improve the validity (accuracy) of the measurements to provide an explanation of the

phenomena. Overall, according to Patton (2001), “the validity, meaningfulness, and insights generated from qualitative inquiry have more to do with the information richness of the cases selected and the observation / analytical capabilities of the researcher than with sample size” (Vohra, 2014, p. 56).

Expected findings.

Based on the review of prior research covered in the literature review, the findings will indicate that there is a relationship between the changes in the hybrid job / work / business processes, and organizational structure. The methodology of Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) searches for an organizational structure that will help the company to improve its business processes; particularly with gaps in the end-to-end business processes from one unit to another (p. 5411, 5412). Although opportunities for improvement can be realized in understanding the work processes that move from one department to the next, the process gaps between departments can be minimized but “will never be eliminated” (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 193). When end-to-end inter-departmental processes are confronted with hybrid processes that are different, the receiving departments may reject revisions (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). Thus, the process gap analysis will be used to understand the process prior to the hybrid policy, the evolving hybrid process, and differences between the two; based on the issues, metrics, business impact, and opportunity; and will culminate with an introduction of recommended changes (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). The expected findings are that hybrid business processes will require organizational structure redesign (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a).

Current literature supports that there is a need to understand the fluid nature of work processes and the effect on organizational structure; however, critical questions about the nature and effects of hybrid work environments on organizational structures have been left unanswered. Hence, this study will contribute towards filling a gap in the literature by identifying the effects, if any, of the fluid nature of hybrid work processes on organizational structure in United States-based multinational organizations.

Ethical issues.

Ethics, in the context of business research, is defined in a number of ways; though, the stakeholder’s perspective is a common factor (Wilson, 2010). From the research stakeholder’s

perspective, ethics in business management research requires conducting the work in a “professional and responsible manner, the use of informed consent, careful control of deception, and careful interpretation” (Wilson, 2010, p. 82). The practice of adhering to Federal Regulations 45 CFR 46 will help to assure the goal of minimizing risk and bringing benefits to all involved. Overall, the research guidelines will include measures to proactively avoid or at least mitigate any violation to principles or procedures.

Conflict of interest assessment.

There is some risk for organizations and their employees taking part in the study; as well as for participants from external organizations (Wilson, 2010). In cases where employees or participants’ input may place their job in jeopardy, pseudonyms and other procedures to mask their identity will be used to lessen risk. In addition, the assessment will take into consideration the variety of cultures in the multinational organization; that is, what may be acceptable in one culture may be considered a conflict in another (Wilson, 2010).

Researcher’s position.

Due to my work and academic experience working virtually, I am biased toward promoting a hybrid work option. To maintain objectivity, the research will highlight organizations with successful, formal hybrid work policies; as well as organizations where policies have been revoked or challenged. By including both, my interest in promoting the hybrid work option will be balanced with information that may indicate when hybrid work is not feasible. Likewise, an objective understanding as to the relationship of hybrid work, job / work / business processes, and organizational structure may contribute to embracing change, as needed. Thus, some of the daily business challenges discovered in the literature review, such as those caused by mismatches in work processes, may be alleviated.

Ethical issues in the study.

Because the population for this study is United States-based multinational organizations with off-shore facilities, there may be ethical issues on an international level that may influence the results. The interpretation of the ethical guidelines for the study may be interpreted differently across cultures; thereby, directly affecting areas of the research (Wilson, 2010). For example, in multinational organizations, the transnational approach invites the transfer of

practices to, from and within the affiliates; parent organization and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others. In contrast, the global approach firms take an ethnocentric approach, managing the firm tightly from the center (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2009). In either case, “coordination is needed across multiple dimensions; e.g. functions, products, and geography” (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007, p. 212). Notwithstanding the contextual, legal, cultural, and political issues that may impact operations, the workforce viewpoints regarding hybrid work, job / work / business processes, and the overall effect on structure may vary. Adapting the view to one that aligns with the United States-based home office could affect the study; ultimately, influencing readers who seek to transfer the results to their own organization.

Summary.

In prior studies where the focus of research has been on business processes, the emphasis has been on the standard issues of cutting time and expense; not on the connections between process and structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). In this study, the research will focus on that connection between processes, how they are conducted, by whom, and the influence on organizational structure (Wilson, 2010). The increase / decrease in work and changes to processes will provide the foundation for the analysis of the influence of the hybrid workforce on the organizational structure. The cumulative data for sectors within the organization; divisions, departments, units; will provide a foundation for change with “a specific set of objectives that may save companies both time and money and increase shareholder value” (Bing, 2004).

The multiple case study approach has been selected for the following reasons: first, the goal will be to gain a holistic sense of the issues; second, variables cannot be controlled; and third, primarily qualitative measures of variables, themes, and categories will be used to assess existing policies (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 484). To address the concern of several researchers covered in the literature review regarding conceptual clarity in organizational studies, e.g. Riemer and Vehring (2012), Grant, Fried, Parker and Frese (2010); this study will triangulate different kinds of data bearing on the same phenomenon to improve accuracy (Kohlbacher, 2006). The objective is to generate a ‘thick description’ of the evolving organization.

Data Analysis and Results

Introduction to data analysis and results.

The purpose of the study is to understand the effects of the fluid nature of hybrid work processes on organizational structure. The research questions highlight the changing business processes in the hybrid venue and the effect on organizational structure: How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What effect is there, if any, on the organizational structure? To address the mismatch between processes and structure, the methodology proposed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) was used to identify changes to job, work, and business processes introduced by the hybrid workforce; and, where feasible, to provide suggestions for revisions to organizational structure (p. 5411).

In determining the organizational structure, the way that processes, affected by the hybrid work environment, are measured and managed were considered (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). The method of measurement is of particular interest as that information may determine how the organization should be structured (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). Nonetheless, measuring the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science. In 1997, “Ralph Westfall proposed a group of hypotheses concerning telework productivity suggesting that there were many pitfalls in measurements. He speculated that reported gains could be biased by factors such as selection of better workers for telework than for ‘normal’ work, unreliability of self-reported productivity gains, inability to separate improvements due to telework from overall management improvements, additional costs for telework not included in analyses, and difficulty in gauging returns that computers gain from telework as more employees participate” (Ruth & Chaudhry, 2008, p. 89). Currently, based on a study by Remote.co, some of the methods of measurement used by organizations to “evaluate and promote the efficiency of remote workers” include “setting clear metrics for each team member; setting short-term goals; monitoring if tasks are completed on time; hold regular team meetings to align goals, plans, and problems; quality of the work; feedback from 360-degree reviews; feedback from clients; performance reviews; focusing on results accomplished rather than time tracked; tracking activity levels and work screenshots; receiving a score on completed work; and tracking challenges that have been overcome” (Nevogt, 2016).

Needless to say, reorganization and restructuring is timely and expensive and may be avoided altogether with diagnosis of lower-level problems that can be resolved with smaller changes (Bing, 2004). Thus, when analyzing the measurements, individual process changes as well as department and unit data should be considered (Bing, 2004). Ultimately, “theory does not always lend itself to practice”; therefore, suggested revisions will not be presented as an ideal structure that will fit all requirements (Hunter, 2002, p. xii).

Description of the sample.

The description of the sample is United States-based multinational organizations, with off-shore locations, and formal hybrid work policies. The sample data was selected from organizations in several different horizontal and vertical markets; thereby, providing an analysis that is based on different contexts.

Research methodology.

In general terms, a business process can be defined as “a completed process within the organization which is characterized by a relationship to customers” (Jost, 2011, p. 187). Whereas processes are frequently linked to strategy and objectives; the business processes in this study—particularly those changed by the hybrid work policy—are identified with regards to their alignment to the organizational structure (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a). The analysis of the business processes includes differentiation within units / departments on the same level as well as vertical dimensions with decision-making delegated to the higher-level units / departments (Jost, 2011). Based on the literature review, the organizational differentiation and, hence, structure is influenced by the hybrid work policy (Reiff-Marganec, 2012; Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

First, the job, work, and business processes; involving both virtual and traditional workers; and covered by a formal hybrid work policy; were selected. The methodology of Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi (2012) was used to develop phases, as follows. (See Appendix F Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi Methodology). For phase one, organization data was used to identify if and where the work within and/or between departments or units change; resulting in increases / decreases. Both transactional information and data in the business log as well as what people ‘think’ is happening was analyzed (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 140). In phase two, a

post-process network was developed (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413). In this phase, bottlenecks in the processing network are discovered (p. 5414). In the third phase, a problem-oriented diagnosis of the process network was completed (p. 5413). For instance, the diagnosis for the bottle-neck revealed that working from home expedites the work process; thereby, creating a work overload for the next point of process. Moreover, management identified reduced collaboration between virtual and traditional office workers. In the fourth phase, the suggestions for complete redesign guidelines, as well as alternatives or partial redesigns, were applied to change the organizational structure (p. 5413).

Research design.

The design will reflect the “study’s purpose, research questions, and potential” (Pell Institute, n.d., Adapted from National Science Foundation, 1997). According to Yin (1994), when multiple cases are used, results are strengthened by replicating the patterns that, in turn, increase the robustness of the findings (Vohra, 2014, p. 55). Hence, the design framework is based on the multiple case studies approach to identify the nature and effects of hybrid work on processes; that, in turn, influence organizational structures. The multiple case studies from various sectors were selected to “produce detailed descriptions of the hybrid workforce phenomenon using constructs to order the data” (Vohra, 2014, p.55). Where possible, the constructs are also referenced to earlier literature.

The units of analysis included: organizational participants and their tasks within the structure; and transactions between organizational units and the alignment with the corporate goals (Jost, 2011). A within-case analysis will provide “a detailed description of each case and themes within the case” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). Then, “a thematic analysis across the cases” will be used to “search for themes that emerge as being important to the development of the phenomenon” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59).

Coding of the qualitative data was based on categories developed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012). The analysis identified the key themes and patterns or relationships based on those categories (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012, p. 560). Additionally, secondary quantitative data included reports provided by the organizations; information from organization Websites; and industry data.

The analysis will be enhanced by following “questions to ask throughout the qualitative analysis process” proposed by the National Science Foundation, User Friendly Handbook for Mixed Methods Evaluations (1997): (1) What patterns / common themes emerge around specific items in the data? (2) Are there any deviations from these patterns? (3) What interesting stories emerge from the data? (4) Do any of the patterns / emergent themes suggest that additional data needs to be collected? (5) Do the patterns that emerge support the findings of other corresponding qualitative analyses that have been conducted? (Pell Institute, n.d., Adapted from National Science Foundation, 1997).

Presentation of the data and results.

Variable: Job Design

Definition: Job design is defined as the functional daily role of the process (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390).

Objective: Identify increase / decrease in virtual (off-site) workforce productivity.

Qualitative Analysis: Increase / decrease productivity, virtual (off-site) worker.

Table 4.1: Virtual Work Productivity (See Also Appendix G: Prior Study by the Canadian Government: Perceived Change in Productivity of Teleworkers and Control Group).

US-Based Multinational Organization, Home Office Location	Market Sector	Virtual Work Productivity Increase / Decrease*
Aetna, Hartford, CT, US	Insurance	Increase
American Express, New York, NY, US	Credit Card / Travel Services	Increase
Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, US	Bank / Investments	Increase
Cisco, San Jose, CA, US	Technology	Increase
Hewlett-Packard, Palo Alto, CA, US	Technology	Increase
Honeywell, Morris Plains, NJ, US	Technology devoted to Energy Efficiency	Increase
IBM, Armonk, North Castle, NY, US	Technology	Increase
Intuit, Mountain View, CA, US	Technology / Tax Programs	Increase
Oracle Corporation, Redwood City, CA, US	Technology	Increase
Sutherland Global Services, Pittsford, NY, US	Technology	Increase

*From <http://www.reuters.com/article/us-yahoo-telecommuting-aetna-idUSBRE92006820130301>

*From <http://globalworkplaceanalytics.com/resources/costs-benefits>

*From http://icasit.gmu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Telework_Article_IEEE_Internet_Computing_Nov_Dec08.pdf

*From https://www.bestworkplaces.org/wp-content/uploads/2010/10/telecommute_benefit_brief.pdf

*Search 'mnc telecommute policy' on Google, results Home Page for several organizations

Summary of the Findings:

Variable: Job Design

Aetna

Job design is defined as the functional daily role of the process (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390). Generally, in comparison to their traditional 'brick and mortar' office counterparts, virtual workers are more productive. For example, "Shelly Ferensic, head of the claims department at Aetna which processes 1 million claims per day, has 2,000 employees around the country, about half of whom work from home" (Humer, 2013). Ferensic, formerly a virtual worker herself, currently works from Aetna's Florida office.

The claims processors receive the claims online, "handle more than 100 medical or dental claims a day, work out issues such as which provider needs to be reimbursed and then push them out" (Humer, 2013). Ferensic noted that "claims teleworkers are 10 to 20 percent more productive than their in-office counterparts and produce comparable quality" (Humer, 2013). Their productivity is "measured on producing a certain number of average claims per hour" (Humer, 2013). While the actual value of productivity and employee costs are not a factor in this paper, a simple calculation of virtual workers' productivity can be based on formulas, such as productivity value = time saved x employee costs. That is, the 10 to 20 percent increase reduces costs and improves profits. At Aetna, the one drawback is that virtual workers are not available to meet with customers when there are "issues that need to be handled in person" (Humer, 2013).

Variable: Work Design

Definition: Work design is defined as work that "goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers" (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390).

Objective: Identify hybrid workforce influence on work design; i.e. work that includes groups of virtual and traditional workers (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

Qualitative Analysis: The influence, if any, of the hybrid workforce on work design.

Table 4.2: Changes to Work Design:

US-Based Multinational Organization, Home Office Location	Market Sector	Virtual Work Policy-In-Force / Policy Cancelled / Revised	Influence on Work Design
Aetna, Hartford, CT, US	Insurance	Revised	Some workers required to return to traditional office to increase collaboration and drive innovation (Lee, 2016).
American Express, New York, NY, US	Credit Card / Travel Services	Policy-In-Force	Receptive to new ways to deliver superior customer service; Able to attract perspective employees across times zones; Allows for a more flexible working model (Remote.co, 2016).
Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, US	Bank / Investments	Revised	The global technology and operations division told to report to an office; foster teamwork and integration; provide opportunities for in-person collaboration; (Roberts, 2014).
Cisco, San Jose, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	The need for round-the-clock connection to service customer base requires employees to adapt when and where they work (Cisco, n.d.).
Hewlett-Packard (HP), Palo Alto, CA, US	Technology	Revised	Not totally banned; however, employees are being asked to work in traditional office during “critical turnaround period”; To strengthen culture of engagement and collaboration (Oremus, 2013).
Honeywell, Morris Plains, NJ, US	Technology / Energy Efficiency	Revised	Some workers required to return to traditional office to improve collaboration; Foster teamwork and ideas sharing (Depass, 2016).
IBM, Armonk, North Castle, NY, US	Technology	Revised	Some workers required to return to traditional office to improve collaboration; Creating small, self-directed agile teams (Isidore, 2017).
Intuit, Mountain View, CA, US	Technology / Tax Programs	Policy-In-Force	Intuit recognizes that great talent, required to service its expanding global footprint, is everywhere (Fell, 2015).
Oracle Corporation, Redwood City, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	Oracle recognizes that “workplace flexibility equals increased innovation” (Oracle.com, n.d.).
Sutherland Global Services, Pittsford, NY, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	Able to recruit the best talent from around the world to insure the best KPI performance (Sutherlandcloudsource.com, n.d.)

Summary of the Findings: Variable: Work Design

IBM

Work design is defined as work that “goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390). For some organizations, virtual workforce increased productivity does not always equal profitability. In cases where organizations have lost their market niche, creativity and innovation became a priority. Hence, IBM, once considered a pioneer in telecommuting, is requiring their virtual workers to return to the traditional ‘brick and mortar’ offices. As part of this initiative, IBM has “decided to co-locate the U.S. marketing department, about 2,600 people, which meant that all teams would now work together, ‘shoulder-to-shoulder’ from one of six different locations—Atlanta, Raleigh, Austin, Boston, San Francisco, and New York” (Kessler, 2017).

Several reasons have been cited for cancelling or at least reducing the virtual work options. Surprisingly, while virtual workers’ productivity is generally higher than traditional office workers, IBM stated the “need for more than better productivity right now” as a reason to cancel virtual work options (Kessler, 2017). Though productivity is a factor in longevity and profitability, IBM needed innovative ideas for future growth. Since “team proximity appears to help foster new ideas”, IBM decided to require teams to work ‘shoulder-to-shoulder’ in assigned brick and mortar offices (Kessler, 2017). The interaction effect was another factor. IBM “used data from badges that collect data on employee interaction to argue that employees who have more chance encounters and unplanned interaction perform better” (Kessler, 2017). Notably, interaction improves the effective communication and corroboration needed for innovation (Kessler, 2017).

Variable: Business Processes (End to End)

Definition: A term credited to Adam Smith, 1776; business process is defined as “a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal” (Appian, 2016). Of particular interest in this part of the study is the perception of existing and changed interdependencies or the relationship of organizational units required to accomplish the goal.

Objective: Identify bottlenecks in business processes due to changes introduced by the hybrid workforce (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a);

Qualitative Analysis: When changes are not recognized, the end-to-end business processes may become bottlenecked. The outcome could become a ‘blame-game’ whereby the bottlenecks may be blamed on the spatial and/or temporal position of the virtual / traditional workers; thus, overlooking advantages as well as disadvantages of those changes to processes.

Table 4.3: Changes to Business Processes (End-to-End)

US-Based Multinational Organization, Home Office Location	Market Sector	Virtual Work Policy-In-Force / Policy Cancelled / Revised	Bottlenecks / With Virtual Work Policy Yes / No	Corrective Measures
Aetna, Hartford, CT, US	Insurance	Revised	Yes: Bottleneck: Community Outreach to Members: Revisions in work from home policy will not affect the vast majority of workers; however, more employees will be sent into the field as part of enhanced community outreach to members (James, 2017).	Yes: Managers, particularly those with larger teams, will be required to work from the traditional office; Every day, face to face contact with team members to encourage collaboration and innovation on (James, 2017).
American Express, New York, NY, US	Credit Card / Travel Services	Policy-In-Force	No: Policy is clearly outlined in formal policies; Support and training of line managers is considered to be the cornerstone of flexible work success (Vercida, 2015).	None: Early on, focused on opportunity to build customer relationship; Improved talent management and work / life balance; i.e. work from home, flexible scheduling; Company policies revised to help customer service better assist customers; Resulted in improving customer relations and increased spending on Amex products (Krishnan, 2011).
Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, US	Bank / Investments	Revised	Yes. Bottlenecks for some teams where three-quarters of the team members were working from home (Rothacker, 2015).	Yes. Particularly in the Charlotte, NC area, telecommuters were required to return to the office for the following reasons: the difficulties with collaboration in distributed workforce; and the difficulties in building a culture when the workforce is overbalanced to working from home (Rothacker, 2015).

Cisco, San Jose, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	No. Technology supports collaboration, communication, etc between telecommuters / traditional office workers (Saltzman, 2017)	None. Cisco Virtual Office (CVO) allows employees to work remotely from their location or have CVO installed on their clients to VPN back to Cisco's network; Additional capabilities are added onto CVO; Cisco's premise is that properly executed programs for telecommuting can unlock employees' potential by increasing work-life balance, productivity, and overall satisfaction (Dubie, 2009).
Hewlett-Packard (HP), Palo Alto, CA, US	Technology	Revised	Yes. Bottlenecks created by insufficient virtual policy; i.e. workers were suddenly sent home and set adrift amid spending cuts was not a viable strategy for managing telecommuters and traditional office workers (Tate 2013).	Yes. Making space for people who want to come back into state-of-the-art offices with all of the amenities, while leaving the old work-from-home policies firmly in place (Tate, 2013).
Honeywell, Morris Plains, NJ, US	Technology / Energy Efficiency	Revised	Yes: Bottlenecks with idea sharing, decision-making, and agility when addressing changes in the global markets (Depass, 2016)	Yes: Requiring workers to return to office; Working from home to be allowed only for legitimate individual circumstances (Depass 2016).
IBM, Armonk, North Castle, NY, US	Technology	Revised	Yes: Bottleneck in the Marketing Department; Marketing is no longer a 'waterfall' process where work is handed from one person to the next (Weller, 2017).	Yes: 2,600 people from the Marketing Department will be required to work or 'co-locate' in one of six cities (Weller, 2017).
Intuit, Mountain View, CA, US	Technology / Tax Programs	Policy-In-Force	No: The organization strives to foster a flexible work culture; Recognizes that work is really about a partnership and setting expectations; Hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned (Fell, 2-15).	None: Organization has an Engagement Specialist, dedicated to the remote workforce, who coordinates offerings that are global and virtual (Fell, 2015).
Oracle Corporation, Redwood City, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	No. Oracle has developed an infrastructure to support collaborative efforts regardless of work location; i.e. telecommute or traditional office (Oracle.com, n.d.).	None. Oracle continues to develop policies, practices, processes, and technology for their workforce to provide elite customer service (Oracle.com, n.d.).
Sutherland Global Services, Pittsford, NY, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	No. The work at home division, CloudSource, sets up technology for each virtual worker; applicants are screened for specific skills related to virtual work; and management is trained to identify issues before they develop (Remote.co, 2015).	None. Sutherland Global continues to develop practices; i.e. hires applicants who have the skill set to work remotely: independent worker who is able to thrive without face to face interaction (Remote.co, 2015).

Summary of the Findings: Variable: Business Processes (End to End)

Business Processes (end-to-end), a term credited to Adam Smith, 1776, is defined as “a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal” (Appian, 2016). In this study, the organizations that revised / cancelled their virtual work policies include Aetna, Bank of America, Hewlett-Packard, Honeywell, and IBM. For example, Honeywell, faced with lackluster growth in the global industrial sector and restructuring within the New Jersey-based behemoth, revised their virtual work policy (Depass, 2016). Honeywell not only required workers to return to the office; it also restricts permission for work from home for legitimate individual circumstances (Depass 2016). The objective for requiring everyone to work from the ‘brick and mortar’ office is to encourage idea sharing, decision-making, and agility to address changes in the global markets (Depass 2016).

In comparison, Hewlett-Packard is making space for people in new state-of-the-art offices with all of the amenities, while leaving the old work-from-home policies firmly in place (Tate, 2013). From the start, Hewlett-Packard’s virtual policy, created on a somewhat ad-hoc basis when workers were suddenly sent home and set adrift amid spending cuts, did not provide a viable strategy for managing virtual and traditional office workers (Tate 2013). The revised policy appears to be the result of competition with low-cost providers, a massive change in how hardware and software was sold, and a series of management miscues (Darrow, 2016).

The organizations in the study with their virtual work policy-in-force include American Express, Cisco, Intuit, Oracle, and Sutherland Global Services. In this case, Intuit has an Engagement Specialist, dedicated to the remote workforce, who coordinates offerings that are global and virtual (Fell, 2015). Intuit recognizes that work is really about a partnership and setting expectations. Hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned (Fell, 2015). Overall, organizations that maintain a policy-in-force provide state-of-the-art technology and support for both their virtual (off-site) and traditional (‘brick and mortar’ office) workforce. They also recognize the global market changes in their respective industries; and then address those changes accordingly.

Variable: Organizational Structure

Definition: Organizational structure is defined as "the formal allocation of work roles and administrative mechanisms to control and integrate work activities, including those that cross formal organizational boundaries" (Child 1972, p. 2, as cited in Lin, 2011, p. 242).

Objective: Identify revisions to organizational structures.

Qualitative Analysis: The influence, if any, of the internal / external environment on organizational structures.

Table 4.4: Changes to Organizational Structure:

US-Based Multinational Organization, Home Office Location	Market Sector	Virtual Work Policy-In-Force / Policy Cancelled / Revised	Revisions to Organizational Structure	Organization Internal / External Environment
Aetna, Hartford, CT, US	Insurance	Revised	Restructuring associated with early retirement program; Acquired Humana Inc / Merging Humana's government related operations into Aetna's structure; Designing leadership structure for the combined companies (Pulliam, 2016).	Reduce its footprint on the Affordable Care Act exchanges; Retool Aetna's Compassionate Care program for patients with advanced illnesses and embrace alternative medicine (James, 2017). Decline in premium revenue; however, government business saw strong growth in membership and premiums; Government business being increased with acquisition of Humana Inc's government operations (Pulliam, 2016).
American Express, New York, NY, US	Credit Card / Travel Services	Policy-In-Force	Restructuring: the chief marketing officer will leave after 21 years at the company; the world service and global credit administration units will be merged into a single organization; an enterprise digital group is being created to centralize its web, mobile, and digital product management activities; layoffs in the Enterprise Growth unit (Wathen, 2016).	"As the battle for customer loyalty in the card industry became increasingly fierce, Amex recognized that its core competitive advantage had to be something that would be difficult to replicate: superior everyday customer service" (Krishnan, 2011).

Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, US	Bank / Investments	Revised	Integration of the Home Loans and Consumer and Small Business banking organizations (Comstock, 2011); Brokerage unit is being reduced from 10 to 6; The executives heading each of the 6 divisions will serve as ‘an extension’ to Andy Sieg, the head of Merrill Lynch Wealth Management (Thrasher, 2017).	Changes in customer demands, i.e. mobile check deposits, fewer delinquent loans / mortgage foreclosures; Increased challenges and requirements for cybersecurity; To provide worldwide support for global businesses, some jobs were moved from the U.S. to off-shore locations (Rothacker, 2015).
Cisco, San Jose, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	The number of councils, representing many different product areas, is being reduced from 9 to 3; Instead of focusing on big cross company goals or organizing new product teams to target a new market segment, the councils will now focus on enterprises, service providers, and emerging countries (Rosoff, 2011).	“Works with focus groups to identify which experiences could be better; Has made performance management much more inclusive and stopped moving from system to system (Morgan, 2016). Has initiated a wide-scale restructuring over the past year, looking to shift away from reliance on its core hardware business and expand into emerging growth markets; such as cybersecurity and the Internet of Things (IoT) industry (Delventhal, 2016).
Hewlett-Packard (HP), Palo Alto, CA, US	Technology	Revised	CEO Meg Whitman divided HP into two divisions: one would focus on the core business of printers and PCs; the other would pursue new areas such as cloud computing, data center hardware, and software (Darrow, 2016).	Experiencing competition with low-cost providers, a massive change in how hardware and software was sold, and a series of management miscues (Darrow, 2016).
Honeywell, Morris Plains, NJ, US	Technology / Energy Efficiency	Revised	Multiple leadership changes will have a positive impact on achieving the new 5-year plan for continued sales and margin rate growth and geographic expansion; Division structure change includes moving the Honeywell Process Solutions (HPS) from the ‘Automation’ group to the ‘Materials’ group (Mintchell, 2014).	Lackluster growth in the global industrial sector and restructuring within the New Jersey-based behemoth (Depass, 2016)

IBM, Armonk, North Castle, NY, US	Technology	Revised	Major corporate reorganization to focus on the cloud and move away from IBM's hardware, software, and service silo history that's long dominated its business structure; Global restructuring to create new business units for Research, Sales & Delivery, Systems, Global Technology Services, Cloud, Watson, Security, Commerce and Analytics (Kass, 2015).	Fundamental shifts in the industry are happening faster than IBM execs thought; Taking series of actions to accelerate IBM's transformation to reorganize around analytics, cloud, social, local, and mobile" (Kass, 2015).
Intuit, Mountain View, CA, US	Technology / Tax Programs	Policy-In-Force	Realigned Accountant related business to provide an increased emphasis on the company's growing global connected services; Will divest of Intuit Financial Services and Intuit Health Group; Realignment will facilitate accomplishment of two strategic goals: 'to be the world's small business operating system' and to 'do the nations' taxes in the United States and Canada' (Murphy, 2013).	Maintains market niche with the accounting application's look and feel that emulates hard-copy checks and ledger journals; Has in-house resources to drive change and innovation; such as the iPhone and Android apps for completing tax returns (Thomas, 2013).
Oracle Corporation, Redwood City, CA, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	Succession plan by founder, Larry Ellison: Two co-presidents, Mark Hurd, and Safra Catz, are to split the role formerly held by Ellison (Zillman, 2015); Structural change as Oracle switches to cloud offerings from core hardware offerings (Pramuk, 2015).	Maintains market niche with new products / acquisitions; i.e. PeopleSoft CRM for banking and capital market industries; and Oracle Retail to help retailers achieve faster concept-to-market, localized merchandising, and improved customer shopping experiences (Oracle.com, n.d.)
Sutherland Global Services, Pittsford, NY, US	Technology	Policy-In-Force	Has expanded its operations with new facilities in Las Vegas and Oklahoma City in the U.S.; and centers in Itajai, Brazil, Kingston, Jamaica, and Sweden (Business Wire, 2015).	Continues to establish itself as a leading and growing player in the global market for business process outsourcing services (Business Wire, 2015); Proactive in breakthrough technology, real-time analytics, domain expertise and service excellence; such as the virtual 'App Store' that will allow banks to select services that best fit their customers' evolving needs (PYMNTS, 2013).

Summary of the Findings: Variable: Organizational Structure

In the cases with revisions to the virtual work option policy; i.e. Aetna, Bank of America, Hewlett-Packard, Honeywell, and IBM, their organizational structures were also revised. For the most part, the revisions to the virtual work option policy to recall workers to the traditional office setting were based on the need to improve collaboration and innovation in a changing global market. For example, IBM, once a forerunner in promoting virtual work, determined that working face-to-face in a traditional office setting was needed in order to accommodate fundamental shifts in the industry. In this case, IBM had to take a series of actions to accelerate the organization's transformation to reorganize around analytics, cloud, social, local, and mobile; including revising their virtual work policy.

In comparison, the cases where the virtual work option policy remained in force; i.e. American Express, Cisco, Intuit, Oracle, and Sutherland Global, the organizational structures were also adapted to changes in the market. For the most part, since there were specific policies, managerial guidelines, and productivity goals for the virtual work option, the virtual workforce was not required to return to the traditional office. For example, structurally, Intuit recognized that they needed to realign their Accountant related business to provide an increased emphasis on the company's growing global connected services; however, the organization maintained its virtual work option. The structural realignment contributed to the accomplishment of two strategic goals: 'to be the world's small business operating system' and to 'do the nations' taxes in the United States and Canada'.

Framework for redesign: organizational structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

The framework underlying the proposed redesign or alternatives to redesign was completed in four phases: (1) collect source data; (2) derive a process network; (3) diagnose 3 problems; and (4) suggest alternatives of redesigning organizational structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413).

Table 4.5: Codebook

Question	Category	Sub-Category	Criteria	Code	Inclusion / Exclusion of Criteria	Source	Examples of Text
How do job designs change because of the hybrid work venue?	Job Design	Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers	Job design is defined as the functional daily role of the process.	J	Increase / decrease productivity, virtual (off-site) worker.	See Table 4.1	Aetna claims teleworkers are 10% -20% more productive than their in-office counterparts; Teleworkers were not available to meet with customers in-person when necessary.
How do work processes change because of the hybrid work venue?	Work Process	Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers	Work process is defined as work that goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers.	W	The influence, if any, of the hybrid workforce on work design.	See Table 4.2	While virtual workers' productivity is generally higher than traditional office workers, IBM needed innovative ideas for future growth. Since team proximity appears to help foster new ideas, IBM decided to require teams to work 'shoulder-to-shoulder' in assigned brick and mortar offices.

<p>How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue?</p>	<p>Business Process</p>	<p>Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers</p>	<p>Business process is defined as a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal</p>	<p>B</p>	<p>Bottlenecks in business processes due to changes introduced by the hybrid workforce</p>	<p>See Table 4.3</p>	<p>At Intuit, hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned. Overall, organizations, including Intuit and Oracle, that maintained a virtual / telecommute policy-in-force, also recognize the global market changes in their respective industries; and then address those changes accordingly.</p>
<p>Changes, if any, in the organizational structure?</p>	<p>Organizational Structure</p>	<p>Organizational Structure Changes; Internal and External Environment</p>	<p>The influence, if any, of the internal / external environment on organizational structures.</p>	<p>O</p>	<p>Internal / External Environment</p>	<p>See Table 4.4</p>	<p>In some cases, organizational restructuring, due to market and management changes, resulted in revisions to or cancellation of the virtual work option policy. In comparison, the cases where the virtual work option policy remained in force, the organizational structures also adapted to changes. However, the policies, managerial guidelines, and productivity goals continued to support the virtual work option.</p>

Derive a Process Network

J: Job Design: Aetna's ms teleworkers are 10 to 20 percent more productive than their in-office counterparts and produce comparable quality" (Humer, 2013). Their productivity is "measured on producing a certain number of average claims per hour" (Humer, 2013). The one drawback is that virtual workers are not available to meet with customers when there are "issues that need to be handled in person" (Humer, 2013).

W: Work Process: Surprisingly, while virtual workers' productivity is generally higher than traditional office workers, IBM stated the "need for more than better productivity right now" as a reason to cancel virtual work options (Kessler, 2017). Though productivity is a factor in longevity and profitability, IBM needed innovative ideas for future growth. Since "team proximity appears to help foster new ideas", IBM decided to require teams to work 'shoulder-to-shoulder' in assigned brick and mortar offices (Kessler, 2017).

B: Business Process: Intuit recognizes that work is really about a partnership and setting expectations. Hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned. Overall, organizations that maintain a virtual / telecommute policy-in-force, provide state-of-the-art technology and support for both their virtual (off-site) and traditional ('brick and mortar' office) workforce. They also recognize the global market changes in their respective industries; and then address those changes accordingly.

O: Organizational Structure: In some cases, where there were structural changes, there were also revisions to the virtual work option policy. The decisions to revise the policy; i.e. to recall workers to the traditional office setting, were based on the need to improve collaboration and innovation in a changing global market. In comparison, in other cases, where there were structural changes, the virtual work option policy remained in force; however, there were pre-existing policies, managerial guidelines, and productivity goals for the virtual work option.

Diagnose 3 Problems

Problem #1: Virtual Workers Recalled to Traditional Offices: Changes to Business Processes (End-to-End)

The hybrid workforce can result in a mismatch of business processes and organizational structure that prevent a company from reaching “operating achievements” (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5411).

For example, at IBM, because marketing is no longer a ‘waterfall’ process where work is handed from one person to the next, 2,600 people from the Marketing Department will be required to work or ‘co-locate’ in one of six cities (Weller, 2017).

Problem #2: Virtual Workers Recalled to Traditional Offices: Changes to Global Market: Products and Services

Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) identified that the dynamics between the organization’s processes and structure can determine whether a company is in a position to achieve its goals—or not (p. 5411).

At Honeywell, there were bottlenecks with idea sharing, decision making, and agility that adversely affected addressing changes in the global market. Thus, workers were required to return to the traditional office; working from home to be allowed for legitimate individual circumstances (Depass, 2016).

At IBM, fundamental shifts in the industry are happening faster than IBM executives thought; therefore, IBM is taking a series of actions to accelerate IBM’s transformation to reorganize around analytics, cloud, social, local, and mobile; including recalling virtual workers to the traditional office (Kass, 2015).

Problem #3: Virtual Workers Recalled to Traditional Offices: Improve Collaboration, Innovation

Cascio (2000) identified that, although all indications are that the hybrid work environment will grow, the virtual portion of the hybridity may not be appropriate for all jobs (p. 81). For some organizations, collaboration and innovation were viewed as being particularly challenging for the hybrid workforce.

At Aetna, some workers were required to return to traditional office to increase collaboration and drive innovation (Lee, 2016). At Bank of America, where three-quarters of the team members were working from home, telecommuters were required to return to the office for the following reasons: the difficulties with collaboration in distributed workforce; and the difficulties in building a culture when the workforce is overbalanced to working from home (Rothacker, 2015). Hewlett-Packard (HP) has asked employees to work in traditional office during a “critical turnaround period”. The reason is to strengthen the culture of engagement and collaboration (Oremus, 2013). On the other hand, Cisco has added capabilities onto their Cisco Virtual Office (CVO) for their virtual workforce. Cisco’s premise is that properly executed telecommuting programs can unlock employees’ potential by increasing work-life balance, productivity, and overall satisfaction (Dubie, 2009).

Recommended alternatives: redesigning organizational structure.

In order to address this mismatch between processes and structure, the methodology proposed by Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) “helps to seek the organizational structure of a company that is needed to perform its business processes well” (p. 5411). Their analysis goes beyond the implications of social relations; therefore, their methodology focuses on the importance of the correlation of business process analysis and organizational structure (p. 5423).

All 3 of the alternatives suggest that the first step should be recognizing the crux of the issues. Once those are determined, restructuring decisions can be considered. This approach is based on the case studies and additional scenarios presented in this paper where the organizations that instituted changes to the structure, including recalling virtual workers to the traditional office, did not fully investigate the underlying reasons as to why their product line or services were no longer profitable. What hybrid job, work, and business processes should have changed or did change but the changes were not formally recognized? Do these changes influence the organizational structure?

Alternative #1: Restructuring May or May Not Resolve Issues

Business Processes (End-to-End) Changes may not be improved with restructuring; i.e. virtual workforce recalled to the traditional offices. For example, at IBM, because marketing is

no longer a ‘waterfall’ process where work is handed from one person to the next, 2,600 people from the Marketing Department will be required to work or ‘co-locate’ in one of six cities (Weller, 2017). Nonetheless, those six cities, Atlanta, Raleigh, Austin, Boston, San Francisco, and New York, cover a wide geographic area (Kessler, 2017). That is, the spatial positions of workers; such as a worker in Atlanta and another in Boston, remains virtual.

Whether the worker is located in a virtual or traditional office, the spatial boundaries of teams “include geographic differences” that affect overall coordination and performance (Cummings, Espinosa, & Pickering, 2007, p. 85). In essence, communication and collaboration may be the issues that need to be resolved. In some cases, restructuring created a larger problem when virtual workers were ordered to return to the office.

Organizations, such as Intuit, recognize that work is really about a partnership and setting expectations. Some organizations, such as Oracle and Sutherland Global Services, make it a point to proactively initiate practices and policies, as well as improve technology, to continually develop their global market position. That is, those organizations tap into the resources of their workforce; regardless of the spatial positions.

Alternative #2: Adapt to Changes in the Internal Environment

Current trends indicate that flexible organizational structures are proven to enhance profitability in the competitive, global market (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010). Other viewpoints offer that flexibility overlook the practicality of the guidelines for work provided by organizational processes and boundaries. From this other view, the formal process and boundaries promote operational effectiveness needed to achieve corporate goals (Schreyögg & Sydow, 2010).

In the hybrid, traditional / virtual workforce, reaching out to another worker no longer means walking down the hall to a meeting room. Thus, the lack of physical presence can no longer be perceived as a barrier. Instead, the worker must be able to expand their spatial dimensions to tap into whatever resource is needed. Some organizations, such as Cisco with their Cisco Virtual Office application, have recognized the benefits of creating an environment where virtual and traditional workers have the ability to “reach out and communicate to other workers” (Kimball, 1997).

On a related note, due to the popularity of online education, games, and shopping; many job applicants know how to function in virtual environments. A key area that is missing is the ability to manage in the virtual environment. Even some of the forerunners in offering virtual work options, such as IBM, have faltered. At Intuit, this roadblock has been addressed by adding the position of Engagement Specialist, who is dedicated to the remote workforce, and coordinates offerings that are global and virtual (Fell, 2015).

Alternative #3: Adapt to Changes in the External Environment

The challenges of the global market range from differences in the customer base to differences in time zones to changing product lines. Regardless, today's organizations must be adaptable and flexible to meet that challenge. Improved customer service was a common theme for the organizations depicted in this paper. Cisco recognized that the round-the-clock connection to their service customer base required employees to adapt when and where they work (Cisco, n.d.). In response to that need, Cisco has created the Cisco Virtual Office (CVO) application that allows employees to work remotely from their location; or they can have CVO installed on their clients to VPN back to Cisco's network. Additional capabilities are added onto CVO, as needed.

Cisco has also recognized the changes in their external market. Hence, Cisco has initiated a wide-scale restructuring over the past year, looking to shift away from reliance on its core hardware business and expand into emerging growth markets; such as cybersecurity and the Internet of Things (IoT) industry (Delventhal, 2016). In addition, Cisco's council framework, representing many different product areas, has been reduced from 9 to 3. Instead of focusing on big cross company goals or organizing new product teams to target a new market segment, the council will now focus on enterprises, service providers, and emerging countries (Rosoff, 2011).

Summary.

The complexity and dynamics of the hybrid workforce challenge existing organizational structures; particularly multi-divisional structures such as in the multinational organizations depicted in the multiple case studies (Jost, 2011). Moreover, the studies by Piccoli, Powell, and Ives (2004) indicate that the complete transfer of current practices used for traditional teams in the workplace to the hybrid environment can potentially be problematic. Thus, proactive

revisions that recognize new practices contribute to the success of the hybrid work policy (Piccoli, Powell, & Ives, 2004). Organizations, such as Oracle, Intuit, and Sutherland Global, have adapted their management practices and technology to support the hybrid workforce from their virtual or traditional work location, while also adapting to the global market. Others, such as Honeywell have restricted their virtual work policy to regain the market position.

Conclusion and Discussion

Introduction.

In prior studies where the focus of research has been on business processes, the emphasis has been on the standard issues of cutting time and expense; not on the connections between process and structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). The goal of this study was to identify the changing business processes in the hybrid venue and the effect on organizational structure. The central research questions are: How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue? What are the effects, if any, of these changes on organizational structure? The research population, selected from a variety of sectors of multinational organizations, provided an overview of the issues in an array of content and contexts.

Summary of the results.

Overall, the results are consistent with the literature review, the organizational differentiation and, hence, structure is influenced by the hybrid work policy (Reiff-Marganiec, 2012; Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). The first variable, job design, is defined as the functional daily role of the process (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390). In the ten organizations selected for this study, in comparison to their traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office counterparts, virtual workers were found to be more productive. However, the interpretation of this productivity changed over time; particularly when market changes affected profitability. The second variable, work design, is defined as work that “goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390). For some organizations, profitability, not the increased productivity of the virtual workforce, became the focal point. Particularly, in cases where organizations lost their market niche, creativity and innovation became a priority; hence, shoulder-to-shoulder teamwork was emphasized. The virtual work option was revised or restricted altogether. The third variable, business processes

(end-to-end) is defined as “a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal” (Appian, 2016). In some cases, where business processes were no longer accomplishing organizational goals, the virtual work policy was revised. Those revisions appear to be the result of market changes (external) and a series of management issues (internal). The fourth variable, organizational structure, is defined as "the formal allocation of work roles and administrative mechanisms to control and integrate work activities, including those that cross formal organizational boundaries" (Child 1972, p. 2, as cited in Lin, 2011, p. 242). The decisions frequently involved restructuring and recalling virtual workers to the traditional office setting. The common objective was to reassess alignment with goals to regain market position.

Discussion of the results.

When technology also includes a virtual workforce, there are challenges from the internal environment as productivity in job, work, and business processes, particularly standardized processes, are changed. All of the organizations depicted in this study initially indicated that virtual workers’ productivity is generally higher than traditional office workers. Subsequently, the importance of the increased levels of productivity changed. For example, IBM, once considered a forerunner in promoting virtual / telecommute work options, stated the “need for more than better productivity right now” as a reason to revise the virtual work policy (Kessler, 2017). Though productivity is a factor in longevity and profitability, IBM needed innovative ideas for future growth. Since “team proximity appears to help foster new ideas”, IBM decided to require teams to work ‘shoulder-to-shoulder’ in assigned brick and mortar offices (Kessler, 2017).

In contrast, under the premise that properly executed telecommuting programs can unlock employees’ potential by increasing productivity, Cisco offers a state-of-the-art Cisco Virtual Office (CVO) application to allow their workforce to work from wherever they choose (Dubie, 2009). Essentially, Cisco has successfully used technology to redefine the traditional organizational structure; i.e. traditional ‘brick and mortar’ offices. By doing so, the organization was able to offer their employees the option to adapt to when and where they work to provide round-the-clock connection to service their customer base (Cisco, n.d.).

The external environment, diverse and ever-changing, creates its own set of far reaching sociopolitical, geographic, and economic implications and threats that vary in severity and frequency (Bhamra, 2016). Hence, efforts must be made to develop “robust and resilient organizational systems capable of withstanding and responding to the uncertainties and challenges” (Bhamra, 2016, p. 4). When Honeywell was faced with the uncertainty and challenge of lackluster growth in the global industrial sector, the organization was restructured and their virtual work policy was revised (Depass, 2016). Honeywell not only required workers to return to the office; it also restricted permission for work from home for legitimate individual circumstances (Depass 2016). The objective for requiring everyone to work from the ‘brick and mortar’ office is to encourage idea sharing, decision-making, and agility to address changes in the global markets (Depass 2016).

In comparison, organizations, such as Intuit, also faced with external uncertainties and challenges; adapted structures to changes in the market. However, Intuit did not recall their virtual workforce to the traditional office. Structurally, Intuit recognized that they needed to realign their Accountant related business to provide an increased emphasis on the company’s growing global connected services. This realignment contributed to the accomplishment of two strategic goals: ‘to be the world’s small business operating system’ and to ‘do the nations’ taxes in the United States and Canada’.

Discussion of the results based on the literature review.

Codes or labels for the categories originated from the analysis of the data, the terms used in the case studies, and from sources of existing theory and literature identified in Chapter 2 of this paper (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). In order to provide meaningful categories, the following were identified and included as part of the analytical framework: data and categories that related to external categories; the relationship of data categories that were concept driven as being derived from existing theory and literature; and those categories that were data driven as being derived from data and actual terms supplied by organizations (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012).

As categories appeared throughout the process, some earlier categories were merged while others were divided. In order to maintain consistency, an up-to-date definition of each

category was maintained in the codebook (See Appendix E Codebook) (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). Generally, patterns and relationships identified the effect of the hybrid workforce on business processes and, hence, on organizational structure. The results related to the literature review in that researchers identified key roadblocks, incentives, advantages, disadvantages; for organizations with a hybrid work policy. (See Table 5.1 Linking Existing Literature to Categories).

Table 5.1: Link Existing Literature to Categories

Concept Driven	Data Driven	
Derived from Existing Theory and Literature	Derived from Analysis	Actual Terms Used by Organization
<p>Structure influences the organization’s workforce and business units; thereby, affecting internal and external business processes (DeCanio, Dibble, & Amir-Atefi, 2000).</p>	<p>In the structure, whether the worker is located in a virtual or traditional office, the spatial boundaries of teams “include geographic differences” that affect overall coordination and performance (Cummings, Espinosa, & Pickering, 2007, p. 85). In essence, communication and collaboration may be the issues that need to be resolved. In some cases, restructuring created a larger problem when virtual workers were also ordered to return to the office.</p>	<p>Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, U.S.</p> <p>The global technology and operations division told to report to an office to foster teamwork and integration; and to provide opportunities for in-person collaboration (Roberts, 2014).</p>
<p>The dynamics between the organization’s processes and structure can determine whether a company is in a position to achieve its goals (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).</p>	<p>Business Processes (end-to-end) are defined as “a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal” (Appian, 2016). Overall, organizations that maintain a policy-in-force, provide state-of-the-art technology and support for both their virtual (off-site) and traditional (‘brick and mortar’ office) workforce. They also recognize the global market changes in their respective industries; and then address those changes accordingly.</p>	<p>American Express, New York, NY, U.S.</p> <p>“As the battle for customer loyalty in the card industry became increasingly fierce, Amex recognized that its core competitive advantage had to be something that would be difficult to replicate: superior everyday customer service” (Krishnan, 2011).</p> <p>Their support and training of line managers is considered to be the cornerstone of flexible work success. (Vercida, 2015). That is, the process and structure places the organization in a position to achieve its goals</p>

<p>Methodology may or may not correctly impact the outcome of an analysis of pre-existing problems to assure successful implementation of a hybrid workforce (Zoghi, Mohr, & Meyer, 2010).</p>	<p>Work design is defined as work that “goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390).</p> <p>When the work is measured by outputs not inputs, the end result is that the hybrid environment frees people to work in a way that is most productive. The innovative and flexible workplace design, when supported with a range of technologies and tools that helped people do their jobs more effectively, is empowering; thereby, improving productivity and profitability to meet the demands of the rapidly changing market (Dodd, 2011).</p> <p>From a practical, business perspective, SHRM [Society for Human Resource Management Global Diversity & Inclusion Division] “advocates that companies should be managing by results, not ‘butts in seats”” (Meinert, 2011).</p>	<p>Yahoo! and Microsoft</p> <p>Ms. Mayer’s announcement to recall Yahoo’s 200 hybrid workers, cited a line of reasoning “that ‘people are more productive when they’re alone,’ and then stressed ‘but they’re more collaborative and innovative when they’re together. Some of the best ideas come from pulling two different ideas together” (Tkaczyk, 2013). In the meantime, even with new product acquisitions and new hires, Yahoo! continues to struggle (Tkaczyk, 2013).</p> <p>Conversely, to understand the changing ways that people work and the influences on organizational structure, Microsoft brought “together experts from the fields of social change, workplace design, technology, public sector development and economics to identify several characteristics of businesses and organizations that are best placed to thrive in uncertain times.” In contrast to Yahoo’s policies that prioritized having all workers return to the structure of the traditional office to improve creativity, the Microsoft project concluded that the innovative and flexible hybrid workplace increased efforts (Dodd, 2011).</p>
<p>Research on hybrid work environments indicates that individual members of organizations and their job responsibilities are evolving in rapid ways (Gutterman, 2013).</p>	<p>Particularly in the 1970s and 1980s, “much of the conceptual richness of the contingency theory was stripped away as researchers adopted simplified (or simplistic) models of the theory on their empirical studies” (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 396). Hence, the existing contingency results indicate the relative simplicity and stability of jobs and organizations; while the complex nature of jobs and organizations has had limited support (p. 396). That is to say, basing future research on past contingency theory results may not embrace the complexity of the hybrid job / work designs and the influence on structure.</p>	<p>Yahoo! cancelled its hybrid work policy; Best Buy limited its policy; and Hewlett-Packard ‘invited’ its virtual workers to return to the traditional office. While a few of the studies in this literature review mentioned the challenges faced by these companies, the researchers did not include those cases in their analysis of actual causes underlying decisions for hybrid work policies. That is, they did not link theory, whether their own or from a review of prior studies, to statistical and practical significance.</p>
<p>All indications are that the hybrid work environment will grow; however, the virtual portion of the hybridity may not be appropriate for all jobs (Cascio, 2000).</p>	<p>Empirical analysis is needed to link the complex relationships as well as disconnects in the functional structure (Jeston & Nelis, 2008a, p. 156).</p>	<p>Two contrasting examples to emphasize the need for empirical analysis:</p> <p>At “Microsoft’s Amsterdam office—a prototype of the hybrid organization structure—sales have increased 50% since employees have been free to work where and when they like, using mobile technology” (Dodd, 2011).</p> <p>At IBM, marketing is no longer a ‘waterfall’ process where work is handed from one person to the next, hence, 2,600 people from the Marketing Department will be required to work or ‘co-locate’ in one of six cities (Weller, 2017).</p>

<p>With the adoption of the hybrid workplace, differentiation, or differences in policies and practices, is likely to increase; possibly requiring changes to organizational structures and systems (Cohen & Gibson, 2002).</p>	<p>While hybrid work environments can challenge cooperative efforts to integrate and coordinate work across organizational units, the demand for flexibility to address these challenges cannot stop at the specific area(s) of the business process directly using the hybrid environment—it needs to extend throughout the entire organization.</p>	<p>Oracle has developed an infrastructure to support collaborative efforts regardless of work location; virtual off-site or traditional brick and mortar office (Oracle.com, n.d.).</p>
<p>The hybrid work environment will require agility that also builds an inclusive identity that transcends where and how work is done (Gan, 2016).</p>	<p>For the most part, the revisions to the virtual work option policy to recall workers to the traditional office setting were based on the need to improve collaboration and innovation in a changing global market.</p>	<p>Interaction effect is a factor in building an inclusive identity. In revising their virtual work option, IBM “used data from badges that collect data on employee interaction to argue that traditional office employees who have more chance encounters and unplanned interaction perform better” (Kessler, 2017). Notably, interaction improves the effective communication and corroboration needed for innovation (Kessler, 2017).</p>

(Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhills, 2012)

Limitations.

With the advances in technology, physical presence for many types of work systems and products are no longer required. Researchers George Gonzales-Rivas and Linus Larsson (2011) go so far as to suggest that “any system that requires physical presence is probably suboptimal” (p. 105). However, they also note that, though the technology is ready to support virtual work environments, many company cultures are not ready for the transition (Gonzales-Rivas & Larsson, 2011). McLennan’s (2008) research identified that the “attitudes, habits and mental models” of the workforce may not be ready to embrace the transition to a hybrid, traditional / virtual option (p. 146). Managers may also be reluctant to measure the “degree of comparative effectiveness”; thereby, missing opportunities that a hybrid workforce may have to offer (Bing, 2004).

Likewise, this study does not account for the effect of cultural differences that may produce different results. The renowned studies of Geert Hofstede, the most researched body of quantitative cross-cultural research in the literature, includes Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, Individualism/Collectivism, Masculinity/Femininity, and Long/Short-Term Orientation (Bing, 2004). These cultural differences are definitely a consideration in a

multinational organization; wherein the home office is likely to set the tone for innovation and change management.

Implication of the results for practice, policy, and theory.

This research identified some of the changes to job, work, and business processes introduced by the hybrid workforce. The goal was to determine if and when a change to organizational structure is needed to facilitate the workflow. Because job processes interact with other work and business processes at the departmental and organizational level, understanding changes in the way that work is done in the hybrid work venue and the influence of those changes, can help the organization to meet its strategic and operational initiatives as well as the expectations of internal and external stakeholders (Gilley, Gilley, Quatro, & Dixon, 2009).

In determining the influence of the hybrid work process on structure, the organization may emphasize goals that are easily quantifiable; thereby, overlooking the complexity of the situation (Tolbert & Hall, 2009). In this case, the organization may undertake change without a real perspective on the nature of the issues; thus, the efforts may produce outcomes that may or may not have real benefits (Tolbert & Hall, 2009). The conversion to technology may also cause some ‘unpopular’ rework of business processes and workflows. For instance, in one traditional / virtual workforce, the virtual workers were able to expedite the process by using technology to alert agents that the information was available for their clients. The traditional, physical office workers continued to call agents; frequently delaying the process, as the agents were not always available for the standard phone call. The delays increased when agents forgot to check voicemail. The conversion to the technology used by the virtual workforce was challenged on many fronts; eventually, the organization succeeded and delays were decreased.

Recommendations for further research.

Business research has the challenge of meeting the ‘double hurdle’; it must be both theoretically and methodologically rigorous while also meeting the world of practice and being of practical relevance. Basically, powerful, busy executives look for practical consequences of the findings. In addition to meeting the standard requirements of advancing knowledge and understanding, business research “also needs to address business issues and practical managerial problems” (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012, p. 9).

Further studies should span a variety of types and structures of organizations. Society-at-large, particularly those in the workforce, would benefit from understanding the overall effects of organizational forms, practices, and consequences in different venues. Because of the array of issues and effects, a recommendation for further research would be to begin by delving into assumptions about how organizations should look and operate (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016). Additionally, these multiple case studies, as well as much of the research covered in the literature review, concentrates on issues within the organization. However, the effect of changes in the organization, such as the influence of the hybrid work venue on business processes and structure, may be carried into other practices; i.e. based on geography, politics. A comparative analysis of various fields; ranging from vendors and professional groups, to business litigation, “would enable researchers to chart variations in these effects across organizational environments” (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016, p. 108).

Conclusion.

In their literature review, Martins, Gilson, and Maynard (2004) concluded that “with rare exceptions all organizational teams are virtual to some extent. We have moved away from working with people who are in our visual proximity to working with people around the globe” (Ebrahim, Ahmed & Taha, 2009). Agreed. That moving away from working with people who are in our visual proximity continues to expand; encompassing different types and sizes of businesses, in many countries. Whether the teams are referred to as ‘virtual’, ‘co-located’, or ‘traditional’, the issue is to recognize the impact of the changing workforce on the business processes and organizational structure.

Appendix A: Conceptual Map

With the implementation of hybrid work policies, business processes are changed; thereby, indicating a need for organizations to realign structures and strategies to adapt to the new methods and workflow.

Definitions

Hybrid Work Policies allow for a variety of combinations of traditional / virtual work schedules; i.e. alternating days in the traditional / virtual offices; virtual office only; traditional office only or as needed.

Organizational Structure is defined as "the formal allocation of work roles and administrative mechanisms to control and integrate work activities, including those that cross formal organizational boundaries" (Child 1972, p. 2, as cited in Lin, 2011, p. 242).

Conceptual Map

The Influence of Hybrid Work on Business Processes and on Organizational Structure

Combined Hybrid Workforce: Traditional and Virtual Office Workforce

The hybrid environment offers the adaptability and flexibility needed to remain profitable & competitive.

Appendix B: Cranet Survey: Increased Hybrid Workforce

Center for International Human Resource Studies (CIHRS) at the Pennsylvania State University,
Cranet Survey, 2014/2015 Highlights

II. Working Arrangements

Trends show more frequent use of teleworking and less frequent use of part time working arrangements.

Proportion of Employees Using Teleworking vs. Part Time Arrangements

Appendix C: Blog Analysis

Case Studies Cited in this Paper

Blog Results: Generally, align with the results in this paper. Initially, virtual work is considered an asset for both the workforce and the organization. Ultimately, issues such as external market changes and internal management / organizational restructuring lead to revised or cancelled virtual work policies.

Organization	Pros	Cons
Aetna, Hartford, CT, US	Pros: Flexible Time and Telecommute Policy ¹ Ability to work at home in some positions	Con: Ending Telecommute Company Wide ¹
American Express, New York, NY, US	Pros: Virtual WFH Great Work Life Balance / Lot of Roles are Work from Home ²	Cons: Management Lacks Vision Work / Life Balance is good; Technology and business leadership struggles to get on the same page; Still operates in a command and control manner ²
Bank of America, Charlotte, NC, US	Pros: Flexible Schedules Lots of accommodations and options available for employees who may be facing hard times in life outside of work ³	Cons: Good Work / Life Balance But... The organization went through a lot of changes since the recession and cut so many jobs; especially on the mortgage banking side ³
Cisco, San Jose, CA, US	Pros: Work / Life Balance Overall, great work / life balance ⁴	Cons: Remote Teams Long work hours to work with remote teams after hours ⁴
Hewlett-Packard, Palo Alto, CA, US	Pros: Work / Life Balance Excellent; Able to work from home ⁵	Cons: No Work / Life Balance due to restructuring ⁵
Honeywell, Morris Plains, NJ, US	Pros: Work / Life Balance Company helps you keep a balance between your personal and professional life ⁶	Cons: Work / Life Balance is greatly determined by the individual department in which you work and your direct supervisor ⁶
IBM, Armonk, North Castle, NY, US	Pros: Sufficient Flexibility for a Reasonable Work / Life Balance ⁷	Cons: Reduced Work / Life Balance Due to restructuring; increased layoffs and long hours ⁷
Intuit, Mountain View, CA, US	Pros: Flexible Work Including Telecommuting and Hours ⁸	Cons: Collaborative work environment; however, roles are not always clear. Need to work on developing management; leadership needs to take chances and be more bold. ⁸
Oracle Corporation, Redwood City, CA, US	Pros: Work / Life Balance Virtual work from home environment; The ability to work from home was a huge benefit ⁹	Cons: Work / Life Balance You're expected to be on email 24X7; Virtual work required weekly management updates with data charts and written summaries; Mandatory attendance on weekly conference calls where verbal input would be a requirement ⁹
Sutherland Global Services, Pittsford, NY, US	Pros: Work From Home The option to work from home is a plus; organization offers good pay with possibility to make a bonus; vacation accrual / tenure ¹⁰	Cons: Work from Home: Company doesn't pay for time where their equipment doesn't work; It takes more than a week to get equipment replaced; help desk is the worst assistance ¹⁰

1 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Aetna/reviews>

2 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/American-Express/reviews>

3 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Bank-of-America/reviews>

4 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Cisco/reviews>

5 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/HP/reviews>

6 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Honeywell/reviews>

7 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/IBM/reviews>

8 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Intuit/reviews>

9 From <http://www.indeed.com/cmp/Oracle/reviews>

10 From <http://www.glassdoor.com/Reviews/Sutherland-Reviews-E25705.htm>

Appendix D: Sample Hybrid Policy Documentation
Global Workplace Analytics (2015).

Samples from <http://globalworkplaceanalytics.com/sample-documents>

There are a variety of forms of hybrid policy documents that address issues such as the company's overall policy; the understanding between the company and its workforce; and the formal guidelines of the policy.

The following is a sample agreement specifying the "who, when, what, and how of offsite work including expectations for availability and communications" (Global Workplace Analytics, 2015).

Sample Teleworker Assignment from Global Workplace Analytics (2015)

Teleworking, or working from another location such as home or an office close to home, is an assignment that the company may choose to make available to some employees when a mutually beneficial situation exists.

Teleworking is not an employee benefit, but rather an alternative method of meeting the needs of the company. Employees do not have a "right" to telework. The arrangement can be terminated by either the employee or the company at any time.

Conditions for teleworking agreed upon by the teleworker and his/her supervisor:

1. The employee agrees to work at the following location:

2. The employee will telework _____ days per week.

3. The employee's work hours will be from _____ a.m. to _____ p.m.

4. The following are the assignments to be worked on by the employee at the remote location, with expected delivery dates:

5. The following equipment will be used by the employee at the remote location:

6. The employee agrees to call the central office to get his/her messages at least _____ times per day.

7. The employee agrees to get all supplies needed for teleworking from the company office. Reimbursement for out-of-pocket expenses for supplies will need prior supervisory approval.

8. Additional conditions agreed upon by the telemanager and teleworker are as follows:

I have reviewed the teleworker's assignment with _____ prior to his/her participation in the company's teleworking program.

Date

Supervisor Name

The above material has been discussed with me.

Date

Employee Name

Appendix E: Codebook

Objective: provide (1) detailed description of each code; (2) inclusion / exclusion of criteria; and (3) examples of real text for each theme

Question	Category	Sub-Category	Criteria	Code	Inclusion / Exclusion of Criteria	Source	Examples of Text
How do job designs change because of the hybrid work venue?	Job Design	Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers	Job design is defined as the functional daily role of the process.	J	Increase / decrease productivity, virtual (off-site) worker.	See Table 4.1	Aetna claims teleworkers are 10% -20% more productive than their in-office counterparts; Teleworkers were not available to meet with customers in-person when necessary.
How do work processes change because of the hybrid work venue?	Work Process	Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers	Work process is defined as work that goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers.	W	The influence, if any, of the hybrid workforce on work design.	See Table 4.2	While virtual workers' productivity is generally higher than traditional office workers, IBM needed innovative ideas for future growth. Since team proximity appears to help foster new ideas, IBM decided to require teams to work 'shoulder-to-shoulder' in assigned brick and mortar offices.

<p>How do business processes change because of the hybrid work venue?</p>	<p>Business Process</p>	<p>Hybrid Workforce: Traditional 'brick and mortar' office and Virtual 'off-site' workers</p>	<p>Business process is defined as a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal</p>	<p>B</p>	<p>Bottlenecks in business processes due to changes introduced by the hybrid workforce</p>	<p>See Table 4.3</p>	<p>At Intuit, hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned. Overall, organizations, including Intuit and Oracle, that maintained a virtual / telecommute policy-in-force, also recognize the global market changes in their respective industries; and then address those changes accordingly.</p>
<p>Changes, if any, in the organizational structure?</p>	<p>Organizational Structure</p>	<p>Organizational Structure Changes; Internal and External Environment</p>	<p>The influence, if any, of the internal / external environment on organizational structures.</p>	<p>O</p>	<p>Internal / External Environment</p>	<p>See Table 4.4</p>	<p>In some cases, organizational restructuring, due to market and management changes, resulted in revisions to or cancellation of the virtual work option policy. In comparison, the cases where the virtual work option policy remained in force, the organizational structures also adapted to changes. However, the policies, managerial guidelines, and productivity goals continued to support the virtual work option.</p>

Appendix F: Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi Methodology

The framework of a methodology has four phases: (1) to collect source data; (2) to derive a process network; (3) to diagnose 5 problems; and (4) to suggest alternatives of redesigning organizational structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012, p. 5413).

Appendix G: Prior Study by the Canadian Government:

Perceived Change in Productivity of Teleworkers and Control Group

Productivity: Major companies, such as American Express, reported that their contact center telecommuters process substantially more calls and close more business than their in-office counterparts. In comparison to the United States-based multinational organizations depicted in this paper, Figure 1 is an illustration of increased telecommuting productivity in research conducted by the Canadian federal government (Avaya, Inc, 2008). Note that, similar to the results in this paper, the overall productivity of virtual workers researched by the Canadian Government also increases.

Figure 1: Productivity Changes in a Telecommuting Environment

**Organizational Management in
the Hybrid (Combined Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’)
Transnational Organizations**

Version Fall, 2018

Abstract

The general topic is management of the hybrid (combined virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce in transnational organizations. Although studies support the need to understand managing virtual teams; e.g. Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015; the effects on organizational management when the virtual option of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policies is revised or revoked in transnational organizations require further research. Hence, the central question is to identify any effect on management when changes are made to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy. The research questions are: Is management affected, if at all, when changes are made to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy? If at all, what management decisions are made as a result of those changes?

According to a survey of 18,000 business professionals across 96 international companies by Switzerland-based IWG , “70% of people globally work remotely at least once a week” (Browne, 2018). Another study by American-based research firm, Gallup, found that “the number of American employees working remotely rose to 43 percent in 2016 from 39 percent in 2012” (Browne, 2018). Alternatively, research by the Bureau of Labor Statistics American Time Use Survey indicates a two percent decrease from 2015 to 2016 in the number of remote workers (Spector, 2017). Overall, there is a “changing perception around location and working hours”; thereby, contributing to an increase in hybrid (virtual / traditional office) work policies and practices (Browne, 2018).

From a positive perspective, research results indicate that hybrid (virtual / traditional office) work policy does help to achieve strategic goals; such as through reduced turnover rates; and increased productivity and employee commitment (Grantham, Ware, Swanberg, et al, 2009,

p. 9). To illustrate, the results of a 2014 study by co-founders of CTrip, a Chinese travel website, identified that “with all other factors being equal, the remote workers made 13.5 percent more calls than their comparable office workers” (Alton, 2017). The number of phone calls by the remote workers “is the equivalent of almost a full day’s worth of work in a given week” (Alton, 2017). Similarly, “a ConnectSolutions study found that 77 percent of remote workers get more done in fewer hours” (Alton, 2017). The increase was due to “fewer distractions like meetings, conversations, and noisy coworkers” (Alton, 2017).

On the other hand, there are negative aspects, as well. A growing concern is the “privacy and security issues posed by a distributed global workforce of people who work digitally and use multiple devices” (McAfee, 2011). Particularly, the digital platform and multiple devices pose a challenge in cases where the employee ceases their employment with the organization. In order to secure sensitive, proprietary information, managers need to be able to lock the user out of the devices (McAfee, 2011). Another challenge is that collaboration and knowledge-sharing remains a key issue in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce. A suggested solution to this challenge is to retain at least some conventional office space or conference facilities for face-to-face meetings (McAfee, 2011).

While some organizations are increasing their flexible work arrangements, allowing the employee to elect to work from home or from the traditional office; other organizations are recalling their virtual workers to the traditional office; see e.g. Swisher, 2013; Marks, 2017; Roberts, 2014. Reasons for revoking the virtual work portion of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy are based on objectives, such as, to promote communication and collaboration (Swisher, 2013); for corporate restructuring and turn-around (Bednarz, 2013); to facilitate the decision-making process (Marks, 2017); and to improve customer service (Roberts, 2014). In addition to the internal reasons, revising or revoking a hybrid (virtual / traditional) work option may be due to changes in the external consumer market; i.e. spending and shopping habits, as well as product / service preferences.

From a theoretical view, Alfred Chandler’s (1977) ‘visible hand’ of management (Harvard University, n.d.) and Adam Smith’s (1776) ‘invisible hand’ of a self-regulating force of a free market (Biography.com Editors, 2018) are being tested. In addition to the challenges of

the ‘invisible hand’ of an evolving global market, the ‘visible hand’ of management has broader issues in dealing with employee relations, where the virtual / traditional workforce for a department may span several geographic locations and time zones.

Furthermore, in 1776, Adam Smith recognized the importance of technological development; noting that the worker should be provided with the best machines that could be purchased or invented (Biography.com Editors, 2018). Whether they work virtually or in traditional offices, workers need state-of-the-art tools, and management thereof, “that help handle complex tasks once reserved for specialists—to streamline work processes, make sense of the overwhelming volumes of data besieging them, and improve productivity” (McAfee, 2011).

The general topic of this research is management of the hybrid (combined virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) workforce in transnational organizations. Whereas studies support the need to understand managing virtual teams, e.g. Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015; critical questions about the effects of the hybrid work environments on organizational management have been left unanswered. The purpose of this study is not to determine the effectiveness of management styles or decisions per se; but to determine the effects on management, if any, when the virtual option of the work policy is revised in the transnational organization.

Overview: Management Theories

Basically, theories are a “collection of ideas that provide the framework for effective management strategy” (Business.com Editorial Staff, 2017). As it is common for managers to practice more than one of the management theories, it is important to understand how they can be implemented in an organization, and how to monitor the results.

This section begins with a brief history of management, then proceeds with an overview of management theories. The management theories are applied to the Discussion Points: Case Studies section.

Early civilizations did use some forms of management. For example, in 350 B.C., Plato described job specialization. In 400 B.C., “management practices and concepts were discussed by Socrates” (iEduNote.com, n.d.). And, “the Egyptians applied the management functions of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling to construct the pyramids” (iEduNote.com, n.d.).

Nevertheless, for the most part, those earlier management functions “centered around political activities leading to the expansion of empires and maintenance thereof” (iEduNote.com, n.d.).

It wasn't until the growth of family businesses in the 18th Century and the development of large organizations in the later periods of the 19th Century that “people began to concern themselves with business management” (iEduNote.com, n.d.). Particularly, with the growth of industries during the Industrial Revolution, “a new era of serious thinking and theories of management” developed (iEduNote.com, n.d.). During this time, the actual “systematic study of management began” (iEduNote.com, n.d.).

In the late 19th Century and early 20th Century, Frederick Winslow Taylor developed the Scientific Management Theory. “The key issue around the Scientific Management Theory”, also known as ‘Taylorism’, “is improving labor productivity” (Yimeng, 2017, p. 103). One tenet of theory proposes that personal judgments or ‘rule of thumb’ should not be part of management decisions. Instead, “the work assigned to any employee should be observed and analyzed with respect to each element or part thereof and the time involved” (Kalpana, n.d.). However, in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization, the lack of opportunity to observe each element or part thereof and the time involved is one of the reasons that organizations revise or revoke the virtual portion of the virtual / traditional work policy. In many cases, “managers often struggle when traditional ‘eyeball’ management or ‘management by walking around’ styles are no longer realistic” (Montero, P. & Montero, J., 2010/2011).

Frank Bunker and Lillian Moller Gilbreth's 1911 publication of *Motion Study* described their time-and-motion study. The study “systematically investigated and analyzed the mechanics and timing of specific tasks” (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2018). Fundamentally, the two differed in their approach. Where Frank Gilbreth “was concerned with the technical aspects of worker efficiency, Lillian Gilbreth was concerned with the human aspects of time” (SDSC.edu, n.d.) Dr. Lillian Gilbreth recognized management challenges that remain significant in today's workplace: 1) workers are motivated by indirect incentives (money) and by direct incentives (job satisfaction); 2) the effects of fatigue; and 3) stress on time management (SCSC.edu., n.d.).

Dr. Lillian Gilbreth's management challenges continue to be a factor in today's hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization. For instance, the option to work virtually reduces fatigue and stress on time management in that it "allows employees to have better work-life balance and improves their health and wellness" (Vasel, 2017). There is also the financial indirect incentives in that it saves "more than \$4,000 in savings each year thanks to reduced expenses on things like gas, parking and public transit costs and dry cleaning" (Vasel, 2017).

In 1916, the French engineer, Henry Fayol, created the first principles of management theory (Van Vliet, 2011). In his famous 14 general principles of management, Fayol "defined five functions of management for the management component" that are still considered relevant in today's organizations (Van Vliet, 2011). These five functions, planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and controlling; all focus on the relationship between the workforce and management. It is the last point, controlling, particularly in a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, that has been a challenge for management.

Controlling requires establishing performance standards based on organizational objectives, measuring and reporting on actual performance, comparing results with performance and standards, and taking corrective and preventive measures as needed (Van Vliet, 2011). Measuring the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science; and a combined virtual and traditional workforce presents additional challenges. In 1997, "Ralph Westfall proposed a group of hypotheses concerning telework productivity suggesting that there were many pitfalls in measurements. He speculated that reported gains could be biased by factors such as selection of better workers for telework than for 'normal' work, unreliability of self-reported productivity gains, inability to separate improvements due to telework from overall management improvements, additional costs for telework not included in analyses, and difficulty in gauging returns that computers gain from telework as more employees participate" (Ruth & Chaudhry, 2008, p. 89).

In 1924, Mary Parker Follett identified factors that can also be applied to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) organization. Follett, who believed that management was the art of getting things done through people, proposed an idea that resonates to today's hybrid workplace: it is not

where work takes place but to “focus on the science of getting people to cooperate”; instead of “power over, believe that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003). Mary Parker Follett based the development of her management theory on the principles of coordination: (1) direct contact between employees and management to help organizations avoid conflicts and misunderstandings; (2) in the early stages, coordination should be learned and mastered; (3) reciprocal relationships / team efforts: regardless of their level in the hierarchy, everyone is responsible for pulling their weight and integrating with the rest of the organization; and (4) coordination is a continuous process that must be maintained (Caramela, 2018). Whether the workplace is a virtual work-from-home setting or a traditional ‘brick and mortar’ office, in the global setting, the workforce is scattered. Hence, the challenge is in developing policies and practices for direct contact, coordination, reciprocal relationships, and continuous process thereof through technology.

In the 1950s, Peter Drucker’s interest in the behavior of people led to his development of the modern study of management. Drucker identified 5 basic tasks of managers: sets objectives, organizes, motivates and communicates, measures, and develops people (Murray, n.d.). For the most part, the 5 basic tasks continue to be a staple for managers. Nevertheless, some aspects of the basic tasks have changed in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace.

In particular, Drucker’s tasks of communication has become a challenge for managers of a combined virtual / traditional workforce / teams. In the hybrid, traditional / virtual workforce, communicating with workers no longer means walking down the hall to a meeting room. Instead, the managers must be able to expand their spatial dimensions to tap into whatever resource is needed. Some organizations, such as Cisco with their Cisco Virtual Office application, have recognized the benefits of creating an environment where virtual and traditional workers, including management, have the ability to “reach out and communicate to other workers” (Kimball, 1997).

In 1977, Alfred Chandler’s *The Visible Hand: The Managerial Revolution in American Business*, replaced Adam Smith’s (1776) invisible hand of market forces, with the visible hand of management. Whereas Smith’s ‘invisible hand’ described “the unobservable market force that helps the demand and supply of goods” in a free market to reach equilibrium automatically (The

Economic Times, n.d.); Chandler's 'visible hand' identifies the importance of the role of management in maintaining equilibrium.

The multiunit, multifunctional enterprise described by Chandler were the forerunners of today's global, transnational organizations (Harvard University, n.d.). In the transnational organizations, the visible hand of management is expanding as managers now contend with a variety of work policy options; e.g. collocation, virtual, traditional, and any combination thereof. That combined with Smith's invisible hand of the global marketplace presents a challenging force-in-action.

Objective

The overall objective is to identify the impact, if any, on management when the virtual option of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce policy is revised or revoked in the United States-based transnational organizations.

Problem Definition

Although studies support the need to understand managing virtual teams; e.g. Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015; the effects on organizational management when the virtual option of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policies is revised or revoked in transnational organizations require further research.

Significance of Problem

Major United-States based, transnational organizations, such as IBM, Honeywell, and Hewlett-Packard, with longstanding hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policies, are requiring their virtual workers to return to the traditional office. There are a variety of stated reasons for those changes; i.e. lack of communication and idea sharing due to expanded virtual / collocated workforces; and delays in decision-making (Kessler, 2017; Depass,2016).

In contrast, the "Intuit 2020 Report, Twenty Trends that will Shape the Next Decade" noted that "the brick-and-mortar office will be a thing of the past, as the where and how people work and do business will change due to emerging Internet cloud and mobile technologies. Working in the cloud will increasingly shift work lives away from corporate offices altogether and toward an in-my-own-place, on-my-own-time work regimen" (Intuit, 2020).

Regardless, the problem is significant in that management is concerned with “the organization and coordination of the activities of a business in order to achieve defined objectives” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). Ultimately, changes in work policies, such as hybrid (virtual / traditional), affect the organization and coordination of activities; e.g. managing how and where work is done. To complicate matters, in the transnational organization, managing the policy change requires coordination across multiple regions.

Research Questions

Hence, the central question is to identify the effect on management when changes are made to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy. The research questions are: Is management affected, if at all, when changes are made to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy? If at all, what management decisions are made as a result of those changes?

Research Method, Methodology, and Design

The multiple case study research strategy is applicable in that there is no clear, single set of outcomes (Yin, 2003). “Widely used in organizational studies and across the social sciences”, the use of multiple case studies will provide the framework for an in-depth analysis of United States-based transnational organizations, with formal hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policies (Kohlbacher, 2006, p. 3). A within-case analysis will provide “a detailed description of each case and themes within the case” (Vohra, 2014, p. 59). The rationale for the basically qualitative design is to allow “the study of things in their natural settings, then attempt to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them” (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011, p. 3).

Limitations of Research Design

Case studies are a popular research method in the business area. The overall goal of this type of study is “to analyze specific issues with the boundaries of a specific environment, situation, or organization” (Research-Methodology.net, n.d.). From a business viewpoint, because case studies are not conducted in an “artificial laboratory environment”, the results “may be more easily generalized to everyday life and thus may have greater external validity” (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 227).

However, from a research standpoint, “manipulation of the independent variable” determines internal validity. In a transnational organization the manipulation of the independent variable may be limited by local and government workplace / workforce regulations (Adams & Lawrence, 2015, p. 71). Thus, in this context, the results lack logical and statistical inference that may challenge the generalizability of qualitative findings (Elsbach & Kramer, 2016).

Expected Findings

The expected findings are that changes to the virtual part of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy in the transnational organization does have an impact on management. In addition, this study will contribute towards filling a gap in the literature regarding management and hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy and practices.

Discussion Points: Case Studies

Introduction

In each of the case studies, the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce policy is a formal standard. That is, there were human resource policies and practices guiding the workforce, including management. However, in some cases where the *Invisible Hand* of the marketplace created changes, the *Visible Hand* of management determined that revising or even revoking the virtual portion of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy was necessary. In other cases, changes in the marketplace were dealt with differently. Management recognized the market changes and adapted their products / services accordingly. The hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy remained in-force.

Within the transnational model depicted in the case studies, the research questions are: Is management affected, if at all, when changes are made to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work policy? If at all, what management decisions are made as a result of those changes?

Management theories covered in the section, Overview: Management Theories, will be applied to this section through the lens of Adam Smith’s *Invisible Hand* of the marketplace and Alfred Chandler’s *Visible Hand* of management.

Case Study #1: Intuit

Intuit, headquartered in Mountain View, California, “is a business and financial software company that develops and sells financial, accounting, and tax preparation software and related

services for small businesses, accountants, and individuals. More than 95% of its revenues and earnings come from its activities within the United States. The company has offices in eight other countries around the world: UK, Australia, France, Singapore, India, Brazil, Canada, and Israel” (Wikipedia.org, 2018).

Intuit has adapted their management practices and technology to support the hybrid workforce from their virtual or traditional work location, while also adapting to the global market. For instance, Intuit has an Engagement Specialist, dedicated to the remote workforce, who coordinates offerings that are global and virtual (Fell, 2015). Moreover, hiring managers define role expectations, location, and then work with candidates to ensure that their expectations are aligned (Fell, 2015).

Discussion Point

When Intuit recognized that global market requirements required revisions within the organization, management did not revise or revoke the virtual portion of their work policy. Instead, they realigned the Accountant related business to provide an increased emphasis on the company’s growing global connected services. Overall, the objective of the realignment was to facilitate accomplishment of two strategic goals: ‘to be the world’s small business operating system’ and to ‘do the nations’ taxes in the United States and Canada’ (Murphy, 2013).

Whereas Intuit has an Engagement Specialist, dedicated to the remote workforce, who coordinates offerings that are global and virtual; the organization is also developing a friendly, campus-like environment, in a traditional office-park setting (Thomas, 2013). The plan, to encourage innovation through its in-house resources, was based on the fact that in the entire decade prior to 2007, “only 4 out of 50 products introduced had grown to \$50 million or more in revenues” (Thomas, 2013). The results were positive. “In 2012, Intuit got \$100 million in revenues from products that didn’t even exist three years ago” (Thomas, 2013). In this case, Peter Drucker’s five basic tasks of managers: sets objectives, organizes, motivates and communicates, measures, and develops people; were evident in the successful outcome (Murray, n.d.). Notably, the organization reverted to a traditional office-park setting for development.

Case Study #2: Sutherland Global

According to their Web site, Sutherland Global is “a process transformation company that rethinks and rebuilds processes for the digital age by combining design-thinking insights and data-driven analytics.” Sutherland “completes 43 million transactions a month on a digital backbone that spans 19 countries around the world for more than 120 clients” (Sutherlandglobal.com, n.d.).

When Sutherland Global was struggling to maintain its market niche, management did not revise or revoke the virtual portion of their work policy. Instead, the organization utilized its in-house resources to drive change and innovation and realigned its accountant related business to provide an increased emphasis on the company’s growing global connected services (Murphy, 2013; Thomas, 2013). Sutherland Global continues to develop human resource practices to sustain those in-house resources; i.e. applicants are screened for specific skills related to virtual work; specifically, applicants who have the skill set to work remotely and are able to thrive without face to face interaction are hired (Remote.co, 2015). Moreover, management is trained to identify issues before they develop (Remote.co, 2015). In addition, the work at home division, CloudSource, continues to improve its technology for each virtual worker. (Remote.co, 2015). Furthermore, “as a top employer for remote workers”, Sutherland Global “has adopted SmashFly’s Total Recruitment Market Platform to unify its recruitment marketing tools for global talent acquisition; and to manage how its global recruiters attract, engage, nurture and convert qualified candidates into job applicants” (SmashFly Technologies, 2015).

Discussion Point:

Before Sutherland Global decides to move into a geographic region, several factors are taken into consideration. Primarily, it has to have a “good, healthy scalable pool of talent”; a “robust infrastructure”, and a “business-friendly environment” (Knowledge@Wharton, 2009). That being considered, when Sutherland Global Services announced in 2012 that it was bringing 600 jobs to Alexandria in Central Louisiana, it was touted as a major economic haul for the region. Then, in 2016, the employees at that Call Center Operations facility were told that it was closing; and that employees who qualified would be offered a flexible work-from-home option (KALB, 2016). Whereas at the Alexandria location, management and the workforce transitioned

from a traditional 40,000 square foot 'brick and mortar' facility to a virtual work-from-home setting; other Sutherland Global locations have maintained the traditional office setting.

From a management theory viewpoint, Peter Drucker's task of measurement has become an issue for managers of the Sutherland Global combined virtual / traditional workforce. In a "recently filed class action lawsuit, Sutherland Global is accused of unlawfully withholding compensation from employees in violation of the federal Fair Labor Standards Act. In particular, workers in customer service agent positions (whether at-home or in brick-and-mortar offices) claim to have been denied compensation" (Turner, 2015). According to the July, 2008, U.S. Department of Labor's Wage and Hour Division, Fact Sheet #64, "call center agents, specialists, and representatives must be paid for 'principal activities' such as: starting the computer to download work instructions, booting up computer applications, shutting down a computer and other systems, and reading work-related emails" (Turner, 2015). Attorneys "are now interviewing additional Sutherland Global remote and on-site customer service agents across the country to determine if their rights were violated and if they recover unpaid wages as part of the class action" (Turner, 2015).

Case Study #3: Aetna

According to the Corporate Profile, Aetna was founded in 1853 in Hartford, Connecticut. The organization "is committed to providing individuals, employers, health care professionals, producers, and others with innovative benefits, products and services" (Aetna.com, n.d.).

Aetna's virtual work from home policy, in place for over 20 years, has had executive-level support. It is also a formal part of the organization's human resource policies and practices. Aetna's Director of Communication, Susan Millerick, stated that there is a strong process in place for identifying "which employees can telework successfully. The three main components include the actual job function (can the work be performed from home?), the individual's capabilities and competencies, and strict security standards for home offices" (Fell, 2015). An example of the success of the work-from-home practice is that Aetna's "claims teleworkers are 10 to 20 percent more productive than their in-office counterparts and produce comparable quality" (Humer, 2013).

Discussion Point:

However, due to recent trends in the United States healthcare market, Aetna announced a reduction in its workforce as well as revisions to its flexible work-from-home policy. Part of the market trends affecting workforce size is Aetna's withdrawal from 'Obamacare' in some states (HartfordBusiness.com, 2016). Of the "800 jobs that are no longer needed to support participation in state healthcare exchanges", approximately 400 have been relocated within the Aetna organization (HartfordBusiness.com, 2016).

Spokesman, Matt Clyburn, added that despite priding itself on being a leader in the telework world, 'Our goal is to figure out how we can work together in the best way. Any changes involve how we can innovate and work toward continued growth' (HartfordBusiness.com, 2016). Hence, the organization's managers who live within 50 miles of an office will be required to work in a traditional office setting within a year. In addition, over time, the 'rank and file' workers will be required to do the same (Lee, 2016). Thus, management and the workforce are transitioning from a mainly virtual work-from-home setting to a traditional 'brick and mortar' office.

From a management theory viewpoint, in 1924, Mary Parker Follett proposed that it is not where takes place but to focus on the science of getting people to cooperate. Today, whether the workplace is a virtual work-from-home setting or a traditional 'brick and mortar' office, the workforce is scattered. Wayne Turmel, co-founder of the Remote Leadership Institute, which helps managers deal with a scattered workforce, said many companies expanded working from home options for financial reasons; however, they don't adjust their remote work approach to balance remote work with collaboration (Lee, 2016).

A Human Resource Perspective

The millennials, also known as Generation Y born between the 1980s and 1990s, "now make up the major portion of the workforce" (Spector, 2017). According to Emily Noll, National Director of CBIZ Well-Being Solutions, millennials are "looking for things like flexible work arrangements and professional and personal development options" (Kohl, 2018). Furthermore, "in the current job market that favors talent", millennials "won't have a problem moving to a company" that offers flexibility; i.e. virtual work options (Spector, 2017). From a

human resource management viewpoint, the growing primary labor pool resource, millennials, often favor flexibility in work schedules over higher salaries (Spector, 2017). Essentially, Dr. Lillian Gilbreth's early 20th Century management theories on the human aspects of time continues to be a factor in today's hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization.

Recommendations for Future Research

One of the key issues around Taylor's Scientific Management Theory is to improve labor productivity. Particularly for managers used to observing work in process, tracking productivity electronically can be a challenge. Nevertheless, technologies can be used to identify gaps in productivity; thereby, contributing to the decision as to whether to revise or revoke the virtual part of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work option.

In order to track long term changes, Henry Fayol's theory of controlling, requiring establishing performance standards based on organizational objectives, measuring and reporting on actual performance, comparing results with performance and standards, and taking corrective and preventive measures, as needed; is applicable. For future research, a quantitative analysis might be considered. For instance, a quantitative analysis of financial data; i.e. sales per geographic region, marketing data, productivity, and cost effectiveness of productivity; may indicate problem areas. Then, a comparative analysis of that information with the before and after of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) work option may provide direction for future decisions to revise work policies.

Conclusion

Overall, management's responsibilities, to achieve defined objectives through the organization and coordination of the activities of a business, is being redefined by how, when, and where work is done. However, whether the organization ever fully developed the practices for a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce or decided to revise or revoke the policy is one of the contributing factors. That is, though changes to the hybrid work policy and practices do influence management; there are a number of other factors. As per the case studies, a contributing factor to management decisions is the force of a global market. Another factor is the challenges of managing a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce; i.e. communication, collaboration, and innovation. Adapting to evolving technology, particularly those that support

work-from-anywhere practices, is yet another. And, from a human resource management view, the work location / hours preferences of the growing primary labor pool, the millennials, can not be ignored. Remarkably, some of the case studies identified factors; i.e. changing consumer preferences, lack of innovation, that were in process for some time. In conclusion, whereas a change in hybrid work policies does affect management, a management decision to change where people work may not necessarily resolve the full range of underlying issues obstructing organizational objectives.

The Virtual Workforce: Adapting Human Resource Policies

Version April, 2013

Executive Summary

The increase in the number of virtual office workers is impacting many aspects of the workplace, including how and where work is being done; thereby, affecting human resource policies. Thus, the paper begins with identifying reasons to revise current policies for the virtual work environment. Then, based on the indication that change is needed, recommendations for revisions, solutions, and implementation are proposed.

A priority for the research is to provide [SCORE](#) with results that can be added to their knowledge base and training tools. For more than forty years, SCORE has been “dedicated to educating entrepreneurs and helping small businesses start, grow, and succeed nationwide.” “With over 13,000 volunteers nationwide, the organization has 364 chapters throughout the United States and its territories, and is a resource partner with the U.S. Small Business Administration (SBA).”

In order to achieve the objectives, an action research approach was used to “involve all stakeholders both in the questioning and sensemaking that informs the research, and in the action which is its focus” (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2). That is to say, the research invited an open discussion and included reviews of multiple sources of information to analyze the effect on existing policies; then to identify, create and implement the revisions. Tangible results include revised policies and procedures that meet the virtual office requirements and that also align with strategic and operational business objectives. Fundamentally, the goal of the research is to provide an action plan that can be implemented in a real world business environment.

Participants represented a range of experience in virtual work. Andy Green, a [SCORE – South Central Pennsylvania Chapter 33](#) volunteer with 30 years management experience in the manufacturing sector, provided leadership for the project. Though Andy has no actual experience in managing a virtual workforce, he agreed to become the mentor – and to carry out his duties in a virtual environment, i.e., Google docs, e-mail and text messages. Moreover, he

added to his mentoring responsibilities by contributing time and expertise in qualitative interviews, also completed virtually via e-mail messages and cell phone conversations.

Additional participants include interviewee, Stevie, who accepted her first virtual office position with a national company. At the time of her hire, there were no formal policies or procedures for a virtual workforce; therefore, she also agreed to become part of their pilot launch for development of the policies for the initiative. Then, although Vicky has no virtual work experience, her background in management parlayed to recognizing issues that may occur. I also contributed my experience whereby my virtual team developed, as often happens, without planning. Other interviewees, as presented in this paper, have a range of professional backgrounds with varying levels of experience in managing and / or working in virtual offices. Furthermore, input was queried from a variety of sources; such as, private sector companies and researchers who shared their results of their studies of virtual work.

In order to facilitate the discovery and understanding of the range of issues, the data collection and analysis phase of the research included open-ended qualitative interviews; quantitative research results; current news articles; comments from researchers; and literature reviews. A review of the data collection presented some positive aspects of virtual office work. For instance, the results of a 2010 report by The Anywhere Office team indicate a “27% increase in productivity” (Montero citing Lister, 2009, p. 5). However, negative aspects, such as communication issues, were a primary topic in the qualitative interviews.

Conversely, current headlines report that Yahoo! is cancelling their virtual work policy and requiring all employees to work from the home office. Best Buy is going to allow the virtual work policy to continue; however, employees will need to request management’s approval in advance. Does the Yahoo! and Best Buy’s change of policy mean that virtual office work is on the decline? According to quantitative statistics from leading corporations, the options for virtual office work are on the increase. If anything, these announcements are likely to affect the future development of human resource policies and procedures – including virtual office worker agreements – that specify the company’s rights to require workers to return to the traditional office.

Needless to say, the information acquired from the data collection and analysis identified an array of issues and venues to be addressed. Accordingly, there are three options for alternative solutions and a recommended, proposed solution provided, as follows.

This brief overview of the three alternative solutions is not listed in any order of priority:

Alternative #1: Recommend traditional office experience, followed by a pilot program with a progressive transition to virtual office work. Build policies and procedures during the pilot program. The benefits include that management can identify workers who are best suited for virtual office worker. A disadvantage is that the worker may not be able to commute or relocate to the home office location for the transition period.

Alternative #2: Combination of traditional office and virtual office work, with workers on a rotating schedule. Revise existing policies to accommodate the rotating schedule. The advantage of this alternative is that the rotating schedule can reduce the 'office politics'. The disadvantage is that the ideal candidate may not be able to relocate to the company's location.

Alternative #3: Telework centers and/or collaborative software. Revise existing policies. Establish requirements to include both the traditional and virtual office workers to attend collaborative meetings on a scheduled basis. While this option allows for the benefits derived from face-to-face communication as identified in the qualitative interviews, the downside is that some workers may be uncomfortable speaking to or being viewed from a 'camera'.

The next part provides a brief overview of the recommended, proposed solution, based on the research provided in this report:

Recommended, proposed solution: Taking into consideration the adverse results of ad-hoc practices, human resource managers / business owners /

corporate managers need to assess the workforce situation prior to implementation or intervene in cases where informal practices have already been adopted.

The proposed recommended solutions include revisions to human resource strategic and operational policies and procedures, i.e. job analysis and descriptions, communication procedures, training and performance appraisals. Preferably, the policies will be launched as part of a pilot program, whereby mismatches in the planning, policy revisions and actual virtual work environment might be discovered before company-wide implementation. Or, in situations where virtual work is not to be offered, then policies must explicitly state that fact and management must be aware of the restrictions. Ultimately, regardless of the decision, the policy needs to be applied in a uniform and consistent manner.

Thus, the selection of a solution is based on a variety of factors; therefore, understanding the benefits and costs of offering a virtual work option can help to determine the direction to take. From the business viewpoint, the option is offered for a variety of reasons, including recruitment and retention; and savings in real estate and overhead costs. From the workforce viewpoint, the advantage is in work – life balance. To illustrate, per quantitative studies, virtual workers save the time and money required for commutes and office lunches and wardrobes. Essentially, this advantage translates to a company benefit as well as workers are less likely to use sick days to take care of personal needs.

Nonetheless, human resources should not overlook the growth and development needs of the workforce. Certainly, efforts should be made to include the virtual worker in training programs, promotions, and meetings. In addition, teamwork should include a combination of the traditional and virtual workforce, when possible.

Ultimately, developing a virtual work option is an undertaking that can affect the organization. Likewise, potential roadblocks identify a key issue: the need for management training. According to Phil Montero, “managers often struggle when traditional ‘eyeball’ management or ‘management by walking around’ styles are no longer realistic.” Risk mitigation is discussed from its advantage when disaster strikes. In this case, the geographically dispersed

workforce can allow the work to be continued. The disadvantages, such as data security and equipment loss, require specific guidelines and agreements to mitigate the risks involved.

To summarize, in an effort to avoid or at least to mitigate problems, the endeavor should include partnerships with all stakeholders. The results should include revised policies and procedures that continually align business and human resource strategies and operations; thereby, providing guidelines for the transition to virtual office work – or a policy that clearly indicates that the option is not to be offered.

The Virtual Workforce: Adapting Human Resource Policies

Virtual offices are changing business strategic initiatives and operations – and presenting a challenge to human resource practices and policies that were initially developed for traditional office settings. For instance, past practices for performance appraisals relied on job analysis and descriptions, as based on the organization’s strategic objectives. As part of the performance appraisal, managers supervised the work being done, observed problem areas and then communicated those issues to the employee.

Alternatively, in virtual offices, managers no longer directly supervise the work and may not be aware of problems or changed roles. Likewise, employees are faced with responsibilities that are not clearly defined in their job descriptions, as well. Without human resource policies to address the virtual office, managers and employees have little or no direction or recourse. Generally, the business is faced with dealing with management procedures that are no longer applicable – and with employee needs that are not being met.

Inherently, SCORE, a national non-profit service providing dedicated volunteer mentors, workshops and tools to help small business owners achieve success, is a prime resource for providing leadership for the project and for distributing the results of the research to their clients. Hence, the overall purpose is to identify human resource policies and practices, not aligned with the virtual business world - and to present the results to SCORE to consider for an addition to their knowledge base.

Moreover, to facilitate the discovery and understanding of a range of issues, additional resources will be researched, as well. For instance, DEF Company, a national service firm

expanding into new markets, is increasing their staff of virtual office workers. Cindy, an employee of the Company, works from a virtual office. There is no nearby physical office; therefore, all of her work is completed via computer or cell phone. Cindy has experienced a number of challenges regarding the lack of overall direction. In comparison, the ABC Company is a small business that, among its services, develops business plans for clients. Owner / manager, Bruce has noticed that more of his clients are allowing employees to work from virtual offices; therefore, he is considering revising client business plans to include the management of a virtual workplace and workforce.

Furthermore, as a small business owner, I will contribute my experience in managing a virtual workforce. In our case, our business outgrew the office space very quickly. Since we were not ready to move into larger quarters, we decided to allow employees to work from home. Then, we hired a programmer from Hawaii, Peter, who had no plans to relocate and had a home office. Without much forethought, we had a virtual team of employees who required direction and leadership. Simply put, we were not prepared for the changes.

For Bruce's company, these issues translate to human resource policies that are not being included in business plans. For Cindy, the end result is increased frustration and tension with the home office. Then too, for businesses small to large, inaccurate procedures for developing job descriptions, result in conflicting job roles and responsibilities; thereby, negatively impacting productivity and profitability.

Thus, a critical area of this research will be determining the modified management and workforce requirements – and the impact on human resource policies. Another significant area will be developing the change management and training requirements needed to successfully implement the revised policies. In summary, the purpose is to define operational human resource practices not meeting the requirements of the virtual workplace; then develop new or revised policies and plans for implementation thereof. The long-term advantages include a work option that can serve, among other things, to enhance work / life balance. Alternatively, there are disadvantages to be discussed, as well.

Objective(s)

The objective of this paper is to review management and virtual office workforce requirements. Then, research options for adapting human resource policies, created for traditional workplaces, to meet the requirements of the virtual office workforce. A variety of human resource policies, ranging from job descriptions to performance appraisals, will be included to determine the extent of the issues. Though telecommuting is a growing worldwide phenomenon, the analysis will be limited to the business private sector within the United States.

The objective is not to produce an academic theory that is based on action, can be applied to an action or is about an action, as in traditional research (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2). As opposed to providing the typical theoretical solutions, an action research approach will be used to facilitate the development of realistic, practical applications for virtual office work for clients of the SCORE organization. To accommodate the variety of needs of the clients served by the SCORE organization, the basis for this paper will rely on the following definition: “Action research is only possible with, for and by persons and communities, ideally involving all stakeholders both in the questioning and sensemaking that informs the research, and in the action which is its focus” (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2).

To achieve the overall objective, the action research will be based on an active exchange of ideas with multiple stakeholders over the next several months to (1) recognize “the need for change”; (2) develop plans for the identified changes; (3) implement the changes and (4) sustain the change (Erwin, 2009, p. 28). Significantly, one of the benefits of the action research approach is that it relies on reflective conversation regarding everyday experiences that, in turn, encourages the development of new ideas. Certainly, with the array of experiences of the SCORE mentor, input from several businesses who have agreed to provide qualitative information, and the use of additional sources, such as Phil Montero of The Anywhere Office, the research has the foundation to evolve over time (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2).

Tangible results include revised policies and procedures that meet the virtual office requirements and that also aligns with strategic business objectives. The ultimate goal, to incorporate these changes into existing policies, will require change management and training.

Thus, a timeline for implementation and training will be developed to encourage the actual practice of the new or revised policies and procedures.

The methods for analysis will include surveys and qualitative interviews with stakeholders, i.e. virtual office workers, business owners and managers. The qualitative interviews will cover specific human resource topics; such as, planning and recruiting, training, retention, performance, and financial incentives; as well as encourage an open-ended dialog for any other related topics of discussion. Human resource metrics will be studied to analyze the turnover / retention / absentee rate of businesses that currently permit virtual office work. Moreover, comparative metrics reports will be developed to track productivity, employee retention and communication, before and after implementation of the revised policies. In addition, a cost / benefit analysis will identify the impact on profitability; i.e. do virtual offices really reduce business costs in rent, utilities, etc?

In addition, the “practical knowledge” gained through the action research will also contribute to “the increased well-being...of human persons and communities, and to a more equitable and sustainable relationship with the wider ecology of the planet....” (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2). To illustrate, the research will also recognize the economic impact of virtual offices on the community at large. In this case, the cost analysis will review the ecological efficiency of virtual offices, i.e. reduced commuting time that, in turn, contributes to the ecological welfare “of the planet” (p. 2).

The project will also rely on the skills gained from coursework completed as part of the Human Resources and Employment Relations Master’s Degree Program. The Seminar in Human Resources (HRER505) will be applied to the discussion of the strategic and operational practices. For instance, specific course related material such as developing “job content analysis, performance management and appraisal, and training and development” will be applied to determine the revisions to policies. Additionally, Organizations in the Workplace (HRER802) will provide a basis for understanding organizational and teamwork changes. Essentially, organizational structures and cultures and their relationship to the revisions being implemented will need to be reviewed as part of the development of the change management process and training program. Likewise, the skills gained in this course will identify negotiating skills that

will encourage the practice of the policies and procedures. From another viewpoint, the aforementioned cost analysis will rely on the course in Labor Market Analysis (HRER816) to apply “economic concepts to analyze a ‘real-world’ human resource issue,” i.e. the economics of virtual office work. (PSU Online Course Syllabus, HRER505, HRER802, and HRER816 Online Course Syllabi)

The overall objective is to create an action plan that will identify the business and workforce requirements – and human resource policies that require modification - as well as provide applicable solutions. The expectations are that the revised policies and procedures will align business and human resource strategies and operations; thereby, providing guidelines for the transition to virtual office work.

Problem Definition

For reasons ranging from employee work / life balance to business cost-efficiency and productivity, there is an increase of workers in virtual offices. “The driving forces, as related to reducing costs, increasing economical outcomes, the needs and preferences of workers...can be clustered into (a) societal forces including technology and (b) organizational and individual forces” (Andriessen & Vartiainen, 2006, p. 4).

While these driving forces represent reasons for the increase of workers in virtual offices, there are underlying business processes to be considered. For instance, from a human resource perspective, the independent role of virtual office workers tend to lead to more responsibility; therefore, the initial job analysis and description may be changed, albeit informally. Furthermore, salary and benefits may not match the actual work being performed.

For Bruce, the oversight may result in a mismatch of the job analysis with pay scales in the business plan; thereby, underestimating the projected income statement. For Cindy, the differences in actual work performed and initial job description are too readily apparent. Her responsibilities have increased – while her pay has not. Primarily, the independent setting of a virtual office means that Cindy is frequently left to make instant decisions; whereas, in the traditional office setting, she might have management to rely on. Ultimately, the SCORE mentors are in a prime position to provide direction and support to businesses that either already have a virtual workforce or those considering initiating one.

Conclusively, a decision to have a virtual office workforce can affect many areas; including human resource operations, organizational efficiencies, external stakeholders, as well as the personal lives of employees (Verbeke, et al, 2008, pp. 20-34). This research project will emphasize issues regarding human resource operations, with a goal of developing guidelines for key areas, such as job descriptions, performance appraisal, communication, and access to training / information.

The success of the research will be determined by several factors, including the feasibility of implementing the suggested changes; the actual practice of the revised policies; and the feedback from businesses, specifically SCORE.

Significance of Project

The increase of telecommuting and virtual offices is influencing many factors in the workplace, including human resource policies. “According to *World at Work Telework Trends*, the number of people working from home at least one day a month...grew from 9.5 million in 1999 to 17.2 million in 2008.” Depending on the research, the numbers do vary; however, “all point to one immutable fact: the workplace of the future is our home” (Wolfe, 2010). ([See Appendix A Facts and Figures](#))

Accordingly, companies are experiencing a change in how and where work is done, how people communicate and management procedures. On the other hand, human resource practices, policies and procedures may not have been revised to address the change. Essentially, the lapse has created financial, workforce and management issues. Notably, though not a primary objective of the research, the mismatch can also result in litigation. Thus, since “ad hoc arrangements are liable to leave companies open to legal liability for workmen’s compensation, and for potential violations of the Fair Labor Standards Act,” the importance of aligning human resource and business operational and strategic goals is further emphasized (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 2).

Ultimately, virtual office work has a positive impact on employee commitment and job satisfaction; as well as a negative impact on areas such as knowledge sharing. Regardless, the virtual office workforce is increasing; thereby, supporting the significance of this project in identifying human resource policies that no longer align with these business strategies.

Data Collection and Analysis

Before proceeding with the qualitative interview, quantitative survey data, and the literature review, it is practical to understand who is using virtual offices – and why? Telecommuting can be beneficial for the company for several reasons: employee attraction and retention, including situations where the candidate may not be willing to relocate to the company’s location; geographic diversification without the initial start-up expenses and overhead of multiple facilities; the related reduction in the cost of a “real estate portfolio”; “continuity planning” in that “a formal distributed work program dramatically lowers the risk of operational disruption;” and the benefits to the environment (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 3, 5, 6).

Who is using virtual offices? The following tables display some general data about companies with telecommuting programs and the increase in the number of workers who telecommute.

Business Demographics

Based on information provided by CNN Money, “100 Best Companies to Work For”, of the 82 Best Companies that allow employees to telecommute or work at home at least 20% of the time; the following 10 companies have the highest percentage of telecommuters. (Retrieved from <http://money.cnn.com/magazines/fortune/bestcompanies/2011/benefits/telecommuting.html>)

Companies	Rank of Best Companies	% of Regular Telecommuters
<i>Deloitte</i>	<i>63</i>	<i>86%</i>
<i>Cisco</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>85%</i>
<i>Intel</i>	<i>51</i>	<i>82%</i>
<i>Accenture</i>	<i>99</i>	<i>80%</i>
<i>Teach for America</i>	<i>82</i>	<i>80%</i>
<i>Pricewaterhouse Coopers</i>	<i>73</i>	<i>70%</i>
<i>Brocade Comm. Systems</i>	<i>89</i>	<i>50%</i>
<i>S. C. Johnson & Son</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>40%</i>
<i>Stryker</i>	<i>68</i>	<i>38%</i>
<i>American Fidelity Assurance</i>	<i>39</i>	<i>37%</i>

Workforce Demographics (,000)

The following chart from the June, 2011 report, titled *The State of Telework in the U.S.*, displays the results of the research for the virtual office 'work at home' workforce for years 2005-2009. Note that the 5 year growth is a substantial 61%. (Lister & Harnish 2011 p 8).

Qualitative Interviews

To learn a variety of viewpoints about virtual office work, qualitative interviews will be conducted as a first-person inquiry where I “engage in self-learning in action, learn to reflect, to engage in deep inquiry about...my own practices and assumptions”; and a second-person inquiry where I “engage multiple stakeholders in face-to-face conversation.” Subsequent third-person inquiry will be evident in the organizations and individuals who, after learning from the first- and second-person practice, put the information into action. (Coghlan, 2006, pp. 299- 300).

Participants

Participants included workers in a variety of positions and length of workforce experience. Likewise, their virtual work experience ranged from none or negligible to the more experienced.

Procedure

Interviews were completed via face-to-face, phone, or an online form of communication such as e-mail. Notably, excluding the face to face interviews, the latter two procedures contributed to the virtual work topic. Though the qualitative interviews began with some basic survey questions; open-ended discussions were encouraged whereby participants contributed their own experiences, viewpoints and recommendations. ([See Appendix B for Qualitative Interview Questionnaire](#))

Interviews: Employees

Stevie works for a national insurance company that is just beginning to allow virtual office work. In this case, if the company had not offered a virtual position, she would not have been able to accept the job offer. On the other hand, although the company had been planning to develop a virtual office workforce, they had no official policy or procedures in place. Then too, Stevie had never worked in a virtual office setting and had some concerns; however, she accepted the opportunity for several reasons; the main reason being for work / life balance.

Prior to starting to work as a virtual office employee, she was provided with onsite training at company headquarters. Stevie acknowledges that, in addition to the job training, the face-to-face meetings and onsite observations allowed her to view the team dynamics firsthand.

Currently, her job description requires processing life insurance applications for her assigned group. At times, there are miscommunications regarding the stage of processing of the application - as well as the location of the file and appended documents. Generally, Stevie's work is appraised with a qualitative approach; the measurement is based on the professionalism and knowledge of the employee. The amount of work processed is not measured quantitatively. Furthermore, Stevie's performance appraisals are very informal, conducted via phone with two supervisors, with no set pattern of information that is covered and no written feedback is received. However, she notes that she does receive her annual raise.

Although the company provided adequate training, they did not spend time working on a needs analysis for the office equipment and supplies. Therefore, Stevie received some equipment that was not setup with the programs or connectivity that she required. Likewise, as

time went on, she learned that her needs for some equipment differed from what she actually received. Nevertheless, she admits that the home office worked with her to correct the equipment situation – and that the human resource director was on the phone with her daily for an update.

Corporate headquarters also gave her permission to order whatever she needed from Staples; however, this too was not a well thought out process. In fact, the home office required the purchase of some office supplies that have never been used. For instance, the existing procedure in the home office required printouts of forms that are subsequently filed in hanging folders. We assumed that was so that other people in the office could readily view the information. However, Stevie, working in a virtual office, simply files her forms electronically, and then submits the link location to the appropriate personnel. Currently, in an effort to reduce the expense of print-outs, the home office is changing to an electronic file system – and following Stevie's process.

In order to maintain communication with the home office, Stevie and her team have a phone meeting every Monday. At first, Stevie admits that the lack of face-to-face contact did affect the conversation; however, after a period of time, everyone has adjusted. Moreover, Stevie noted that when everyone is sitting around a meeting table, there is more conversation that is not centered on the business. Alternatively, the phone meeting seems to decrease the 'chit chat' and moves right into discussing the topics in the meeting agenda. Overall, she feels that time is saved and issues are readily addressed in the virtual meetings.

Then again, communication does not always reach Stevie's virtual office. For instance, on one particularly nice Friday, the home office dismissed the staff at 3 p.m. Stevie was never advised of the early dismissal and continued to work. After repeated failed attempts to contact her co-workers at the home office by phone and by e-mail, she was able to reach a vice-president and was told about the early dismissal. Needless to say, a new procedure has been added whereby Stevie is now included in all communications.

On the other hand, this same insurance company lost the opportunity to hire a qualified candidate, Mary. In this case, though Mary was unemployed and not in a position to relocate, she was unwilling to try the virtual office position. Her main reasons were that the company had

no official policy in place and had no experience in working with a virtual team. Therefore, though the company assured her otherwise, she was concerned that if the venture failed, she would be out of a job. Currently, Mary has been hired at another company; albeit several years after rejecting the insurance company's offer.

The next interviewee, Cindy, found her job on the Internet. Because Cindy homeschooled her two young daughters, the virtual office work was a perfect fit for her schedule. In this case, she was told that the home office would supply her with the connectivity and program applications that would be needed to do the job; however, Cindy had to provide her own computer and phone. There was no specific job description for the virtual office; she simply had to schedule phone meetings with the companies specified by the home office and review their real estate information, i.e. the number of offices, the square footage, utility usage, etc. The information was to be entered into a preformatted online form. Additionally, she was told that the hours were flexible with no set time frame; an option that she was definitely looking for in a job. However, many of the client companies have traditional workday hours between 8 a.m. and 6 p.m.; therefore, the schedule is not as flexible as originally presented. Nevertheless, although there were some initial setbacks with contacting client companies and entering the information, Cindy has managed to find ways to successfully complete her tasks – and she enjoys working with the client companies, as well.

After Cindy finished sharing details about her job duties, the discussion turned to virtual office work, in general. She, too, has had some communications issues. At times, the company would call when her personal schedule was hectic, resulting in – as she said – some misunderstandings. Moreover, at the time she was hired, the company was fairly new at allowing employees to work virtually and had not considered any differences that might occur in completing the job. For instance, Cindy has had issues with client companies who are not able to complete all of the questions in one session; therefore, subsequent session(s) have to be scheduled. Thus, without a co-worker to rely on, Cindy has had to learn to balance the client company's schedule and her own schedule – in order to meet her employer's deadlines. To date, the home office has not developed any particular policies or procedures for a virtual office.

Instead, they feel that virtual office workers should simply do the job as if they were in a traditional office.

Interviews: Management

Regardless of their work position, the majority of interviewees mentioned that not meeting in person, at least at some point, had some negative aspects. For instance, I sent an e-mail message to Andy Green, a SCORE mentor with over 30 years experience in management in the manufacturing sector, to share his viewpoint on the following:

Research conversation / question: During our phone meeting, you mentioned that, for the most part, your management experience was based in the traditional 'brick and mortar' office - However, you also mentioned that, due to your SCORE caseload, you would probably (or maybe already have) incorporate more virtual type of management, Additionally, you and I have agreed to work as a virtual team on this project. How do you feel about the virtual team work? What are the advantages? What are the disadvantages?

Response from Andy Green: “I think that conferencing, with simultaneous visual and verbal contact, is better at reducing misunderstandings on the material at hand because an immediate conversation can take place. I still prefer in person, at least initially, because I can get a better read of the person, his/her communication style, attitude and drive through the unspoken body language.”

Andy Green then relates this comment to today’s workforce: “Coming from a different generation, I dislike the impersonalization of the virtual world but, interestingly enough, I see it emerging in a different way. Relationships with people are a human need that must be filled to grow. I see this occurring through interpersonal networking across businesses and industries more so than ever before. I see more depersonalization within companies as the ranks are thinned to cut costs and bosses are under considerable pressure. At one time, employees had very strong loyalties to their organization... much less so today.”

“As a manager, [Andy Green commented that he] would not want to go virtual unless the employee or contractor was proven capable of doing the work and working alone. At that point virtual is fine with mutually agreed outcomes, benchmarks and deadlines along with a communication plan to assure that projects are on their timeline. Virtual teams would be fine under the same conditions plus that they could work together... not all people can.”

The conversations with the next interviewee, Vicky, were conducted over several weeks. During that time frame, she not only modified her opinion about virtual office work but also provided some excellent insight into the issues that might have to be addressed. Primarily, Vicky works in a traditional brick and mortar office setting and manages a workforce of 200 +/- people. Vicky also has 4 administrative assistants. During the initial part of the conversation, she was skeptical as to the benefits of a virtual workforce. However, after discussion, she commented that she could see the benefits in having the administrative assistants rotate their time between working in the office and working from home. In this case, she identified the possibility of a decrease in office politics as a key benefit in that it would save her the time and effort that she expends in intervention.

Vicky also noted that [she could] “see how such arrangements will eliminate some jobs and increase others. The decrease in interaction among employees might increase productivity and decrease negative issues that come with people sitting in close quarters. On the other hand, some positions have already been eliminated by the computer. Therefore, the possibility of increase in productivity may serve to eliminate even more positions.”

In addition, based on a situation outside of her place of work, she discussed the possibility that virtual office workers may be overlooked for internal opportunities. In this case, an acquaintance was given permission, albeit informally, to work virtually. Since this was an ad hoc arrangement, there were no policies or procedures in place – from a management or human resource perspective. Subsequently, there was an opportunity to make a presentation at a company-wide event. However, the virtual worker was not even aware of the event – or the opportunity – until well after the fact. Furthermore, there were no clear guidelines in place that would have required that she receive communication thereof or given the opportunity to make

the presentation. Moreover, since her virtual work assignment fulfilled her work-life balance needs, she felt that she could not question the issue.

Interestingly, after Vicky understood more about the virtual office environment, she questioned some of the problems that might arise. In fact, her questions were very much 'on target' with the problems that have been identified in other research, current court cases, and in interviews for this paper. Additionally, she also asked about issues that need to be addressed within the virtual office worker's agreement. Moreover, Vicky questioned how Worker's Compensation laws would be applied. Then, too, she also asked about Occupational Safety and Health Act (OSHA) standards. In both cases, her concerns were based on experience in a traditional office setting whereby she noted that employees "came up with some pretty creative ideas when it came to collecting compensation."

In comparison to Vicky, I have extensive experience working in a virtual office and in managing a virtual team. In my case, after hiring Peter from Hawaii and David in Florida, the virtual team evolved 'on its own'. Similar to some of the companies that I have researched for this project, we also had no policies or procedures in place. Likewise, communications became a key issue; therefore, we developed a meeting plan whereby local employees would meet in the office – and David and Peter would join us via phone. Accommodating Peter's time difference was hectic, at first. Though the first few meetings were a little awkward, eventually we all became used to the combination of communicating virtually and face-to-face. Although David and Peter's faraway location might seem to have been part of the issue; the fact is that, after we hired a local programmer who wanted to work virtually, we had similar problems in communication.

On another note, management may not be aware of work and responsibilities that may have changed in the virtual office. Therefore, recognizing an employee's contributions or problems with completing the work has an added challenge. To illustrate, on the recommendation of an acquaintance, I hired a local applicant who had successfully completed a 1 year computer programming certificate at xxx. While I had heard of the school, I was not familiar with their programs; however, after discussing our projects with the applicant, I felt that he could do the job. Subsequently, I hired him and he was assigned to a fairly simple

programming project. I contacted him during the first week for updates. Though he had some questions, I thought that everything was going alright. After about 3 weeks, he was clearly frustrated. I asked to meet with him personally. During that meeting, I learned that the training that he had received was nothing more than online modules that led the student through the process. At no time was he asked to apply the theory that he had learned to an actual problem. Unfortunately, he chose to quit the job and return to his previous work as a warehouse manager.

Needless to say, policies and procedures for communication, deadlines, task assignments and a myriad of other issues eventually had to be addressed. Nowadays, I prefer to develop and update policies and procedures, including those for hiring, before allowing the employee to work from a virtual office.

Quantitative Surveys

In addition to the qualitative interviews, quantitative survey information will be included to provide measurable data for the action plan. Significantly, quantitative surveys conducted by the World at Work organization found that “the majority of [their] respondents seem to be positioning their flexible/distributed work programs as part of a key talent acquisition and retention strategy.” Therefore, including the survey data is an important area of the action research as it contributes to the identification of key human resource procedures that should be adapted to the virtual office requirements, i.e. hiring and retention (Grantham et al, 2009, p. 15).

Overall, virtual office work has benefits for the employee, the company – and for the environment. Needless to say, for companies, the current economic climate and globalization requires a reduction in the “cost of operations”, the ability to “attract and retain key talent”, and a corporate culture that encourages innovation to maintain the competitive edge. Research results indicate that a virtual work policy does help to achieve the company goals through reduced turnover rates; and increased productivity and employee commitment (Grantham et al, 2009, p. 9).

To illustrate, according to a WorldatWork report titled, *Flexible Work Arrangements for Nonexempt Employees*, virtual worker productivity increased “by an average of 7%”; and turnover and related costs are “reduced by 4.8%”. Moreover, virtual workers are more likely to “be engaged in their jobs and committed to helping their organizations succeed” (Grantham et al,

2009, p. 9). In addition, the results of a 2010 report by The Anywhere Office team indicate a “27% increase in productivity” and a “25% reduction in attrition.” The “*Telework Survey at Cisco Systems*” results also reported improvements for the company as productivity increased by 69% and a 75% improvement in meeting deadlines (Montero citing Lister, 2009, p. 5).

For employees, the benefits include savings in time and money. Primarily, with the rising cost of gasoline and the growing awareness of the impact on the environment, commuting time and costs are becoming significant discussion points in the recruiting process. For instance, the savings in transportation and work-related costs range from “\$1,800 to \$6,800”. Accordingly, the virtual office worker gains the equivalent of “2-3 weeks of vacation time per year” (Montero citing Lister, 2009, p. 5). As a result, work – life balance, an important topic in recruiting and retention, also improves. Moreover, the flexible hours gives the employee an opportunity to attend to personal needs – without taking vacation time or sick days; therefore, virtual office “employee absenteeism is decreased by 60%” (p. 4).

Though virtual office work is on the increase, the development of supporting human resource policies and procedures is deficient in some critical areas. Basically, the problem is “that most organizations don’t plan” to begin a virtual office work policy – it just happens as a result of need. For instance, 44% of companies researched do not have a “formal process in place for determining which employees should be – or should not be – working from a virtual office.” And, employees are provided with technology that may not help them to do their jobs; and tools that may not even be necessary. According to WorldatWork, “44% [of the companies surveyed] did not evaluate technology effectiveness.” In fact, as a result of this pre- and post-survey information, companies reinforced the development of “planning, comprehensive policy development, training, and evaluation systems based on performance measurement” (Grantham et al, 2009, p. 5).

Literature Review

. A variety of human resource policies, ranging from job descriptions to performance appraisals, have been identified; thereby, serving as indicators to the extent of the issues. To

widen the scope of understanding, a literature review, including several books, Web sites, and professional non-juried articles, was completed as part of the research process.

First, the book, titled *Growing the Virtual Workplace*, reviewed the impact, tracking, implementation and adoption of virtual work from the perspectives of employees, organizations and society. The authors refer to the “use of these constructs and stakeholders” as the EOS framework: “employees, organizations and societal decision-makers.” (Verbeke 2008 Summary p x) Their application of this framework aligns with the definition of action research applied to this research paper: “Action research is only possible with, for and by persons and communities, ideally involving all stakeholders both in the questioning and sensemaking that informs the research, and in the action which is its focus” (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2).

Essentially, the book was a resource for additional information for the employee and organizational issues presented in the qualitative interviews. For instance, Chapter 3, *Telework Impacts: The Organizational Perspective* identifies strategic and operational human resource issues. The chapter was critical in supporting the qualitative interview information; such as, recruiting, retention, knowledge sharing (communication), and absenteeism. In addition, the authors provide the results of their own surveys. The data categories of those surveys were helpful in directing the research in this paper.

Then, *Implementing and Managing Telework* explores virtual work from many viewpoints; including human resources, organizational requirements, and security issues. With regards to security, the authors devote an entire Chapter 7 to “Preparing for Disaster” and the ever-present need for continuity planning. In this chapter, the authors refer to the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake in the San Francisco Bay area and the 9/11 attacks on the New York City World Trade Center and the Pentagon, as being the main reason promoting virtual office work in those regions. And, for employers developing a human resource policy for a virtual workforce, the appendices provide templates for evaluations, virtual office worker / employer agreements, and follow-up surveys.

The creators of the Web site ‘youcanworkfromanywhere.com’ devote time and effort to researching issues regarding the virtual workplaces. Several of their reports and e-mail updates were used as guidelines for this research, including *Work Unchained: Workshifting and the*

Competitive Edge of The Anywhere Office. Accordingly, one of the objectives for this research was in identifying whether there was a need for change in management requirements and procedures. Phil Montero, founder of YouCanWorkFromAnywhere.com, provided this insight: “One of the key elements of highly successful virtual teamwork is a shift in management or leadership perspective about where, when, and how work gets done. Managers often struggle when traditional ‘eyeball’ management or ‘management by walking around’ styles are no longer realistic.”

Reflective Comment: Data Collection and Analysis

Generally, the results were surprising in that the recommendations for addressing the issues came from all participants - including those with little or no experience in a virtual office. In this case, it appears that their overall professional experience gave the ‘little or no experience’ participant insight as to the problems that might occur. Moreover, the problems that were identified would feasibly impact many areas of the organization, including human resource policies and procedures.

Alternatively, the interviewees also asked many questions. Basically, they questioned what I had learned about how ‘other’ companies might be handling the transition to virtual office work. In this case, based on interviews, literature and research reviews, I was able to add insight to the conversation.

Relating the Data Analysis to the Action Research Plan

As stated previously, the objective of this paper is to review management and virtual office workforce requirements. Fundamentally, the goal of the research is not to prove or disprove theories but to provide an action plan that can be implemented in a real world business environment.

In order to achieve this objective, quantitative data, qualitative interviews and literature reviews were used to identify, first, if human resource policies need to be revised. After identifying that there were reasons for revisions, the research proceeded to identify specific policies and procedures that did not meet the needs of the virtual office workforce and management thereof.

First, communication issues were identified in all of the research. In this case, missed or misinterpreted communication caused problems for the virtual worker and hindered the workflow. Then, based on quantitative data, recruiting, retention and turnover are human resource issues that can be eased with a virtual office option. Alternatively, one of the applicants recruited for a virtual office assignment did not accept it due to the lack of policies and management experience. Performance analysis appears to be a weak link in that research indicates that management continues to review an employee's performance as based on traditional office work. Incentives and recognition are another area where management practices need to be revised. In addition, need for training and change management procedures need to be developed and implemented.

Solutions

In amongst the success stories, there are failures. Generally, the failures point to issues such as management requirements that are not clearly defined; lack of planning for hiring and selecting personnel suited for virtual work; training; performance appraisals that are not modified for the virtual office environment; financial expenditures for work at home equipment and supplies; miscommunication; among others. ([See Appendix C: Virtual Employee Training Chart](#) and [Appendix D: Training Management for Virtual Workforce Chart](#))

Primarily, in order to create a successful program, the development of human resource policies begins with “an understanding as to why [virtual work] is being considered” (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 204). Then, “best practices” include that “the program is formal, explicit and sponsored by senior management;” recognize that “going mobile means changes to the way that work is done and how it is measured and rewarded; training is provided for managers and virtual office workers; and there is an effective use of collaboration technology” (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 7).

Essentially, best practices promote planning for a myriad of issues. Nevertheless, many virtual office work practices are created informally or in an ad hoc manner. Therefore, as identified in the introduction section of this paper: a critical area of this research will be determining the virtual office management and workforce requirements – and the impact on

human resource policies. Another significant area will be developing the change management and training requirements needed to successfully implement the revised policies.

Conclusively, the following sections present an overview of alternative solutions for virtual office work and proposed recommended solutions for strategic and operational human resource policies and procedures, as based on the interviews and the research in this paper.

Alternative Solutions

Alternative Solution #1: Recommend traditional office experience, followed by a pilot program with a progressive transition to virtual office work. Build policies and procedures during the pilot program.

The initial decision to allow an employee to work virtually is dependent on several factors, including the ability of the worker to do the job and to meet deadlines and goals without direct supervision. Accordingly, interviewee Andy Green emphasized “that he would not want to go virtual unless the employee or contractor was proven capable of doing the work and working alone. At that point virtual is fine with mutually agreed outcomes, benchmarks and deadlines along with a communication plan to assure that projects are on their timeline.” Then again, the quantitative data in this report indicates that “44% of workers do not have a formal process in place for selecting individuals for virtual work.” Therefore, an alternative solution is that, in addition to a formal interview, the selection process also requires that the candidate has applicable traditional office experience, first; thereby, assuring that they can meet their deadlines. After that point, during a pilot program, a progressive transition to virtual work can be made either to either full-time or part-time, depending on the company’s goals.

Alternative Solution #2: Combination of traditional office and virtual office work, with workers on a rotating schedule. Revise existing policies to accommodate the rotating schedule.

A combination of traditional office and virtual office work may decrease adverse interpersonal dynamics and increase productivity; while also giving employees the option to work virtually. Interviewee Vicky commented that she could see the benefits in having her 4

administrative assistants rotate their time between working in the office and working from home. She identified a key benefit in that the office politics would decrease; thereby, saving her the time and effort that she expends in intervention.

Alternative Solution #3: Telework centers and/or collaborative software. Revise existing policies. Establish requirements to include both the traditional and virtual office workers to attend collaborative meetings on a scheduled basis.

Essentially, one of the benefits for offering a virtual office policy is that qualified applicants are not faced with either relocating to the company's location or declining the position. In Stevie's interview for this research, she stated that, if she would have been required to relocate, she would not have been able to accept the job offer. Yet, she also mentioned that she gained personal knowledge regarding team dynamics during her onsite training at corporate headquarters. As presented in the literature review, a Telework center that allows the workers to schedule a 'face to face meeting' might be an option. For example, if the company headquarters are located in the northeast section of the United States and the virtual work staff is geographically located in other regions, then Telework centers might be an option that offers the similarly situated regional workers time to meet without the need for relocation or extensive, overnight travel. In this case, the Telework center would serve to reduce the company's real estate portfolio while also giving the worker the opportunity to work together (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 109). An alternative solution to the Telework center is online collaborative software that allows face-to-face communication over the Web with many of the same benefits.

Decision Matrix: Weighting Alternative Solutions with Human Resource Requirements

The decision matrix integrates the information from the qualitative interviews, quantitative data and literature reviews presented in this paper. Fundamentally, it has been developed to provide some direction in the decision-making process for the implementation of an alternative solution. Moreover, the objective of this research is to identify practices that need to be modified to accommodate the implementation; therefore, the criteria are weighted per human

resource policies and procedures, i.e. workforce interest, cost /benefit, ease of implementation, obstacles and, in order to benefit from the experiences of other companies, research based success rates.

Primarily, without workforce interest, there is either no need for implementation – or implementation will likely be challenged on all fronts – therefore, it has been assigned the highest weight. In this decision matrix, the workforce interest includes all employees in the organization. Notably, some researchers have identified that management is less likely to support a virtual work option.

Then, the lowest ranking criterion is research-based success rates. This low ranking is due to the fact that researchers have noted that there are many variables to be considered in a quantitative survey of the implementation of virtual office workers; therefore, the results may differ per organizations.

The highest ranking alternative solution, Collaborative Online Meeting Requirements, does align with the majority of qualitative interviewee comments regarding communication. For instance, the virtual office workers, Stevie and Cindy, both identified problems that resulted from communication. Management interviewees also recognized communication issues. Interviewee and project mentor, Andy Green, stated that, though he still prefers in person meetings at least initially, “conferencing, with simultaneous visual and verbal contact, is better at reducing misunderstandings on the material at hand because an immediate conversation can take place.”

In summary, the three alternative solutions that enhance and encourage communication – Collaborative Online Meeting Requirements, Part-time Virtual Office and Part-time Traditional Office Work, and Optional Use of Local Telework Centers – also have the highest ranking. The alternative solution for Full-Time Virtual Office Work after Receiving Training has the lowest rank. This too aligns with the research in that without team support, interaction and communication, the full-time virtual office worker is likely to be excluded from opportunities for training and recognition. Thus, the outcome is a worker who is not fully engaged. Furthermore, whereas a primary point for providing the virtual work option is to enhance work / life balance, research indicates that the option without the support and engagement is likely to increase turnover rates.

Rating	Priority
1	High Priority
2	Medium
3	Low

Virtual Office Policy: Alternative Solutions

	Weight	Full-Time Virtual Office After Onsite Experience, Training and Assessment	Rating	Part-Time Virtual Office / Part-time Traditional Office	Rating	Collaborative Online Meeting Requirements	Rating	Optional Use of Local Telework Centers	Rating
Workforce Interest	0.50	1	0.50	1	0.50	1	0.50	1	0.50
Cost Benefit	0.25	1	0.25	2	0.50	3	0.75	1	0.25
Ease of Implementation	0.10	1	0.10	1	0.10	1	0.10	3	0.30
Obstacles	0.10	2	0.20	3	0.30	2	0.20	3	0.30
Research-based Success Rates	0.05	3	0.15	3	0.15	3	0.15	3	0.15
	1.00		1.20		1.55		1.70		1.50

Summary Table: Advantages and Disadvantages of Alternative Solutions

The following table represents a sample of the advantages and disadvantages for each of the alternative solutions, based on the information and interviews researched for this paper.

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Full-Time Virtual Office After Onsite Experience, Training and Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employee or contractor has proven capable of doing the work and working alone 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential candidate may be unwilling to relocate for extensive training period
Part-Time Virtual Office / Part-time Traditional Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows for management to review work being done Has the potential to decrease 'office politics'; thereby, increasing productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Would not be acceptable to a candidate who is unwilling to relocate

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Collaborative Online Meeting Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Encourages communication and development of relationships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● People may be uncomfortable with the technology or with meeting online
Optional Use of Local Telework Centers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Decreases the feeling of isolation that some virtual office workers develop ● Increases the potential for communication and development of relationships with workers from employer as well as from other employers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The success rate of Telework centers is low ● Might not be an option for virtual workers in remote locations

Proposed Recommended Solutions

Whether the employees will work from their virtual office on a full-time or part-time basis or utilize collaborative software or a Telework center is a decision that must align with the corporate goals and objectives. Therefore, during the planning stages, viewpoints from a variety of internal and external stakeholders – from top management to the workforce – should be included. In the process, goals need to be assessed, policies revised, and strategies for implementation should be developed.

However, current research indicates that virtual work is frequently instituted in an ad hoc manner; with little or no corporate-wide planning and development. Though the decision to allow an employee to work virtually may be based on the good intentions, the ad hoc approach could lead to discontent among the workforce; thereby, increasing turnover. In addition, the lack of planning can result in labor law litigation; such as the Fair Labor Standards Act. Moreover, tax laws require that taxes are based on the employee’s virtual office location. Without official recognition of the virtual office policy, the tax assessment might be overlooked.

Taking into consideration the adverse results of informal practices, human resource managers, as strategic and operational partners of the business, need to assess the situation prior to implementation. In cases where virtual office work is already in place without the benefit of policies and procedures, human resources should intervene with valid issues sustaining the need for explicit guidelines.

Essentially, the proposed recommended solutions is to revise human resource strategic and operational policies and procedures, i.e. job analysis and descriptions, communication procedures, training and performance appraisals, prior to offering virtual office positions. Preferably, the policies will be launched as part of a pilot program, whereby mismatches in the planning, policies and actual virtual work environment might be discovered before company-wide implementation.

To illustrate, revising job analysis and descriptions prior to offering a virtual assignment is prudent from a business and legal viewpoint. In this case, companies can avoid “discrimination charges of ‘favoritism’ when offering” positions with the development and consistent practice of a formal selection process for virtual office assignments (Fenson & Hill, 2003, pp. 71-2). Notably, one of the qualitative interviews in this report identified that the company missed the opportunity to hire a qualified applicant because there was no formal policy or management experience dealing with virtual office workers.

Additionally, during the revision to job descriptions, recognize that the way that the work is done may impact other areas. To illustrate, during Stevie’s interview, she mentioned that she is frequently asked how she manages to get so much work done. Needless to say, she creates a bottleneck of activity for the next step in the application process that is completed in the traditional office environment. In summary, the virtual office allows workers to work during early morning or late night hours, utilize the time that they may have spent commuting, and to work uninterrupted by other employees. As a result, productivity increases and, therefore, the workers in the next step in the operations may have to adjust their schedule accordingly (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 24).

A related point is that all stakeholders need to understand that virtual office does not imply that the worker is available whenever needed. Then too, virtual workers need to learn to

‘disconnect’ from work. Though flexibility is an attractive option, an orientation and pilot program will help to define required hours of operations and compliance with deadlines from all viewpoints.

Likewise, metrics reports should be revised to reflect the virtual office performance and productivity. For instance, a report that compares the productivity of a traditional office worker to a virtual office worker may have to account for extraneous variables; such as those that might affect time to task completion status. Additionally, if the virtual office program was launched to attract and retain qualified candidates, then a metrics report should show a comparative hiring and retention rate.

Moreover, the performance analysis needs to be adapted. As depicted in the qualitative interviews, virtual office workers can be overlooked. The workers may feel that their performance is not being fairly assessed. Furthermore, they may also feel that they are not receiving the same level of feedback from management as compared to the on-site employees; thereby, affecting their work. The text titled “Growing the Virtual Workplace” suggests that “managers and employees work together to define performance goals and provide regular feedback to each other.” In any case, both should be encouraged to provide feedback at any time. The performance analysis should also discuss “the employee’s performance both as a worker and as a virtual office worker” (Verbeke et al, 2008, p. 24).

In addition, though employees may not be working together in the same physical location, the qualitative interview with Andy Green emphasizes that relationships with people is a human need that must be filled to grow. Basically, in the changing work environment, he sees that interpersonal relationships are emerging through networks across businesses and industries; albeit with different methods and results. Accordingly, policies and practice need to reflect that relationships are needed for growth. For instance, policies can enforce that teams include a combination of traditional and virtual office workers, when possible; and that virtual workers are included in career development, appraisal schemes and training opportunities. Hence, virtual workers will be given the opportunity to meet their basic needs for work-life balance as well as develop professional goals. Moreover, they will build their “confidence, achievement and

self-esteem” toward achievement of Maslow’s highest level of “self-actualization” as their “creativity and problem solving skills” develop in a collaborative team environment.

Alternatively, because of the separate workplaces and the use of technology, communication may be ignored or reduced. Interviewee, Stevie, experienced miscommunication when she was not advised of the early Friday quit time. On the other hand, the separate quarters and use of communication technology; such as e-mail, can have its benefits as “interactions with individuals considered difficult, unpleasant or ineffective can be reduced in number and scope; thereby, eliminating the resulting stress or emotional upset.” This point was presented during the interview with Vicky who recognized that rotating her administrative assistants on a virtual office schedule would reduce their stress – as well as her own in having to deal with the situation (Verbeke et al, 2008, p. 24).

Preparing the workforce is a key factor; likewise, updating human resource procedures for management is essential to providing leadership and direction – for both traditional and virtual office workers during the transition. Notably, for managers, “there are challenges; such as, determining performance standards and metrics, and accountability issues.” “Other challenges are more specific to and prevalent in the virtual context, such as problems with technology” (Verbeke et al, 2008, p. 162). Accordingly, the research of B.J. Avolio, S. Kahai, R. Dum Dum and N. Sivasubramaniam indicates that this leadership is “a social influence process mediated by advanced information technologies to produce changes in attitudes, feelings, thinking, behaviour, and/or performance of individuals, groups and/or organizations” (Aviolo et al 2000 p 617 as cited in Verbeke, 2008, p 163).

Conclusively, human resources should be viewing the corporate culture as well as the revisions for management and workforce policies and procedures for the implementation of virtual office work – and making plans for adapting those policies, as needed. Certainly, this action research approach allowed for the exchange of dialog among multiple stakeholders; thereby, encouraging the development of a feasible approach to the issue. Moreover, the interactive dialog can work toward the development of relations that will serve to sustain the implementation and practice thereof.

Benefits and Costs

Business / Workforce Benefits and Costs

Based on the research conducted for this paper, the prime benefit for employees appears to be work / life balance. (See [Appendix E: Work / Life Balance: Travel / Commute Time and Expense](#)) On the other hand, there are related costs in that some of the interviewees expressed concerns about being able to ‘disconnect’ from their jobs. Others have identified the ‘relative costs to their careers’ due to missed communication and being overlooked for special assignments or promotions.

However, not all employees are ‘suited’ for virtual work. One of the qualitative interviewees, Andy, commented, “I’m suggesting the virtual work office is a partial alternative for some people who are good time managers and are at a ‘needs’ level where this is a match. If the person’s style requires more socialization, virtual office may not be effective. If they are loners, maybe it will. I suspect a blend makes the most sense if the person can be effective when alone.”

From a business perspective, the decrease in the real estate portfolio can ease some of the company’s financial burdens. For instance, between 2007 and 2010 SCAN Health “reduced the corporate real estate portfolio by as much as 40% - 50% by offering employees an opportunity to work from home full- or part-time in return for giving up an assigned private workspace in the corporate facility. Consolidating the real estate portfolio enabled greater density in the re-designed space;” thereby, “eliminating private offices, concentrating storage space, and providing standardized ‘neighborhood’-based work areas” (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 5). (See [Appendix F: Suggested Real Estate Calculations](#))

Nonetheless, the benefits derived from the implementation can quickly be lost due to a lack of planning for policies and procedures. To illustrate, though employee turnover is reduced when virtual office options are provided, a lack of planning can actually increase costs for several reasons. For one, an employee who is not offered the option may become disgruntled and leave; or may report a violation of the Fair Labor Standards Act or the Equal Employment Opportunity Commission. In any case, turnover and litigation do represent a cost to the company as well as to the workforce.

Then again, what happens when a company needs a complete reorganization of strategic and operational goals? Apparently, Yahoo!'s CEO believes that traditional office work is necessary for the business to recover its niche. Reportedly, CEO Marissa Mayer's memo stated "To become the absolute best place to work, communication and collaboration will be important, so we need to be working side-by-side. That is why it is critical that we are all present in our offices" (Pepitone, 2013).

Conversely, Yahoo! might be taking a chance that the announcement may result in a turnover of their experienced work staff, at a critical time when the company needs their expertise. In essence, because of the level of technology required by the Yahoo! jobs, the workforce is highly skilled. Even with currently high unemployment rates, a skilled worker in the area of technology can find another job.

Then too, many of the Yahoo! employees do not work in the immediate area; therefore, the announcement will require a transfer to the home office location. What about the employees' families? For some, the reason for working from a virtual office was for work / life balance. In addition, from an economic viewpoint, the real estate market has not fully recovered; therefore, for the employees who are also homeowners, selling their home and relocating might become a challenge.

On another note, one of the interviewees in this paper, Vicky, replied with the following comment:

"I was really annoyed at hearing that Yahoo's CEO was given public attention for returning to work 2 weeks after delivering. What none of us knew, until now, was that she built a nursery next to her office. She didn't have to go through the emotional trauma of leaving a newborn like most of us have had to experience. Who does that? I feel [the change to the virtual work policy] is a rather callous move, and most likely an underhanded move to save money. Also, if [the virtual office workers] quit, will they qualify for unemployment? Would this be any area of clarification when one is hired for a virtual position?"

Similarly, Best Buy has made an announcement affecting the virtual work policy. In opposition to Yahoo!, the virtual office work option will continue to be allowed; though, workers

will need management pre-approval. Comparable to Yahoo!, Best Buy is also experiencing problems and has “brought in a new CEO” (Pepitone, 2013).

Does the Yahoo! and Best Buy’s change of policy mean that virtual office work is on the decline? According to quantitative statistics from leading corporations, the options for virtual office work are on the increase. If anything, these announcements are likely to affect the future development of human resource policies and procedures – including virtual office worker agreements – that specify the company’s rights to require workers to return to the traditional office.

Corporate Responsibility: Ecological Benefits and Costs

Accordingly, the costs and benefits from an ecological viewpoint are important as the research regarding the impact of virtual work on the environment supports a company’s decision to offer the option. In fact, “the largest ecological footprint, especially the carbon footprint, for many organizations derives from workers commuting to work.” And, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) officially lists worker commutes “as a scope 3 greenhouse gas emission.” (See e.g. [Greenhouse Gas Protocol](#)) Hence, “with all these social benefits of telecommuting, Yahoo! and other like-minded organizations need to carefully think about setting thoughtful, socially responsible corporate practices” (Sarkis, 2013). From the human resource viewpoint, the initiative would require updates to existing policies, procedures and practices. Likewise, the pre-planning should include a partnership with the finance department to discover tax benefits for the company.

Workforce Benefits and Costs: Another Perspective

For the most part, this research has identified workforce benefits for family members who must also provide caregiving for children and family members. However, the article titled “Simplify Your Life: Telecommuting Isn’t Just for Parents” asks “Why shouldn’t all of us, whether we parent children or not, have access to civilized ways of working that simplify our lives, decrease our commutes, allow us to be more efficient and maintain our sanity at the same time?” Accordingly, the author identifies work-related costs that affect everyone – from the dry cleaning bills for the required office wardrobe to the expense of commuting and mid-workday lunches (Jenkins, 2013).

Moreover, “Shirley Davis-Sheppard, the Society for Human Resources Management’s vice-president of Global Diversity & Inclusion” advises that “employees shouldn’t have to tell the organization the reason for wanting to work virtually.” In fact, “[SHRM’s Global Diversity & Inclusion division] “advocates that companies should be managing by results, not ‘butts in seats’.”

Ms. Davis-Sheppard, “who is also the co-leader of the Society for Human Resources Management’s Workplace Flexibility initiative and holds a doctorate in business and organization management”, goes on to say “That’s what inclusion is all about...[organizations] are not going to be able to engage and retain great talent without having flexibility. “ Furthermore, Davis-Sheppard advises that “this is not just about telecommuting. It’s about compressed workweeks, part-time job options, flexible schedules and job sharing.”

Policy Revision Implementation Plan

Policy Creation

The information presented in this paper indicates the need for revised human resource policies for the virtual workforce. Minimally, issues that will need to be acknowledged include “applications, assessments, guidelines, policies, surveys and home office evaluations.” Additionally, human resource managers would do well to keep abreast of changes to the laws (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 259).

Due to the overall impact on the organization’s structure, operations and strategic initiatives, the input from a variety of stakeholders – both from within the workforce and from additional resources – will be needed. Given the array of information and participants, technology is a good source to encourage participation as well as to allow for automated processes to analyze and compile their input. In this case, if the company’s technology is not set up to support the functions needed; a number of Internet providers do provide services to accommodate online forms, surveys, etc. In addition, collaborative software that allows for online meetings, chat rooms, and Webinars can facilitate the disbursement of information as well as encourage conversation thereof. Furthermore, round table discussions, scheduled during the workday, will provide a venue for face-to-face communication.

Essentially, relying on the experience of company's who have already implemented a virtual work policy can help to shed some light on what to include. In addition, there are examples available online and in texts for Virtual Office policies and agreements.

Potential Roadblocks

As mentioned in Stevie's interview, the issue with the technology and equipment expense was due to the fact that a needs analysis had not been completed. If the home office had done so, they would have realized that her connection requirements would differ. As a result, Stevie had to work with the home office to get her hardware and applications operating. In this case, the connectivity issue cost time and money – and could have caused a real problem for a virtual worker who was not as technically savvy as Stevie.

In addition, change management is essential to preparing the entire workforce, including managers. Based on the research, there are several key areas for revisions to human resource policies and procedures. For one, since the virtual worker is not on site, the performance appraisal will need to be based on something other than management's observation of the work completed. In some cases, work, such as data entry on forms, can be measured by the amount completed. However, in other cases, the work is more qualitative, such as the amount of time troubleshooting problems for clients.

Likewise, management practices will need to be changed. For some managers, supervising translates to being able to see the employee doing the work. In fact, several researchers, including Phil Montero of founder of YouCanWorkFromAnywhere.com, provided this insight: "Managers often struggle when traditional 'eyeball' management or 'management by walking around' styles are no longer realistic."

To summarize, "new processes for controlling, measuring, and evaluating will be needed, as not all of the systems used in the traditional office apply virtually." In essence, human resource managers, as an operational and strategic partner, are in a position to identify revisions needed for policies, such as job descriptions, metric reports and performance appraisals (Helms & Raiszadeh, 2002, as cited in Verbeke et al, 2008, p. 44).

Risk Mitigation

Essentially, virtual offices provide the company with a ‘built in’ risk mitigation plan. From “natural to man-made disasters”, the work in virtual offices can continue. Moreover, since “employee benefits include continuity in employee work, and in some cases their earnings”, the “operational continuity” benefits the organization as well as the employees (Verbeke et al, 2008, pp. 28-9).

In addition, the risk in not allowing virtual office work is that the company may not hire the most qualified candidate. For instance, one of the interviewees, Stevie, could not have accepted the position if she was required to relocate. More importantly, Stevie has the expertise and experience that her company was looking for. Therefore, by allowing her to work virtually, the company gained an employee who is most qualified for the job.

Alternatively, there are risks in allowing virtual office work. For instance, security issues may arise with the use of the company’s intranet and company data. As a result, the organization has to develop and implement another layer of security, policies and procedures. On the other hand, the “measures may negatively affect the employee’s view of virtual work.” Needless to say, human resources can provide training and clearly-stated virtual work agreements to help to mitigate these issues (Verbeke et al, 2008, p. 30).

Implementation Schedule

The implementation schedule also applies an action research approach to policy development as it “involves all stakeholders both in the questioning and sensemaking that informs” the development of the policies and procedures. (Reason & Bradbury, 2006, p. 2). At best, the development should rely on an iterative process whereby existing information is constantly refreshed by new ideas – and the policies development is readily available for review. Understandably, this approach requires technology to capture thoughts, analyze information and then present it for review. Notably, this implementation schedule provides some generic recommendations. That is to say, there are many job-related issues, laws and corporate goals to consider; thus, the development of the implementation schedules should also be unique per venue.

Human Resource Virtual Workforce Policy Development			
	Start Date	Day	Remaining
Task 1: Post Electronic Form: Input from Stakeholders (management, workforce, IT, accounting, etc.)	6/1/		
Task 1A: Host Roundtable discussions, forums, etc.			
Task 2: Webinar Presentations; Post Electronic Form for Feedback	7/15/	45	
Task 3: Post Initial Policy for Online Review	7/31/	61	
*Modify schedule if additional time needed for online review			
Task 4: Pilot Phase; Limited Number of Pre-Screened Participants	9/1/	90	
Task 5: Review Input from Pilot Phase	9/30/	120	
Task 6: Rewrite Policy, where needed.	10/15/	135	
Task 7: Post Revised Policy for Online Review	10/30/	150	
*Modify schedule if additional time needed for online review			
Task 8: Incremental Launch	12/1/	180	
Task 9: Full Launch	12/30/	210	
Task 10: Invite Continuous Feedback, Provide Periodic Updates and Training	1/1/	210	

Sustaining the Initiative

Unfortunately, some virtual work programs have resulted in failures or, as in the case of Yahoo!, the virtual work policy has been rescinded. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to discuss suggestions for revised policies and procedures as well as the reasons for continual alignment of the virtual office requirements and with strategic business objectives. The ultimate goal, to incorporate these changes into existing policies, will require change management and training.

Thus, the initiative will have been implemented on a solid foundation whereby multiple stakeholders are involved in the process; formal policies and procedures are in place to sustain

the initiative; and ongoing training and support is provided to ease the transition and any future modifications.

Moreover, as the initiative evolves, corporate strategies and objectives may change, as well. Therefore, human resources should invite continual feedback that, where applicable, should be analyzed and incorporated into existing policies and agreements.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that companies offer virtual work for a variety of reasons. Accordingly, a decision to have a virtual office workforce can affect many areas; including human resource operations, organizational efficiencies, external stakeholders, as well as the personal lives of employees (Verbeke et al, 2008, pp. 20-34). On the other hand, the option is frequently offered on an ad hoc basis; without formal policies or signed agreements in place. Generally, without the formal development, problems do develop.

Thus, management should be trained regarding their limitations in offering the option; particularly without the benefit of human resource development. Likewise, in situations where virtual work is not currently being considered, policies and procedures should clearly state that fact. With the announcement of the aforementioned situations at Yahoo! and Best Buy, the policy should probably also include a caveat whereby management may rescind the offer.

In addition to changes in the business requirements, companies need to also be aware of evolving technologies and changes to laws. To illustrate the breadth of these issues, even the United States Supreme Court has acknowledged the challenge of understanding “the implications of emerging technology before its role has become clear” in judicial decisions. (See e.g. *Olmstead v. United States*, 277 U.S. 438 (1928), overruled by *Katz v. United States*, 389 U.S. 347, 353 (1967)).

To summarize, the goal should be to research and identify whether there is a need for a virtual work option; then develop a feasible plan for implementing the policies and procedures; enforce an ongoing audit of the actual practice of the revised policies; and a plan for encouraging continual feedback from all stakeholders. Essentially, in an effort to avoid or at least to mitigate problems, human resource professionals need to partner with all stakeholders to address the issue accordingly. The outcome should include revised policies and procedures that continually align

business and human resource strategies and operations; thereby, providing guidelines for the transition to virtual office work – or a policy that clearly indicates that the option is not to be offered.

Appendix A: Facts and Figures (Retrieved From Manpower The World of Virtual Work Facts and Statistics) ([Click to Return](#))

While virtual offices (telecommuting) are on the increase worldwide, the area of concentration for this research will be the United States. The following are some facts, figures and reasons supporting the need for research.

- In a survey of 178 U.S. businesses with between 20 and 99 employees, the Yankee Group found that 79% had mobile workers, with an average of 11 mobile workers per company and 54% had telecommuters, with an average of eight telecommuters per company. (Source: Yankee Group)
- The number of Americans whose employer allows them to work remotely at least one day per month increased 63 percent, from 7.6 million in 2004 to 12.4 million in 2006. (Source: The Telework Advisory Group for World at Work - www.workingfromanywhere.org)
- The rising trend in the past two years is likely because of a combination of factors, including the proliferation of high speed/broadband and other wireless access (which has made it both less expensive and more productive to work remotely) and the willingness of more employers to embrace flexibility and work-life balance. (Source: Telework Advisory Group for World at Work: www.workingfromanywhere.org)
- It is estimated that 100 million U.S. workers will Telecommute by 2010. (Source: Kiplinger, 12/00)
- 22.2 million Americans worked from home or another out-of-office location at least one day per week in 2005. (Source: www.forbes.com 27/07/06)
- In 2003, there were 4.4 million Teleworkers working at home with broadband. By 2004, the number soared to 8.1 million, an 84% increase. (Source: 2004 American Interactive Consumer Survey conducted by The Dieringer Research Group)
- Teleworkers who worked at home during business hours at least one day per month increased in the past year from 23.5 million to 24.1 million, a 2.6% increase. Of that 24.1 million, 16.5 million are self employed, a 4.4% increase over 2003. This 24.1 million represents 18.3% of employed adult Americans, nearly one-fifth of the workforce. (Source: 2004 American Interactive Consumer Survey conducted by The Dieringer Research Group)
- The number of employed Americans who performed any kind of work from home, with a frequency range from as little as 1 day a year to full time, grew from 41.3 million in 2003, to 44.4 million in 2004, a 7.5% growth rate. (Source: 2004 American Interactive Consumer Survey conducted by The Dieringer Research Group)

Appendix B: Qualitative Interview Questionnaire ([Click to Return](#))

The qualitative interviews began with a brief overview of the project, and then proceeded with some of the following questions. The purpose of the qualitative data analysis was to encourage an open-ended conversation whereby the interviewee would share their experience, comments and observations of virtual work; therefore, the questions, along with the brief overview, were provided to simply encourage conversation. Ultimately, I wanted to avoid having the interviewee “agree with a statement just to avoid being disagreeable.” (Schutt 2009 p 265)

Questions

1. As an employee, do you view the virtual office as a benefit to the department, company? If yes, why and how? If no, why and how?

Or... As a manager, do you view the virtual office as a benefit to the department, company? If yes, why and how? If no, why and how?

2. If you are already working in a virtual office – either as an employee or as a manager – have you encountered any obstacles?

Or... Although you do not have experience working in a virtual office – either as an employee or as a manager – do you think that you might encounter some obstacles? If yes, please explain.

3. Based on the transition to virtual office work, I have noticed in my own experience plus in reviewing current research, that management is also changing. In some cases, virtual teams become self-managed. In others, the levels of management are changing.

In your experience as a virtual office worker, how, if at all, has management of your job changed? How and why?

As an employee without virtual office experience, would you expect management to change? How and why?

As a manager (with or without virtual office experience), what is your viewpoint on changes that management might have to address?

Appendix C: Virtual Employee Training Chart ([Click to Return](#))

From World At Work, Telework 2011, page 6 Retrieved From
<http://www.worldatwork.org/waw/adimLink?id=53034>

FIGURE 5a: Training for Employees

“Is training provided to employees about how to be successful as an employee with a flexible work arrangement?” (n = 455)

Appendix D: Training Management for Virtual Workforce Chart ([Click to Return](#))

From World At Work, Telework 2011, page 6 Retrieved From
<http://www.worldatwork.org/waw/adimLink?id=53034>

FIGURE 5b: Training for Managers

“Is training provided to managers about how to successfully manage employees with a flexible work arrangement?” (n= 455)

Appendix E: Work / Life Balance: Travel / Commute Time and Expense ([Click to Return](#))

In addition to the positive impact on the air quality as a result of the traffic reduction, “numerous states, as well as the federal government, are...rewarding firms who keep their workers off the roads.” Legislation is evolving; therefore, State or Local government Web sites will provide the most current information on tax reductions and incentives. (Fenson & Hill 2003 p 28)

Likewise, there is a savings on time and related travel expenses for the virtual office worker. The following is a **sample calculation** from the Oregon Office of Energy for savings on the hours of travel saved and gasoline costs: (Fenson & Hill 2003 p 267)

Proposed Start Date _____ Hrs. travel saved per week _____

of round trips per week **X** miles per round trip **X** miles per gallon = gallons saved per week.

Appendix F: Suggested Real Estate Calculations ([Click to Return](#))

Generally, the financial cost of maintaining real estate is one of primary concern. Then again, there is also the fact that some locations have no space available for another office building.

There are various methods to calculate the cost efficiency. For instance, the state of Arizona “points out that the reduction depends on the space occupied by the employee, the rental cost for the floor area required, and the slight increase in space required for shared office space for telecommuters when they are in the office.” (Fenson & Hill 2003 p 20)

Accordingly, Arizona has created the following **formula** to calculate the savings:

of virtual workers **X** average reduction of square feet per virtual worker **X** annual cost / square foot **X** % of space to be retained for virtual office workers when they are in the office

**Section Two:
Stand Alone Literature Review**

**Stand-Alone Literature Review:
The Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’)
Transnational Organization**

Abstract

In this *stand-alone literature review**, the specific topic, the evolving environment of hybrid (virtual offsite and traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organizations, is presented through the subtopics of organizational structure, design, management; and human resource policies and practices. The aim of the stand-alone literature review, defined as a detailed statement of what the review is intending to achieve, is to summarize, synthesize, and evaluate research regarding the impact of the hybrid (virtual offsite and traditional ‘brick and mortar’) practices in transnational organizations on structure, design, management, and human resources (Monash.edu, 2018).

* Whereas “a literature review that forms part of a research proposal or project also describes the gaps in the current knowledge that the project aims to address; a *stand-alone literature review* aims to summarize and evaluate the current knowledge of a specific topic” (Monash.edu, 2018).

Introduction to the Stand-Alone Literature Review

Bartlett and Ghoshal predict that, due to increased globalization, multinational organizations will need to embrace the transnational model. Their transnational approach invites the transfer of practices to, from and within the affiliates; parent organization and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others. There is high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 1989). This approach combines global and international strategies to “achieve local stability while rapidly absorbing and differing the parent company’s innovations” (Nirav, 2012).

Currently, there is an increase in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) options in transnational organizations. (See Appendix A: Global Trends in Telecommuting). This balance of a combination of virtual and traditional work and space offers

an opportunity for organizations, including transnationals, to improve productivity and to lower costs (Fortune Editors, 2011). (See Appendix B: Transnational Organizations / Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Options). Nevertheless, capturing that opportunity is predicated on recognizing that the ‘fit’ between internal processes, strategies, and structures; as well as the variety of external environments, is likely changing. That ‘fit’ is crucial as organizational success or failure is often explained by the ability or lack thereof to achieve a system that is adequate for the interdependence of the internal and external environments (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013).

Ultimately, the test will be to thrive while adapting to changes that are taking place around and within the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization. (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012). In consideration thereof, efforts must be made to develop “robust and resilient organizational systems capable of withstanding and responding to the uncertainties and challenges” (Bhamra, 2016, p. 4).

The topic for this stand-alone literature review is the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization. The aim, defined “as a detailed statement of what the review is intending to achieve”, is to describe the impact of the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) practices in transnational organizations on organizational structure; organizational design; organizational management; and human resource policies and practices (Monash.edu, 2018).

Review of Research Literature

Martins, Gilson, and Maynard (2004) concluded that “we have moved away from working with people who are in our visual proximity to working with people around the globe” (Ebrahim, Ahmed & Taha, 2009). The concept of physical placement continues to evolve as the hybrid (combined virtual / traditional) transnational organizations include the use of telework centers, collaborative online projects, and rotating schedules. The physical placement is further complicated in the transnational model as operations are guided by local context as well as by “close cooperation and interdependence among its headquarters, operations, and international subsidiaries” (Zwass, 1998). Hence, the introduction of a hybrid (virtual / traditional) setting in a transnational organization affects and is affected by an array of policies, procedures, and practices.

The stand-alone literature review explores prior research on the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational model. The aim of the stand-alone literature review, defined as a detailed statement of what the review is intending to achieve; is to summarize, synthesize, and evaluate research regarding the impact of the hybrid (virtual offsite and traditional ‘brick and mortar’) practices in transnational organizations on organizational structure, organizational design, management; and human resources (Monash.edu, 2018).

Organizational Structures (*Excerpts from Zeller, 2017*).

The transition from a traditional ‘brick and mortar’ organization to a combined virtual / traditional one questions the practicality of existing structures. For this section, the specific topic for review of prior research is the impact of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) environment on the organizational structure of transnational organizations. Accordingly, several research studies in this section of the stand-alone literature review identify that technology; in this case, particularly with its expanded use in the virtual / traditional venue, does have an influence on structure (Zeller, 2017).

Based on Bartlett and Ghoshal’s (1989) models of globalization, the transnational approach combines global and international strategies to “achieve local stability while rapidly absorbing and differing the parent company’s innovations” (Nirav, 2012). Within that goal, there is also a need for “coordination across multiple functions; e.g. products and geography” (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007, p. 212). Thus, the business is challenged as the components of transnational organizations are each empowered to become a source of specialized innovation as well as being “integrated into the overall corporate structure across several dimensions” (Reference for Business, n.d.).

Moreover, "organizations in which virtual-work arrangements thrive will be flatter than they are today” (Cascio, 2000, p. 89). In that context, “workers within these environments will have more autonomy and responsibility than in traditional organizations.” Nevertheless, “lines of authority, roles, & responsibilities will still need to be defined clearly" (Cascio, 2000, p. 89). Therefore, a proactive and ongoing review of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) venue will contribute toward identifying where structural change is required..

Fundamentally, restructuring requires key steps, including (1) preparing the organization, (2) rethinking the way that work is done, (3) restructuring the organization around the new business processes, and (4) implementing new information and measurement systems (Myers, Hulks, & Wiggins, 2012, p. 200). In organizational theory, the redesign of structure is viewed as a directed, ‘top-down’ initiative, one that is generally economic-based; or facilitated where staff members provide input to and shape the change (p. 194). The implementation of a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce presents the opportunity for a different approach to restructuring. In this case, instead of a directed, top-down initiative, the change may be based on the input, formal and informal, from the virtual and traditional workforce of the organization; thereby, shaping what needs to happen at the business process, job, and work level (p. 194).

Additionally, there are three interdependent activities in the virtualization part of the hybrid transnational organization: (1) networking through Information and Communications Technology (ICTs), (2) building a learning organization culture, and (3) restructuring (Dutton, 1999, as cited in Hemingway & Breu, 2003). Networking in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization is particularly problematic as methods and functions of communication are affected. A contributing factor is the change in the spatial environment from face-to-face or office-to-office to multiple work areas. In the spatial proximity of a hybrid traditional / virtual workforce, workers are no longer physically situated; i.e. by business process or department. Their physical location or spatial proximity is important as it is “interrelated in business practices” (Andersson & Mattsson, 2014, p. 2).

A study by “one of the most influential contributors to the Contingency School, Joan Woodward (1950-1959), focused on the relationship between organizational structure and organizational performance” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). The results of Woodward’s comparative empirical study (1950-1959) of 100 manufacturing organizations in England indicated that the “relationship between structure and performance surfaced only by introducing an extra variable: the type of technology” (Vector Study Group, n.d.). “In her later studies, Woodward (1970) emphasized how changes in markets led to product innovation which then led to changes in technology and subsequently organizational structures” (Hinings & Greenwood,

2017, p. 135). In the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization, both the use of technology and the global market can have a significant influence on structure (Zeller, 2017).

The main objective of Edward Harvey's research was to "relate organizational technology to organizational structure and to suggest some implications of this linkage for organizational decision-making"; i.e. the internal structure (Harvey, 1968, p. 249). Although organizational charts representing the structure were used to obtain information for the number of employees and the number of individuals in managerial and supervisory roles for Harvey's research, the charts were not assumed to be "reliable or valid indicators of actual arrangements" (p. 253). Pertinent to this review is the idea that the "the charts were discussed with members of management in an attempt to identify significant discrepancies between formal and informal arrangements" (p. 253). Furthermore, organizational theory researcher, Joan Woodward (1965, 1980), noted that "in some firms, role relationships prescribed by the chart; i.e. structure, seemed to be of secondary importance to personal relationships between individuals" (Woodward, 1958, p. 24).

For instance, the introduction of a hybrid workforce can be quite successful in achieving 'within division' project goals; however, organizational structures that are unable to accommodate any subsequent changes in end-to-end processes between divisions can be problematic (Morley, Cormican, & Folan, 2015). In an insurance firm transitioning to a hybrid workplace, the applications processed from the virtual office produced a bottle-neck of work for the next traditional 'brick and mortar' office based department. Subsequently, the reason for the overflow of work was discovered and changes were made to the job, work, and business processes, as well as the structure; e.g. report-to managers and supervisors (Zeller 2017).

That is, the structure may be challenged from the internal environment as standardized job, work, and business processes are changed. Likewise, the use of technology in a virtual offsite / traditional brick and mortar organization, affects the flow of information; thereby, frequently requiring restructuring. Hence, in their studies, Lawrence and Suddaby (2012) urge researchers to look behind the scenes of the outward appearance of permanent processes in the organization; and to focus on the gap between action (business processes) and organizational structure (Greenwood, Oliver, Sahlin, & Suddaby, 2012, Vol 5).

Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, and Choi (2012) promote that this mismatch of business processes and organizational structure in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization can prevent a company from reaching “operating achievements” (p. 5411). In prior studies where the focus of research was on business processes for traditional or virtual work, the emphasis for reaching operating achievements was on cutting time and expense. Any challenges regarding the interrelationship of hybrid job, work, and business processes with existing organizational structure were not considered (Hong et al., 2012, p. 5411). However, as is being seen in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) environments, the actual system of roles underlying the organizational processes can deviate from the scheduled processes that are the foundation for the formal organizational structure (Cordes-Berszinn, 2013).

While the changes brought on by the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) work complicate the integration or coordination across key organizational systems and structures, the hybrid environments are also known to encourage coordinating efforts to support adaptability and flexibility. The coordination of efforts toward flexibility should not stop at the specific area(s) of the business process directly using the hybrid environment—it needs to extend throughout the entire organization. On the other hand, some companies lack coordination on many levels; thus, the organization misses an opportunity to improve business processes, productivity, and profitability because revisions are not considered to be suitable for the existing structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012).

Though the use of technology influences the daily functions of the organizational structure; there is minimal systematic knowledge of whether or how technology has altered structural patterns or conditions that may lead to changes thereof (Tolbert & Hall, 2009). Realistically, the complexity of the internal and external environments coupled with the changing ways of work in a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) venue indicates that organizations can no longer remain attached to their processes and structure (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). Ultimately, in the twenty-first century, organizations and their structures will need to be able to recognize and to adapt to informal systems, such as those introduced in a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization,

to integrate new methods and ideas for growth in the evolving global market (Choi & Click, 2007).

Organizational Design (*Excerpts from Zeller, 2018a*).

The number of transnational organizations transitioning to the hybrid (combined virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) setting are increasing; thereby, sustaining the need to understand the impact on organizational design. (See Appendix B: Transnational Organizations / Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Options). The issue is identifying whether the changes introduced by the hybrid (hybrid / traditional) environment influence the existing organizational design. One possibility to be considered is that while existing formal designs may remain intact, the actual hybrid practices and processes portray a different organizational design. In addition, the question is whether the changes require a redesign to align internal and external environments (Zeller, 2018a). Realistically, though the design plays a critical role, “less than a quarter of organizational-redesign efforts succeed. And, forty-four percent run out of steam after getting underway, while a third fail to meet objectives or improve performance after implementation” (Aronowitz, De Smet, & McGinty, 2015).

Relevant to the topic on hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations is the theorists’ interest in “how new organizational designs arise and become established” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015). Organizational theorists, interested in a wide range of designs, are concerned with areas such as “governance capabilities (e.g., the ability to innovate, learn, and adapt), processes (e.g., decision making), and consequences (e.g., for whom)” (Greenwood & Hinings, 2015).

For example, the Classical Theories were best known for scientific management and bureaucratic structures; though, there was some recognition that organizations were flexible and that the hierarchy did not always know best. Classical Theorist, Mary Parker Follet (1924) identified factors that can be applied to the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization; e.g. it is not where work takes place but to “focus on the science of getting people to cooperate”; and instead of “power over, believe that genuine power is power with” (Mele & Rosanas, 2003). In the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organization, the place where work takes place affects business, work, and job processes (Zeller,

2017, 2018a). Thus, getting people to cooperate through the use of technology in a hybrid (virtual / traditional) venue requires a ‘power with’ approach; whereby, collective efforts are made to follow the existing organizational design or to recognize the need for revisions in areas such as interdepartmental end-to-end business, work, and job processes (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012). Ultimately, any mismatch may result in revised designs, formal or informal, to support the processes (Hong, Yonghyuk, Jinwoo, & Choi, 2012; Zeller, 2018a).

Later, the Neoclassical Theories “displayed genuine concern for human needs”; e.g. “creativity, individual growth, and motivation” (Walonick, 1993). In the 1940s, Kurt Lewin’s “force field theory viewed people’s activity as affected by forces in their surrounding environment, or field” (British Library, n.d.). Lewin identified two questions to ask when seeking to make changes within the framework of force field analysis: (1) Why does a process continue at its current level under the present circumstances? (2) What conditions would change these circumstances?” (British Library, n.d.). In the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations, revised job / work / business processes may be beneficial; however, they do not necessarily create value (Jeston & Nelis, 2008). Furthermore, outdated designs; e.g. bureaucracies and structural components, may slow responses (Werther, 1999). Whether the transnational organization adapts to the changing conditions, introduced by the hybrid (virtual / traditional) venue, or adheres to the existing design is the crux of the issue (Zeller, 2018a).

Renowned Contingency Theorist, Joan Woodward (1970), “argued that differences in the organization of work and in behavior at work could usually be traced to the immediate work situation itself” (Oxford Reference, n.d.). The behaviors include “the number of levels of management, areas of responsibilities of supervisors, division of functions among specialists, clarity with which roles and duties are defined, amount of written communication, and such like” (Oxford Reference, n.d.). These behaviors are subject to change with the introduction of a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace in a transnational organization; see e.g. Cascio, 2000 (management); Jeston & Nelis, 2008 (job / work functions); Cordes-Berszinn, 2013 (system of roles); and King, 2007 (communication).

The principles of Systems Theories, “introduced into the organizational setting by Katz and Khan in 1966,” (Foster, 2012) recognize organizations “as open systems that operate in an

open equilibrium” with “components that interrelate nonlinearly”. Thus, “making a small change in one variable impacts many others” (Wright, n.d.). This, too, is applicable in that many transnational organizations begin a hybrid (virtual / traditional) option without prior planning. After the fact, the ripple effect of the hybrid environment is known to impact the entire transnational organization; not simply the location and / or department(s) in which the option is offered (Zeller, 2017, 2018a).

Furthermore, Systems Theory views communication “as a system binder, crucial for the survival and growth of the organization. Binding the subsystems together facilitates internal stability and control. By binding the total system to the external environment, communication promotes organizational growth and goal attainment” (Almaney, 1974, Abstract). However, in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization, communication as a system binder is evolving as organizational communication has changed from a ‘top down’ voice to a multilevel one with multiple avenues for input. That is, the homophonic organization, where the code formed from the ‘top down’ is a given; has been replaced by the polyphonic organization that encourages listening for conversations from multiple sources in order to gain a broader understanding of the issues (Almaney, 1974).

The communication challenges are not limited to United States-based transnational organizations. In Japan, “teleworking is a key part of the government’s work-style reform”; hence, organizations are adjusting and adapting to these changes in their environment by facilitating “communication between those clocking in from home and those at the office” (Kyodo, 2018). For example, in organizations, such as Nippon Telegraph and Telephone East Corporation, a subsidiary of telecommunications giant Nippon Telegraph and Telephone Corporation, avatar robots are being used to smooth out the communication processes (Kyodo, 2018).

Correspondingly, boundary analysis is useful for understanding the design of hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations “and their working models as they often displace boundaries and redefine their meanings” (Hinds & Kiesler, 1995, as cited in Hemingway & Breu, 2003). Thus, the transition from a traditional to a hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization “requires an examination of the relationships between

organization level changes, described in terms of virtualization activities; and changes to the organization's working arrangements, described in terms of work units' boundary properties and activities" (Hemingway & Breu, 2003, Section 5 Discussion).

Certainly, due to the complexity and array of issues, the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization and its influence on organizational design requires ongoing research (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 146). Nevertheless, given the impact on productivity and profitability, revisions to design require a cautious approach to interpretation and action taken upon findings (Wilson, 2010).

Organizational Management (*Excerpts from Zeller, 2018b*).

This section of the stand-alone literature review will highlight management in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') transnational organization. Management theories are a "collection of ideas that provide the framework for effective management strategy" (Business.com, 2017). In practice, managers use "more than one theory in order to achieve productivity or organizational goals" (Business.com, 2017).

"Managing employees who don't report to the office also comes with a set of unique challenges, and overcoming them has become a top priority for many employers" (Fallon, 2014, para. 4). From a management viewpoint, the combination of virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar' methods introduces the feasibility of new capabilities, e.g. applications for tracking and controlling the workforce. These new capabilities also "allow companies to improve workload forecasting and resource scheduling directly" (Wang, de Kar, Meijer, & Sol, 2006, p. 44).

On the other hand, with the new capabilities; e.g. Information and Communication Technology; "managers have lost their exclusive authority or priority on accessing the information, thus failing to retain their superior positions in controlling resources and information." Additionally, "driven by a high degree of flexibility and participants", a virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar' workforce "can be differently composed every day, resulting in the collapse of manager's role in thoroughly monitoring and controlling subordinates' performance" (He, 2008, p. 15).

Thus, the first challenge for management in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization is ‘How can I manage if I can’t see them?’ Walking around the office to see what is being done is no longer an option. Hence, this challenge requires a transition from viewable, activities-based management to outcome or results-based (Cascio, 2000, p. 81). Accordingly, “[SHRM’s Global Diversity & Inclusion division] “advocates that companies should be managing by results, not ‘butts in seats’” (Meinert, 2011).

The second is “to overcome uncertainty about whether managers will still be valued by their companies if they are managing employees who are not physically present” (Cascio, 2000, p.81). Considering that transnational organizations have offices throughout the world, they are all virtual to some degree. Nevertheless, the actual practice of the virtual portion of the hybrid organization influences the perception of management and duties thereof.

In essence, organizations are struggling to understand how to manage the innovative processes introduced in hybrid (virtual offsite and traditional ‘brick and mortar’) transnational organizations. Some have even gone so far as to ask, “Can innovation be successful in the virtual / traditional workspace?” More often than not, Digital Age innovation requires expertise not yet clear (Logeski & Reilly, 2007, p. 5). Perhaps, aside from the technology, the crucial question is how to manage the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workforce (Zeller, 2018b).

Dr. Lillian Gilbreth (1911) recognized management challenges that remain significant in today’s workplace: 1) workers are motivated by indirect incentives (money) and by direct incentives (job satisfaction); 2) the effects of fatigue; and 3) stress on time management (SCSC.edu., n.d.). Dr. Gilbreth’s management challenges continue to be a factor in today’s hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization. For instance, the option to work virtually reduces fatigue and stress on time management in that it “allows employees to have better work-life balance and improves their health and wellness” (Vasel, 2017). There is also the financial indirect incentives in that it saves “more than \$4,000 each year thanks to reduced expenses on things like gas, parking and public transit costs and dry cleaning” (Vasel, 2017).

In 1916, the French engineer, Henry Fayol, “defined five functions of management for the management component” that are still considered relevant in today’s organizations (Van Vliet, 2011). These five functions, planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and

controlling; all focus on the relationship between the workforce and management. It is the last point, controlling, particularly in a hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, that has been a challenge for management. Controlling requires establishing performance standards based on organizational objectives, measuring and reporting on actual performance, comparing results with performance and standards, and taking corrective and preventive measures as needed (Van Vliet, 2011). Measuring the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science; and a combined virtual and traditional workforce presents additional challenges (Jeston & Nelis, 2008).

In the 1950s, Peter Drucker's interest in the behavior of people led to his development of the modern study of management. Drucker identified 5 basic tasks of managers: sets objectives, organizes, motivates and communicates, measures, and develops people (Murray, n.d.). For the most part, the 5 basic tasks continue to be a staple for managers. Nevertheless, some aspects of the basic tasks have changed in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace. In particular, Drucker's tasks of communication has become a challenge for managers of a hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization. In the hybrid, traditional / virtual workforce, communicating with workers no longer means walking down the hall to a meeting room. Instead, the managers must be able to adapt their perception of spatial dimensions and tap into whatever technology is needed to communicate effectively (Cummings, Espinosa, & Pickering, 2007; Ruth & Chaudhry, 2008).

In 1977, Alfred Chandler's *The Visible Hand: The Managerial Revolution in American Business*, replaced Adam Smith's (1776) invisible hand of market forces, with the visible hand of management. Whereas Smith's 'invisible hand' described "the unobservable market force that helps the demand and supply of goods" in a free market to reach equilibrium automatically (The Economic Times, n.d.); Chandler's 'visible hand' identifies the importance of the role of management in maintaining equilibrium (Zeller, 2018b). In the transnational organizations, the visible hand of management is expanding as managers now contend with a variety of work policy options; e.g. collocation, virtual, traditional, and any combination thereof. That combined with Smith's invisible hand of the global marketplace presents a formidable challenge for managers (Zeller, 2018b).

In summary, many managers simply don't know how to manage in a hybrid (virtual / traditional) organization. "Projects fail, and companies assume that the workers can't do the work," says Colleen Garton, author of *Managing without Walls*. But a high percentage of time, it's the manager." (King, 2007). Hence, there is a need for continual, well thought out revisions to and training for management policies and practices to address the virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar' venue in a transnational organization.

Human Resource Policies and Practices (*Excerpts from Zeller, 2013*).

This section of the stand-alone literature review will emphasize human resource policies and practices in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization; including key areas, such as job descriptions, performance appraisal, communication, and access to training / information. The crux of the issue is that most organizations don't plan to begin the virtual offsite part of the traditional 'brick and mortar' organization – it just happens as a result of need. Then, without updated human resource policies and practices to address the daily operations, managers and employees have little or no direction or procedures for recourse (Zeller, 2013).

To illustrate the issues, "when you think of a public relations person you rarely think of a shrinking violet, someone who can easily be ignored or even forgotten by their employer. But according to Cynthia N., a public relations specialist who teleworked from her home, that is exactly what happened. "They literally forgot about me. They put in this computer system and forgot to put me on the network... It didn't work with them at all. Cynthia also encountered psychological and social stressors; unable to separate work and home life and missing the camaraderie of other co-located employees, she eventually left the company. Unfortunately Cynthia's teleworking experience is not unusual" (Arling, 2004) .

Primarily, the standard functions of Human Resource Management; such as recruitment, hiring, wage conformity, training, continue. Currently though, the increase in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organizations has added a strategic dimension to the Human Resource functions. Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) aligns the goals and objectives of the worker with the corporate goals and objectives. Additionally, SHRM works toward differentiating the organization from its competitors; thereby, contributing significantly to the organization's long term success (HRDictionary, 2012). To complicate matters, "the evolution

of human resource management (HRM) into a global discipline”, such as in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization, is in various stages of development (Oxford Bibliographies, 2016). (See Appendix C: History of Human Resource Management.)

From the human resource perspective, the virtual / traditional option can be beneficial for several reasons; e.g. “employee attraction and retention, including situations where the candidate may not be willing to relocate to the company’s location;” (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 3, 5, 6). As for organizations, the current economic climate and globalization requires a reduction in the “cost of operations”, the ability to “attract and retain key talent”, and a corporate culture that encourages innovation to maintain the competitive edge. Alternatively, there are risks involved. For instance, revised policies; i.e. security, performance analysis, communications; may negatively affect the employee’s view of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) organization. Overall, Human Resource Management will need to work with all stakeholders to develop clearly-stated hybrid (virtual / traditional) policies to help to promote the benefits and to mitigate any issues (Verbeke, Schultz, Greidanus, & Hambley, 2008, p. 30).

That being considered, the development of human resource policies should begin with “an understanding as to why [virtual work] is being considered” (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 204). Then, “best practices” include that “the program is formal, explicit and sponsored by senior management; recognize that going mobile means changes to the way that work is done and how it is measured and rewarded; training is provided for managers and virtual office workers; and there is an effective use of collaboration technology” (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 7). Moreover, human resources can not overlook the changing growth and development needs of the virtual / traditional workforce. In this case, revisions to practices may be needed to insure that virtual workers are included for training programs, promotions, and meetings (Zeller, 2013).

In addition, revising job analysis and descriptions prior to offering a hybrid virtual / traditional policy is prudent from a business and legal viewpoint. For example, companies can avoid “discrimination charges of ‘favoritism’ when offering” positions with the development and consistent practice of a formal selection process for virtual office assignments. Minimally, issues that will need to be acknowledged include policies and practices for applications, assessments, and home office evaluations (Fenson & Hill, 2003).

Furthermore, Human Resource Managers would do well to keep abreast of changes to the laws (Fenson & Hill, 2003, p. 259). Where human resource practices, policies and procedures may not have been revised to address changes, the mismatch can result in litigation. Thus, since “ad hoc arrangements are liable to leave companies open to legal liability for workmen’s compensation, and for potential violations of the Fair Labor Standards Act, the importance of aligning human resource and business operational and strategic goals is further emphasized” (Ware & Grantham, 2010, p. 2).

Even with revised job / work / business process designs, the hybrid work option may not be suitable. Drawing on the experiences of Fortune 500 companies to identify the business reason advantages and disadvantages for the hybrid work options, Cascio (2000) maintained that although all indications are that the hybrid (virtual / traditional) environment will grow; human resources may need to determine when the virtual portion of the hybridity may not be appropriate for the job (p. 81).

The text titled *Growing the Virtual Workplace* (Verbeke, Schultz, Greidanus, & Hambley, 2008) suggests that “managers and employees work together to define performance goals and provide regular feedback to each other.” The performance analysis should include “the employee’s performance both as a worker and as a virtual office worker” (Verbeke, Schultz, Greidanus, & Hambley, 2008, p 24). Chapter 3, *Telework Impacts: The Organizational Perspective*, also identifies strategic and operational human resource issues; such as, the impact on recruiting, retention, knowledge sharing (communication), and absenteeism.

Implementing and Managing Telework (Fenson & Hill, 2003) explores virtual work from many viewpoints; including human resources, organizational requirements, and security issues. The information can be used to develop guidelines for the transition from traditional to a virtual / traditional organization – or for developing a policy that clearly indicates that the option is not to be offered. For employers developing a human resource policy for a virtual / traditional workforce, the appendices also provide templates for evaluations, virtual office worker / employer agreements, and follow-up surveys.

From a strategic human resource perspective, the evolving nature of the hybrid (virtual / traditional) transnational organization requires preliminary and ongoing analysis with internal

and external stakeholders in order to fully support the endeavor (Helms and Raiszadeh, 2002, as cited in Verbeke, Schultz, Greidanus, & Hambley, 2008, p. 44). In addition, the standard human resource practices; e.g. the identification of changing roles and business, work, and job practices will require revisions to formal policies.

Conclusion

The aim of the stand-alone literature review, defined “as a detailed statement of what the review is intending to achieve”, was to describe the impact of the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) practices in transnational organizations on organizational structure, design, and management; and on human resource policies and practices.

The hybrid (virtual / traditional) practices, particularly the technology, complicate the integration or coordination across key organizational systems and structures. However, based on the literature reviewed, there is minimal systematic knowledge of whether or how the use of technology has altered structural patterns or conditions that may lead to changes thereof. Thus, the transnational organizations, implementing a hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional ‘brick and mortar’) option, will need to proactively identify changed operations, processes, and procedures and any influence on their structure.

Another issue identified by the research is how practices introduced by the hybrid (virtual / traditional) venue, with the transnational approach that promotes integration, differentiation, and the empowered components; influence design. In this case, while the formal design may remain intact; the actual design after implementation of the hybrid venue may differ across regions, divisions, and departments. Though change may be indicated, given the impact on productivity, revisions to design require a cautious approach to interpretation and action taken upon findings. Overall, the test of the design will be to achieve the right combination of differentiation and integration in the organization’s operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in the environment.

Managing employees who don’t report to the office also comes with a set of unique challenges, and overcoming them has become a top priority for many employers. Considering that transnational organizations have offices throughout the world, the workforce is all virtual to

some degree. Nevertheless, the actual practice of the virtual portion of the hybrid transnational organization influences the perception of management and duties thereof. Hence, there is also a need for well thought out revisions to and training for management policies and practices to address the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') venue.

Whereas the role Human Resource Managers continues to include the standard practices of personnel management; e.g. recruiting, hiring, training, salaries/wages; the current Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) role is much more critical. Fundamentally, Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) aligns the goals and objectives of the worker with the corporate goals and objectives as well as works toward differentiating the organization from its competitors; thereby, contributing significantly to the organization's long term success. With the expanding roles, SHRM is in a position to proactively identify, bring attention to, and act on revisions in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) venue. Alternatively, SHRM, coordinating with internal and external stakeholders, may also determine that a hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy may not be suitable.

Whether the transnational organization decides to implement a hybrid (virtual / traditional) policy as a top-down directive or if one department manager decides to allow individual employees to work virtually, the literature reviewed indicates that the practices can have an impact on many different areas. Therefore, the decision requires initial and ongoing input from internal and external stakeholders, with revisions to organization-wide policies and practices to support the initiative.

Appendix A: Global Trends in Telecommuting

Asia Pacific Region (From

<https://www.jobstreet.com.ph/career-resources/telecommuting-company-ready#.XG1iPkxFzIU>)

In the Asia Pacific region, for those who commute to work, majority of these employees experienced round trips between 45 and 60 minutes or more on a daily basis. With commutes like these, it should become a no brainer for anyone to choose to work from home if they had been given a choice. However, the survey further revealed that despite qualifying as teleworkers, most teleworkers in the region reported that they are still spending majority of their time in the office with only 68% of them working from home in just one day or less in a typical telework week.

India (From <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-telecommuting-idUSTRE80N1IL20120125>)

According to IPSOS/Reuters, telecommuting is particularly popular in India where more than half of workers were most likely to be working from home.

Japan (From

<https://qz.com/935374/japans-office-managers-are-experimenting-with-this-radical-new-trend-called-remote-working/>

According to a survey conducted by the Ministry of International Affairs and Communications and released last summer (link in Japanese, pdf, p19), the percentage of companies that allowed telecommuting in some form in 2015 increased to 16.2%, compared with 11.4% the year before. Companies said their main reasons for introducing telecommuting were to improve efficiency and to reduce employees' commuting time (which can sometimes involve being pushed into crammed trains by transport workers).

Portugal (From https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/5628/1/MPRA_paper_5628.pdf)

In the software sector, teleworking practices are more visible than in the other sectors studied. In the so-called “traditional” sectors, teleworking practices and dynamics are more hidden or covered up. In these sectors the use of information and communication technologies is relatively low, limited to information and communication channels and terminals. However, modernization processes in these sectors let us foresee that there is the possibility of a quick spreading of the capability to use these new forms of working within a relatively short period of time.

South Africa (From <https://www.skillsportal.co.za/content/7-hr-trends-south-africa>)

Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU) Business School today released seven trend predictions for human resources management, workplace dynamics and executive education in South Africa for 2016. One of the seven is: Telecommuting, shrinking office spaces, a growing body of literature around unproductive open-plan office spaces, and new computer-mediated communication technologies are shifting employee preferences to flexible workplaces. In fact, in view of the talent shortages, we believe that organizations with flexible working policies and arrangements will become the most attractively positioned companies for top talent.

United States (From <https://chiefexecutive.net/top-10-technology-trend-predictions-for-2019/>)

According to Global Workplace Analytics, 25% of the US workforce teleworks at least part of the time, yet 50% holds jobs that are compatible with remote work. What's more: 80-90% of the US workforce says they would *like* to telework at least part time. When you zoom in on Millennials – who will make up 75% of the global workforce by 2025 – that percentage jumps to 95.

Appendix B: Transnational Organizations / Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Options

Business Demographics

Based on information provided by CNN Money, “100 Best Companies to Work For” (2011), of the 82 Best Companies that allow employees to telecommute or work at home at least 20% of the time; the following 10 companies have the highest percentage of telecommuters. (From <http://money.cnn.com/magazines/fortune/bestcompanies/2011/benefits/telecommuting.html>)

Companies	Rank of Best Companies	% of Regular Telecommuters
<i>Deloitte</i>	<i>63</i>	<i>86%</i>
<i>Cisco</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>85%</i>
<i>Intel</i>	<i>51</i>	<i>82%</i>
<i>Accenture</i>	<i>99</i>	<i>80%</i>
<i>Teach for America</i>	<i>82</i>	<i>80%</i>
<i>Pricewaterhouse Coopers</i>	<i>73</i>	<i>70%</i>
<i>Brocade Comm. Systems</i>	<i>89</i>	<i>50%</i>
<i>S. C. Johnson & Son</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>40%</i>
<i>Stryker</i>	<i>68</i>	<i>38%</i>
<i>American Fidelity Assurance</i>	<i>39</i>	<i>37%</i>

United States-based Hybrid (Combined Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’ Office)
Transnational Organizations

2016 Top 10 Telecommute-Friendly Companies: Based on High Frequency and Variety of Telecommute Jobs From <https://www.virtualvocations.com/blog/telecommuting-news/virtual-vocations-2016-year-end-report/>

- UnitedHealth Group, Minneapolis, MN
- IBM, Armonk, NY
- Dell, Inc, Round Rock, TX
- Xerox Corp, Norwalk, CT
- Salesforce.com, San Francisco, CA
- Humana, Inc, Louisville, KY
- Oracle Corp, Redwood Shores, CA
- Connections Academy, Baltimore, MD
- K12 Inc, Herndon, VA
- Kaplan, Inc, Fort Lauderdale, FL

Appendix C: History of Human Resource Management.

From Evolution of Human Resource Management (2012)

<https://hrdictionaryblog.com/2012/10/28/evolution-of-human-resource-management/comment-page-1/>

Strategic Human Resource Management Approach

With increase in technology and knowledge base industries and as a result of global competition, Human Resource Management is assuming more critical role today. Its major accomplishment is aligning individual goals and objectives with corporate goals and objectives. Strategic HRM focuses on actions that differentiate the organization from its competitors and aims to make long term impact on the success of organization.

Evolution of HRM ...

Glossary

The term 'hybrid' can refer to organizational structure or technology / manufacturing designs or, as applied in this study, to where people work; i.e. traditional physical office or virtual location. The interchangeable use of the terms job / work design causes some confusion. In addition, the interpretation of several variables introduced in the Literature Review studies are identified as context dependent; thereby, producing different results. Thus, the researcher's understanding of the variable, the literal interpretation, as well as the context of the study, can influence results, analysis thereof, and the decisions that are based on those results.

Hybrid Organization: For these studies, a hybrid organization will refer to a design that includes virtual offsite and traditional physical offices.

Hybrid Work Environment: For this study, a hybrid work environment will refer to a combination of physical and virtual workspace / scheduling in a multinational organization.

Organization: The term 'organizations' is "a social unit of people that is structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals. All organizations have a management structure that determines the relationships between the different activities and the members and subdivides and assigns roles, responsibilities, and authority to carry out different tasks.

Organizations are open systems — they affect and are affected by their environment" (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational Design: Organizational design, a central concept of organization theory, is defined in several ways. Frequently, it is defined as "the manner in which a management achieves the right combination of differentiation and integration of the organization's operations, in response to the level of uncertainty in its external environment" (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). "Differentiation refers to the subdivision of functional or departmental units, each concentrating on a particular aspect of the organization's operations. Integration refers to the linking of differential units to achieve unity of effort in working toward the organization's goals" (Business Dictionary.com). In addition, it is defined as "a formal process of integrating people, information and technology together in the right mix to achieve objectives" (Study.com, n.d.). Organizational design is also a step-by-step methodology which can be applied to "identify

dysfunctional aspects of workflow, procedures, structures and systems, realign them to fit current business realities/goals and then used to develop plans to implement the new changes” (Allen, n.d.).

Organizational Management: Management is defined as ‘the organization and coordination of the activities of a business in order to achieve defined objectives” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). Organizational management is “the process of organizing, planning, leading, and controlling resources within an entity with the overall aim of achieving its objectives. The organizational management of a business needs to be able to make decisions and resolve issues in order to be both effective and beneficial” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.). Management theories are a “collection of ideas that provide the framework for effective management strategy” (Business.com, 2017). Generally, managers use “more than one theory in order to achieve productivity or organizational goals” (Business.com, 2017).

Organizational Strategy: "An expression of how an organization needs to evolve over time to meet its objectives along with a detailed assessment of what needs to be done" (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational Structure: According to Mintzberg (1972), “organizational structure is the framework of the relations on jobs, systems, operating process, people and groups making efforts to achieve the goals” (Ahmady, Mehrpour, & Nikooravesh, 2016). Basically, “organizational structure determines how the roles, power, and responsibilities are assigned, controlled, and coordinated, and how information flows between the different levels of management” (Business Dictionary.com, n.d.).

Organizational Theory: Organizational theory is “the study of organizational designs and organizational structures, relationship of organizations with their external environment, and the behavior of managers and technocrats within organizations. It suggests ways in which an organization can cope with rapid change” (BusinessDictionary.com, n.d.).

Business-Related Terms

Business Process: a term credited to Adam Smith, 1776; “a set of activities and tasks that, once accomplished, will accomplish an organizational goal” (Appian, 2016).

Productivity: will refer to the amount of work that the traditional and virtual workers complete in a specific timeframe; such as within one work day. The workers' experience will not be considered; that is, the differences in productivity of new and experienced workers will not be identified. Efficiency, such as the increase in errors / accuracy, will also not be indicated (Ingram, n.d.).

Job Design: The variable 'job design' is frequently used interchangeably with the variable 'work design'. Generally, job design is the functional daily role of the process (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390).

Work Design: The variable 'work design' is frequently used interchangeably with the variable 'job design'. Generally, the work design will be defined as work that "goes beyond individual jobs to the organization of groups of workers" (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005, p. 390).

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